

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

**AI-Driven Predictive Intelligence for
Detection and Early Warning of Unseen
Cyberthreats in 5G/6G Networks**

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate the following lines to many people, to all those who have been with me throughout this journey that has been my PhD. Brother and sister, friends, my scout groups... there have been many connections that have helped me for a long time and have always maintained that loving and affectionate contact that anyone could wish for. However, there are two people in particular who deserve special attention in these lines, to whom more than dedicating the development of this thesis, I must, have and will thank them for all that they are.

Thank you for asking me every week if I have eaten well. Thank you for always being concerned about my state of mind and health, even if sometimes I am a bit inaccessible with my answers. Thank you for the culinary tips to keep me healthy. Thank you for the phone calls and tutorials to fix the bike that allowed me to live a regular life. Thank you for being an example of tireless effort and work. Lifting the shutters at four o'clock in the morning from Monday to Sunday, for more than 30 years, has not been enough for you to give us everything you wanted for us. Writing these lines I realise why I identify with the article of the Scout Law which says: "The Scout is responsible and leaves nothing half done". Thank you for loving me and for having loved me during all these years, because knowing and feeling loved is my cure and treatment. Thanks to you, I have reached where I am, proud of my achievements. Thank you mum. Thank you dad.

Dedicatoria

Desearía dedicarle las siguientes líneas a muchas personas, a todos aquellos que han estado conmigo a lo largo de este viaje que ha supuesto mi doctorado. Hermanos, amigos, mis grupos scouts, han sido muchas las conexiones que me han ayudado durante mucho tiempo y han mantenido siempre ese contacto cariñoso y afectivo con el que cualquiera podría desear. Sin embargo, hay dos personas en particular que merecen especial atención en estas líneas, a las cuales más que dedicarles el desarrollo de esta tesis, debo, tengo y voy a agradecerles por todo lo que ellos son.

Gracias por preguntarme todas las semanas si he comido bien. Gracias por preocuparos siempre por mi estado de ánimo y de salud, aunque a veces sea un poco inaccesible con mis respuestas. Gracias por los consejos culinarios para mantenerme sano. Gracias por las llamadas-tutoriales para arreglar la bici que me permitió hacer vida regularmente. Gracias por ser ejemplo de incansable esfuerzo y trabajo. Levantar la persiana a las cuatro de la mañana de lunes a domingo, durante más de 30 años, no ha sido suficiente para vosotros para darnos todo aquello que deseábais para nosotros. Escribiendo estas líneas me doy cuenta de por qué me siento identificado con el artículo de la Ley Scout que dice: “El Scout es responsable y no deja nada a medias”. Gracias por quererme y haberme querido durante todos estos años, porque saberse y sentirse amado es mi cura y tratamiento. Gracias a vosotros, he llegado a donde estoy, orgulloso de mis logros. Gracias mamá. Gracias papá.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis and the work presented in it are my own and has been generated by me as the result of my own original research. This thesis contains no material that has been submitted previously, in whole or in part, for the award of any other academic degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Pablo Benlloch-Caballero

September 2024

This doctoral thesis has been funded by two large European H2020 research projects in which the candidate has been actively involved, carrying out tasks of design, prototyping, implementation and deployment of innovative advanced network automation capabilities on software data path in Beyond 5G multi-tenant architectures:

- **Project 1: ARCAIDAN-IoT**

Project Title	ARCADIAN-IoT (Autonomous trust, security and privacy management framework for IoT)
Horizon 2020 Call	H-SU-DS02-2020
Topic	Intelligent security and privacy management
Type of action	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Duration	36 Months
Start date	01/05/2021
End date	30/04/2024
Budget	+5.8 million €
Description	The ARCADIAN-IoT project aims to develop and make available an innovative, advanced, solid framework for trust, security and privacy management for IoT systems. The ARCADIAN-IoT framework will accelerate the development of IoT systems towards decentralized, transparent and user controllable privacy in three real use cases.
Consortium	University of the West of Scotland (UK) Instituto Pedro Nunes (PT) ATOS (SP) E-LEX (IT) LOAD (PT) Martel Innovate (SWTZ) RGB (SP) RISE (SWDN) BOX2M (ROM) ONE-GLOBAL (PT) Universidad de Navarra (SP) XLAB (SVN)

- **Project 2: RIGOUROUS**

Project Title	RIGOUROUS (secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsth-woRthy cOntinUum computing 6G Services)
Horizon 2020 Call	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022
Topic	Secure Service development and Smart Security
Type of action	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Duration	36 Months
Start date	01/01/2023
Budget	+4.5 million €
Description	The onset of 6G (sixth-generation wireless) technologies has reaffirmed the need for improved and efficient security and privacy when these technologies finally arrive. The EU-funded RIGOUROUS project aims to improve the security, privacy and trust present in both 6G and other novel computing technologies and services. To do so, it will develop an innovative smart service framework that will make software and AI parts comply with security requirements throughout their development and up to launch while detecting and stopping security breaches. The project is also researching possibilities to improve the secure and efficient automation of security management.
Consortium	University of the West of Scotland (UK) Orange Romania SA (ROM) Lenovo Deutschland GMBH (GER) Starion Luxembourg SA (LXM) EBOS Technologies Limited (CYPR) WINGS ICT (GRC) One Source Consultoria Informatica LDA (PT) ICTFICIAL OY (FIN) OULUN YLIOPISTO (FIN) Instituto de Telecomunicacoes (PT)

The research work presented in this thesis has been disseminated through publications accepted and published in recognized international journals and conferences, where the PhD candidate is listed as the first and primary author. This confirms that the PhD candidate has made the major contributions to all publications included in this thesis. The following is a detailed list of the published research outcomes:

Journal	Computer Networks
Title	Distributed dual-layer autonomous closed loops for self-protection of 5G/6G IoT networks from distributed denial of service attacks
Authors	Pablo Benlloch-Caballero, Qi Wang and Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero
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DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2022.109526
URL	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S138912862005606
Abstract	<p>Internet of Things (IoT) is a major application area of the Fifth-Generation (5G) and beyond capable of providing massive machine-type communications (mMTC) at a large scale. It enables a wide range of applications such as smart cities, smart grids, smart factories and so on. In light of the huge number of devices involved, it is prohibitive to manage the massive large-scale cyber security scenarios manually. Therefore, closed automation loops are essential to automate such management. This paper proposes a new cognitive closed loop system to offer distributed dual-layer self-protection capabilities to battle against Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks. The proposed system features the novel usage of concurrent autonomous closed-loops for the different stakeholders' business roles: Digital Service Providers (DSPs) and Infrastructure Service Providers (ISPs) respectively, suitable to provide a multi-layer self-protection defence mechanisms across multiple administrative domains. It has been designed, implemented and experimentally validated. Empirical results have shown that there is a high potential in the collaboration between the stakeholders to achieve the common goal of self-protection of infrastructures. It makes a major difference in the performance of the whole infrastructure for detecting, analysing and mitigating the threat when the proposed distributed dual-layer loops are applied instead of a standalone loop. The system has achieved a 78.12% of effectiveness compared with a 4.73% of the standalone counterpart, for a large scale attack when stopping 256 infected devices. Also, the proposed system has achieved a response time of 18 s whereas the standalone has required 57 s, achieving an optimization of performance of 316%.</p>

Conference	2023 IEEE 31st International Conference on Network Protocols (ICNP)
Title	Topology-Aware Cognitive Self-Protection Framework for Automated Detection and Mitigation of Security and Privacy Incidents in 5G-IoT Networks
Authors	Pablo Benlloch-Caballero, Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro, Antonio Matencio-Escolar, Jose M. Alcaraz Calero, Qi Wang
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DOI	10.1109/ICNP59255.2023.10355595
URL	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10355595
Abstract	<p>Internet of Things (IoT) coupled with 5G networks enable unprecedented levels of scalability and performance in the computing industry. These enhanced performance features allow to offer and deploy a wide range of new use cases and services in scenarios such as Smart Cities, Smart Grid or Industry 5.0 just to mention a few. However, the inherent complexity of such networks is a serious concern in terms of security. Furthermore, the vulnerability and low-power constraints of IoT devices make such networks a targeted vector for cyber criminals. In this contribution, authors present an innovative topology-aware Cognitive Self-protection framework able to detect and mitigate attacks in an autonomous way with no human intervention in the wired segments of 5G-IoT multi-tenant networks. Preliminary tests carried out on a realistic emulated testbed show promising results in terms of time spent in stopping DDoS attacks (less than 47 seconds) and scalability for scenarios with different number of tenants and UEs (2 virtual tenants deployed in 4 Edge nodes and up to 64 IoT devices or sensors connected to the infrastructure).</p>

Conference	2025 IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning for Communication and Networking (ICMLCN)
Title	Enhanced Protection of 5G-IoT and Beyond Infrastructures: Evolving Intelligent Strategies for DDoS Attack Multiclass Classification
Authors	Pablo Benlloch-Caballero, Jose M. Alcaraz Calero, Qi Wang
Status	Under review
Australian Conference Ranking	CORE -
Date of Conference	26–29 May 2025
Location	Barcelona, Spain
Electronic ISSN	–
DOI	–
URL	–
Abstract	<p>In the evolving landscape of next-generation networks beyond 5G, the persistent threat of multiple cyber attacks remains one of the main concerns. 5G-IoT networks enable the deployment of use cases involving a huge number of constrained and vulnerable IoT devices, making them an attractive target for hackers to exploit with Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks (e.g. botnets) and thus increasing the attack surface. Consequently, 5G infrastructures and service providers are tasked with creating robust systems able to detect and mitigate these threats. To tackle this challenge, the presented research paper aims to address these concerns by introducing a novel dataset gathered by monitoring 5G-IoT multi-tenant traffic with multiple nested encapsulation headers. Featuring six distinct network traffic classes tailored for Machine Learning (ML) model classification, our dataset provides a comprehensive understanding of network behaviour. Leveraging aggregated features and metrics of 5G-IoT network flows across various topological scenarios. Furthermore, among the multiple ML models studied in this research, the Histogram Gradient Boost Classifier (HGBC) outperformed, renowned for its resilience on different network topology scenarios, to effectively classify network flows and bolster defence mechanisms against potential attacks. The achieved F1 scores by the HGBC in both scenarios presented in this paper are 99.42% and 98.62%.</p>

Journal	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management
Title	Automated Framework for B5G network topology emulation and experiment execution
Authors	Pablo Benlloch-Caballero, Pablo Salva-Garcia, Qi Wang and Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero
Status	Under review
JCR Impact (Journal Citation Report)	4.7
Volume	–
Issue	–
Pages	–
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Electronic ISSN	–
DOI	–
URL	–
Abstract	<p>This paper presents CORE eXecutor (COREX), an innovative architecture designed to automate the deployment of emulated Beyond 5G (B5G) network topologies. COREX efficiently provisions network resources on the host machine, deploys the necessary software components to network nodes, and orchestrates a range of experiments, such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, to assess network performance. Key features of COREX include a robust orchestration framework that operates across the host, emulator, and network nodes, automation of B5G topology deployment, and the capability to switch between various predefined use cases. Additionally, it supports the distribution and coordination of network topologies over multiple physical hosts. The experimental evaluation demonstrates COREX's scalability and efficiency, particularly in distributed setups. As the number of User Equipment (UE) increases, execution times range from 699 to 1191 seconds, with the distributed setup delivering superior bandwidth performance. While standalone experiments experience bandwidth reductions under heavy loads, distributed setups consistently achieve higher bandwidth utilization, maintaining up to 99.93% at lower loads and 51% at higher loads. In cybersecurity experiments, COREX automates the detection, planning, and mitigation of threats, offering a comprehensive self-protection mechanism. The framework's robust architecture, enhanced automation, and scalability make it a valuable tool for large-scale B5G network emulations, facilitating seamless orchestration across multiple machines and reducing manual intervention.</p>

Acronyms

4G 4th Generation. 39, 95, 98, 124, 125

5G 5th Generation. 1, 2, 5, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 38, 39, 40, 41, 43, 53, 54, 64, 65, 69, 82, 83, 88, 95, 96, 97, 98, 99, 100, 101, 103, 105, 109, 110, 111, 114, 115, 117, 118, 119, 121, 122, 123, 124, 125, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 133, 140, 141, 143, 152, 155, 156, 157, 158, 159, 160, 162, 164, 176, 177, 179, 190, 191, 192, 196, 197, 198

5GPPP 5G Infrastructure Private Public Partnership. 119

5GS 5G System. 1

6G 6th Generation. 1, 12, 38, 43, 53, 61, 62, 117, 118, 119, 121, 122, 123, 127, 152, 182, 187, 191, 196, 198

AAS Asset Administration Shell. 64

AI Artificial Intelligence. 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 43, 49, 51, 52, 57, 58, 59, 65, 153, 158, 179, 182, 183, 192, 197, 198

AMF Access Management Function. 39, 100, 119

API Application Programming Interface. 67

AUC Area Under the ROC Curve. 171, 172

B5G Beyond the 5th Generation. 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 22, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 33, 34, 35, 36, 38, 39, 40, 41, 44, 49, 50, 51, 53, 57, 58, 59, 61, 62, 63, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 73, 74, 78, 79, 80, 81, 84, 90, 91, 92, 93, 96, 115, 134, 135, 136, 137, 166, 168, 182, 183, 184, 185, 186, 188, 192, 195, 196, 198

CNN Convolutional Neural Network. 55, 124, 158

COREX CORE eXecutor. 62, 63, 66, 67, 68, 69, 71, 73, 74, 77, 78, 79, 80, 82, 83, 84

C-RAN Core-RAN. 40

CORE Common Open Research Emulator. 18, 20, 21, 22, 35, 36, 37, 62, 65, 66, 69, 74, 79, 105, 106, 115, 124, 140, 141, 142, 153, 157, 159, 189, 196

CPRI Common Public Radio Interface. 39, 128, 138

- CU** Central Unit. 26, 119, 160
- DB** Database. 11, 41, 73, 74, 76, 77, 140, 166, 167, 192
- DDoS** Distributed Denial of Service. 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 14, 16, 27, 55, 63, 71, 79, 80, 81, 82, 85, 87, 88, 89, 91, 98, 102, 104, 105, 109, 110, 111, 113, 115, 117, 118, 121, 122, 124, 125, 131, 140, 142, 144, 146, 150, 152, 153, 155, 156, 158, 159, 162, 184, 186, 190, 191, 192, 196, 197
- DL** Deep Learning. 98, 124, 157, 159, 179
- DSC** Datapath Security Controller. 103
- DSP** Digital Service Provider. 29, 39, 40, 41, 50, 52, 71, 75, 76, 96, 105, 118, 119, 120, 121, 122, 126, 127, 128, 138, 139, 141, 143, 144, 145, 151, 160, 190
- DTC** Decision Tree Classifier. 159
- DU** Distributed Unit. 26, 39, 100, 119, 160
- ECP** Evolved Packet Core. 43
- ERC** Emulator Resource Controller. 66, 67, 69, 74, 79
- ETC** ExtraTrees Classifier. 55, 56, 169, 170, 171, 176, 179, 185, 197
- ETNO** European Telecommunications Network Operators' Association. 155
- FFN** Feed Forwarded Neural Network. 157
- FMA** Flow Monitoring Agent. 134
- GENEVE** Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation protocol. 26, 39, 40, 76, 122
- gNB** Next Generation NodeB. 39, 105, 141, 160
- GRE** Generic Routing Encapsulation protocol. 26, 39, 40, 76, 96, 101, 106, 114, 122, 196
- GTP** GPRS Transport Protocol. 26, 39, 40, 71, 96, 101, 106, 114, 126, 127, 128, 138, 143, 156, 162, 196
- GUI** Graphical User Interface. xxix, xxxi, 19, 35, 36, 41, 141, 145
- HGBC** HistGradBoost Classifier. 55, 56, 157, 169, 170, 171, 172, 176, 177, 179, 185, 192, 197, 198
- HRC** Host Resource Controller. 66, 67, 69, 79
- IaaS** Infrastructure as a Service. 96

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- ICMP** Internet Control Message Protocol. 14, 162, 163, 176, 184
- IDS** Intrusion Detection System. 45, 97, 99, 102, 125, 131, 158, 164
- IoT** Internet of Things. 1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 30, 38, 39, 43, 54, 55, 95, 96, 97, 98, 99, 100, 103, 105, 106, 107, 108, 109, 110, 111, 114, 115, 117, 118, 119, 121, 122, 123, 124, 125, 127, 140, 141, 142, 143, 144, 152, 155, 156, 157, 159, 160, 162, 177, 179, 183, 184, 185, 186, 190, 191, 196, 197
- IP** Internet Protocol. 28, 54, 65, 96, 104, 122, 124, 128, 142, 143, 144
- ISP** Infrastructure Service Provider. 40, 41, 50, 52, 71, 75, 76, 77, 105, 119, 121, 122, 125, 126, 127, 128, 129, 138, 139, 140, 142, 143, 144, 145, 149, 151
- LC** Logging Controller. 67
- LiFi** Light Fidelity. 57
- LLDP** Link Layer Discovery Protocol. 64, 95, 124, 140
- LSTM** Long Short-Term Memory. 55, 98, 124, 158, 159, 179
- MAC** Medium Access Control. 119, 142, 166
- MEC** Mobile/Multi-access Edge Computing. 40, 100, 119
- ML** Machine Learning. xxvii, 2, 3, 5, 6, 15, 16, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 34, 43, 54, 55, 58, 92, 98, 123, 125, 156, 157, 158, 159, 163, 167, 168, 169, 171, 176, 179, 185, 186, 192, 197
- MLP** Multilayer Perceptron. 125, 159
- MTU** Maximum Transmission Unit. 104, 147, 162, 166
- NBI** North Bound Interface. 103
- netns** Network Namespaces. 67, 105, 140, 159
- NFM** Network Flow Monitoring. 97, 100, 102, 107, 108, 110, 111, 113, 190
- NFV** Network Function Virtualization. 26, 39, 40, 64
- NIDS** Network Intrusion Detection System. 41, 70, 78, 100, 102, 131, 152, 153, 197
- NRC** Node Resource Controller. 66, 67, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 79
- NSH** Network Self-Healing. 97, 102, 103, 107, 108, 110, 111, 112, 113, 190, 191, 192
- NSP** Network Self-Protection. 103, 107, 108, 110, 111, 112, 113, 190
- NWDAF** Network Data Analytic Functions. 43

- O-RAN** Open Radio Access Network. 158, 159
- OVS** Open vSwitch. 69, 70, 71, 74, 77, 97, 103, 109, 111, 113, 114, 115, 196
- PD** Protection Decider. 103
- PDCCP** Packet Data Convergence Protocol. 119
- PIN** Personal IoT Networks. 43
- PPM** Packet Performance Monitoring. 164
- pps** Packets per second. 142, 147, 162, 165, 167
- QoS** Quality of Service. 43, 95
- RAN** Radio Access Network. 1, 38, 39, 40, 76, 118, 119, 127
- RFC** Random Forest Classifier. 55, 56, 158, 169, 171, 176, 179, 185, 197
- RIA** Resource Inventory Agent. 102, 108, 130, 131, 132, 134, 140, 143
- RL** Reinforcement Learning. 157
- RLC** Radio Link Control. 119
- RRC** Radio Resource Control. 119
- SBA** Service-Based Architecture. 38, 40, 43
- SDAP** Service Data Adaptation Protocol. 119
- SDN** Software Defined Networks. 4, 39, 54, 98, 124, 125
- SHDM** Self-Healing Decision Maker. 102, 108
- SMA** Snort Monitoring Agent. 127, 128, 131, 138, 140, 141, 143, 152, 197
- SMF** Session Management Function. 39, 100, 119
- SOAR** Security Orchestration, Automation and Response. 44
- SVMC** Support Vector Machine Classifier. 55, 56, 159, 169, 170, 171, 172, 176, 177, 179, 185, 197
- TC** Traffic Control. 70, 81, 97, 109, 111, 113, 114, 115, 196
- TCP** Transmission Control Protocol. 14, 122, 162, 163, 165, 167, 168, 176, 184
- UDP** User Datagram Protocol. 14, 81, 104, 105, 122, 144, 162, 163, 165, 167, 168, 176, 184

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- UE** User Equipment. 26, 29, 39, 40, 43, 50, 62, 71, 75, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 88, 89, 91, 104, 105, 106, 109, 115, 127, 128, 141, 156, 160, 162, 163, 170, 171, 172, 184, 189, 190, 191, 195, 196
- UPF** User Plane Function. 39, 43, 100, 119, 160
- vCU** virtual Central Unit. 40, 128
- vISP** virtual Infrastructure Service Provider. 96, 100
- VM** Virtual Machine. 34, 46, 141
- VoIP** Voice over IP. 118
- VXLAN** Virtual Extensible LAN. 26, 39, 40, 76, 77, 96, 101, 106, 114, 122, 127, 128, 138, 143, 156, 160, 162, 196
- XGBC** XGBoost Classifier. 179

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Abstract

The exponential growth in telecommunications and artificial intelligence is transforming the landscape of cybersecurity, creating a dynamic environment where new attack vectors, including increasingly sophisticated Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, continuously emerge. In this rapidly evolving field, staying ahead of threats is a formidable challenge. Companies worldwide report significant financial losses due to security breaches, with estimates ranging between £600,000 and £1.15 million per incident. As B5G and the forthcoming 6G networks become integral to global communications, there is an urgent need for advanced solutions that can protect these critical infrastructures. The integration of Software Defined Networks (SDN) and AI-driven automation into these networks is not just beneficial but essential for enabling robust cybersecurity defenses. These technologies lay the groundwork for creating emulated environments and testbeds, where potential vulnerabilities can be explored, and automated frameworks for real-time attack detection and mitigation can be developed.

This PhD thesis seeks to expand the research domain in these crucial directions, contributing to the cybersecurity community with innovative frameworks and datasets that provide valuable insights and actionable solutions. The first major contribution is the design and implementation of a comprehensive framework for emulating B5G network topologies. This framework serves as a versatile testbed for executing cyberattack scenarios and incorporating detection, analysis, and mitigation features directly into the control and management planes of emulated networks. The framework is flexible, operating in both single and distributed modes, allowing for performance comparisons. In single mode, the framework can set up, configure, and execute a full B5G network topology in just 11.15 minutes, while the

distributed mode, which offers enhanced performance, completes the process in 19.85 minutes. Importantly, the distributed system maintained a stable bandwidth of 2 Gbps while successfully mitigating attacks on 64 emulated infected UEs, demonstrating its capability to handle complex and high-stakes scenarios.

Building on this foundation, the thesis presents a topology-aware cognitive self-protection loop designed to autonomously detect, analyze, and mitigate DDoS attacks in 5G-IoT environments. This self-protection loop comprises three core components: Network Flow Monitoring (NFM), responsible for the fine-grained detection and analysis of malicious network flows; Network Self-Healing (NSH), which acts as the brain of the loop by conducting predictive analysis to determine the optimal mitigation plan; and Network Self-Protection (NSP), which executes the mitigation actions across various datapath technologies, including Open vSwitch (OVS) and Traffic Control (TC). In rigorous testing within a 5G-IoT emulated scenario, the cognitive self-protection loop demonstrated its efficacy by mitigating cyberattacks in under 2 minutes, even as the number of UEs varied between 8 and 64 and the number of Edge servers increased from 2 to 4.

The third significant contribution of this thesis is the development of an evolved and enhanced distributed cognitive self-protection loop. By distributing the control and management planes among the network's stakeholders, this system achieves a collaborative, yet zero-information exchange, self-protection loop. This approach not only preserves the privacy and autonomy of each stakeholder but also significantly improves the system's overall performance. In tests conducted within B5G emulated scenarios, the distributed cognitive loop successfully managed the stable emulation of 128 UEs, achieving a 100% mitigation success rate. This solution was validated through the integration and coordination of up to seven software components within the cognitive loop, further demonstrating its scalability and effectiveness in complex network environments.

Finally, leveraging the insights gained from these developments, the thesis introduces a novel dataset specifically designed for AI/ML-based cybersecurity research. The dataset includes six classes—three representing different types of DDoS attacks and three representing legitimate network traffic patterns—captured across both topology and network flow

domains. This dual-domain approach provides an extended perspective on network behavior, enabling more accurate and nuanced classification of network patterns. The Histogram-based Gradient Boosting Classifier (HGBC) model applied to this dataset achieved remarkable results, with accuracy rates of 99.92% in the best-case scenario and 98.62% in the worst case, and an inference time of just 5.5 milliseconds. These results underscore the potential of AI and ML in enhancing the security of next-generation networks, even as network topologies evolve.

In conclusion, this research advances the state of the art in network security, providing a robust framework and a comprehensive dataset that together offer a solid foundation for the continued development of AI-driven cybersecurity solutions for B5G and 6G networks. The contributions of this thesis not only address current challenges but also pave the way for future innovations in safeguarding the communications infrastructure of tomorrow.

Chapter 1

Introduction

The momentum of the 6th Generation (6G) mobile networks is accelerating globally, as evidenced by the involvement of multiple international organizations in the initial discussions of these emerging technologies. Notable organizations include the NextGAlliance in the USA, 6G SNS IA in the European Union, Bharat 6G Alliance in India, and Beyond 5th Generation (5G) PC in Japan. Meanwhile, the 5G networks continue to evolve, with the latest releases from the 3GPP organization (Releases 18 [2] and upcoming 19) projecting 5G-Advanced standardization efforts extending until mid-2027. These rapid advancements necessitate a reduction in deployment times for these infrastructures to stay aligned with technological progress and market demands.

Both the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core domains of 3GPP studies in Beyond the 5th Generation (B5G) networks introduce new 5G System (5GS) capabilities aimed with direction towards 6G. One notable development is Ambient Internet of Things (IoT), which integrates a variety of low-power devices that harvest energy from ambient sources such as radio waves, light, motion, and heat [3]. In the first quarter of 2024, approximately 15% of devices connected to cellular networks have been from the IoT market, highlighting a growing B5G capability. According to the latest GSMA report, the number of connected IoT devices on cellular networks is expected to rise to 5.8 billion by 2030. China is leading this IoT growth, presenting an ambitious timeline for B5G services and verticals [4]. Figure 1.1 is an infographic from the GSMA report [4] that illustrates the growing trend of B5G and

IoT connections. The infographic highlights the expected increase in 5G connections from 2023 to 2030 and the economic implications of incorporating these technologies.

Fig. 1.1 The GSMA Mobile Economy 2024 infographic.

It is remarkable how the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ML solutions is becoming democratized in everyday life. Many companies are incorporating AI solutions as part of their resources, seeking specific enhancements in productivity and quality of services and products. Furthermore, the job market for AI engineers is expanding, driving the development of new solutions that benefit companies' revenues. This is also the case for the 3GPP roadmap for the near future. According to Release 18 [2], several specification groups leading upcoming research directions have incorporated AI innovations. For instance, Management, Orchestration, and Charging of Service and System Aspects are expected to develop under an AI/ML management framework. Additionally, the Radio Layer will also be influenced by AI/ML enablers, enhancing the evolution of Uplink and Downlink for the NR Air Interfaces.

Cybersecurity has become a crucial concern not only for companies but also for individuals. In recent years, numerous campaigns have warned end-users about new technologies and how companies use their personal data, along with the potential social impact. The rise of Virtual Private Network (VPN) providers like NordVPN, secure cloud-based hosting for photos and files like Google Photos, and the inclusion of Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) methods such as new biometric sensors in smartphones are examples of the democratization of cybersecurity. Nevertheless, companies and large tech firms are the major investors in security solutions to safeguard their capital and resources. According to the report titled *Cybersecurity: market data & analysis from Stratista Market Insights* [5], in 2023 the global Cybersecurity market has been worth US\$ 166.2 billion and the predictions have been to keep a stable growth for the upcoming years. Moreover, 3 of the top 5 IT investments of the companies studied in the cited report are: AI/ML, Cybersecurity and Automation. Additionally, the business area with higher expected investment is Cloud security.

The role of AI in B5G networks is a crucial aspect to consider when developing security solutions. The primary goal is to provide highly intelligent network enablers. A key area of study is network security, which aims to offer predictive intelligence and enable proactive threat detection. The research community is currently exploring AI-enabled solutions that may enhance the security of B5G networks. These solutions include anomaly detection, pattern recognition, and real-time threat analysis. Leveraging AI capabilities to improve threat detection and automate decision-making tasks is essential in today's market.

1.1 Problem statement

Cloudflare, a security company with over 95% of the market share in the network security sector [6], analyzes their traffic volume across various sectors and domains using a tool called Cloudflare Radar [7]. According to a Cloudflare report, 36% of network attack volume is attributed to Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks. Additionally, 30% of total traffic is generated by bots. Hackers exploit the increasing number of devices connected to B5G-IoT networks by infecting them with malicious software, turning them into botnets for targeted

attacks. Consequently, some public reports on the sector, like this one provided by the National Cyber Security Center [8] state that a direct impact exists on the financial costs of the security breaches, and this has been reported as an average between £600K and £1.15M. Hence, the security sector must continuously evolve to prevent and mitigate such threats. The cybersecurity field is an ever-evolving domain where hackers and security engineers constantly engage in a cat-and-mouse game. Companies need to protect their revenues, and individuals must be informed about the use of their personal data and its potential impact on their lives.

The increasing trends of new connected devices, the adoption of new technologies, and the availability of reliable cloud services have led to a primary constraint in the telecommunications field: increased data transmission and bandwidth consumption, which directly affect network performance and security. This creates new challenges for monitoring and analyzing vast amounts of data for potential threats. Therefore, telecommunications stakeholders must provide reliable and intelligent solutions capable of detecting and classifying cyberattacks.

As more devices connect, B5G networks evolve, leading to more complex networks that may introduce new attack vectors. The management and orchestration of these networks are currently achieved through Software Defined Networks (SDN) and other software-based solutions, enabling security engineers to create specific decision-making plans and orchestrate threat mitigations. This workflow, known as a closed security loop, involves detecting, analyzing threats, orchestrating, and enforcing mitigation rules. IT Operations teams use these loops to automate tasks, enhancing response capabilities toward self-driven protection and healing systems. AI solutions are crucial in providing fine-grained decisions based on real-time metrics from monitoring systems.

1.2 Innovations and main contributions

Automation of tasks and AI enablers in threat detection are reliable solutions in the cybersecurity landscape. Both aim to reduce companies' capital costs and minimize the time required for detecting and mitigating threats. This doctoral thesis aims to provide a frame-

work for automatically deploying emulated data, control, and management planes for B5G network infrastructures. Additionally, it will explore AI-enabled solutions for detecting and classifying cyberattacks. By leveraging automation and AI, this research seeks to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of cybersecurity measures, addressing the growing demands of the digital age. The main contributions of this thesis can be summarised as follows:

- **Design and implementation of an automated framework for 5G Network emulation and experiment execution:** An innovative and automated framework for B5G network topology creation and experiment execution is designed and implemented. The framework, composed by multiple controllers and an orchestrator enables, the researcher with the necessary tools to execute cybersecurity experiments over a B5G testbed and gather the results. The achievement of this framework significantly reduces the time and effort required for conducting complex network topology experiments and can be extended with other components or enablers, such as ML and/or AI model training loops.
- **Topology aware and cognitive self-protection loop:** It has been designed, developed and validated an automated cognitive protection loop for cybersecurity incidents (e.g. DDoS attacks). It is composed by three software tools in charge of i) detect the incoming threat over the B5G network topology; ii) provide the fine grained decision making and planning of the mitigation actions; iii) enforce the mitigation actions on the B5G network datapath. The achievement and integration of such self-protection control-loop is one of the main contributions presented in this work.
- **Enhanced cross-stakeholder cognitive self-protection loop:** It has been enhanced and extended the previously mentioned cognitive self-protection loop with software components to cover tasks such as analysis of the threat, decision making, and orchestration of the mitigation actions. Additionally, the distribution of the self-protection loop between the involved stakeholders in the B5G network topology to provide better

mitigation response and performance. This achievement extends the contributions and results found for the presented work.

- **Cybersecurity B5G and multidomain ML dataset:** It has been created and gathered a newly cybersecurity dataset for ML model training with multidomain in B5G networks, i.e. network flow and network interface. The dataset is composed by 6 different classes, including 3 kinds of DDoS attacks and legitimate traffic. Four ML models have been evaluated with this dataset in order to validate the resilience to B5G topology changes. Achieving such combination of domains in a single dataset enhances the whole view of the network state for the researchers and security engineers, and it is one of the main contributions presented for this PhD thesis.

Moreover, these innovations have been presented as research papers in peer-reviewed journals and international conferences. Some have been published already and others are under review process at the date of publishing this doctoral thesis.

Current solutions often lack the scalability, flexibility, and advanced capabilities required for comprehensive B5G network emulation. Many existing approaches do not fully integrate automation and orchestration, which are essential for efficient and scalable network management. Furthermore, the absence of AI-enabled predictive intelligence in these solutions limits their ability to provide early warning and effective detection of emerging cyber threats. My research addresses these gaps by introducing a robust, scalable network emulation framework that incorporates advanced automation, orchestration, and AI-driven security measures. This work not only sets a new standard for future research in B5G networks but also enhances the security and resilience of next-generation networks through early threat detection and response.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

This doctoral thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 1 provides an introduction and outlines the state of the problem that this research aims to address. Chapter 2 defines the aim and

objectives of the study. In Chapter 3, the methodology, research methods, and work roadmap are discussed, laying the foundation for the research process. Chapter 4 offers an overview of the relevant technical knowledge necessary for understanding the subsequent chapters. The literature review is presented in Chapter 5, contextualizing the research within the existing body of work. The thesis then delves into the core developments, with Chapter 6 focusing on the automation of B5G network topologies. Chapter 7 explores a three-component self-protection security loop, followed by Chapter 8, which addresses the distribution of the control plane within this security loop. Chapter 9 shifts the focus to an AI-enabled detection tool for DDoS attacks. In Chapter 10, a critical analysis of the achieved work is conducted, alongside an evaluation of the key performance indicators (KPIs). Finally, Chapter 12 concludes the thesis by summarizing the findings and proposing directions for future work.

Chapter 2

Aim and Objectives

2.1 Aim

The main aim of this doctoral thesis is to provide a framework that allows both the automatic deployment of emulated data-planes, control-planes and management-planes for B5G and IoT infrastructures and the finding of AI-models that are directly deployable in such infrastructures to achieve close-loop self-protection capabilities without human intervention against large-scale DDoS attacks. To achieve this aim, the thesis sets forth several research questions and objectives defined in the subsections.

2.2 Research questions

The research project presented in this thesis investigates novel AI-enabled solutions for DDoS cyberattack detection and classification in B5G-IoT networks. Due to the complexity of this kind of network and its features, the available computer network dataset on the internet and other resource repositories lack relevant metrics and metadata information on the 5G capabilities. Hence, this thesis delves into a multidisciplinary approach to cover some of the encountered research gaps and provide an extensive research framework covering the B5G-IoT network infrastructures, modelling of multiple cyberattack scenarios and topologies, and the creation of AI-enabled solutions for detecting and classifying these network cyberattacks.

The following research questions railroad the completion of this thesis. The answer to these questions is crucial to achieving a deep understanding of the underlying features and techniques used to develop AI solutions in B5G-IoT networks. Moreover, to provide a solution that successfully fulfils the ambitious aims of this thesis:

- **Question 1:** How the deployment of the data-plane, control-plane and management-plane of emulated large-scale Beyond 5G IoT networks can be automated to achieve self-protection capabilities ?
- **Question 2:** How do the features and technologies of B5G-IoT networks affect the design and implementation of cybersecurity solutions, particularly in the context of AI-enabled threat detection and classification?
- **Question 3:** How much does such automated deployment enhance the efficiency, and scalability of experiments conducted in 5G network environments?
- **Question 4:** What are the key research gaps in the cybersecurity field of AI-enabled B5G-IoT networks, and how can these gaps be addressed through the development of comprehensive datasets and advanced AI models?
- **Question 5:** How effective are AI-driven cybersecurity solutions in detecting and classifying diverse cyber threats targeting 5G networks, and how do these solutions perform under varying network topologies, traffic patterns, and attack scenarios?

2.3 Research Objectives

To successfully achieve the challenging outcomes and aims of this PhD thesis, several research objectives are outlined in this chapter. Each of these objectives are associated to a set of results outcomes and key performance indicators (KPI) to properly understand the contribution and innovation of this thesis. The KPIs outlined in this section have been established in alignment with the objectives of the EU-funded projects ARCADIAN-IoT and RIGOUROUS. These KPIs were set up at the consortium level, ensuring consistency across

the projects and directly supporting the research carried out in this PhD. By aligning with these consortium-defined KPIs, the thesis ensures that the evaluation metrics are both relevant and comprehensive, reflecting the collaborative nature of the research effort. Furthermore, these KPIs set a new baseline for future research work in the field, providing a structured framework for measuring progress and impact in 5G cybersecurity and network automation.

Objective 1: To create a framework for automated B5G-IoT network deployment, experiment execution, results collection, and AI models' training.

This objective aims to automate the entire research lifecycle for B5G-IoT networks, from the network infrastructure creation to AI model training and evaluation. Developing an integrated framework that orchestrates the design, execution and analysis of experiments, accelerates the innovation into AI-driven solutions for complex network environments—implementing automation scripts and workflows to orchestrate the experiment's execution process. This involves defining the VFN in the 5G infrastructures, start-up and control of the network sensors and analysers, and the data collection to a Database (DB). Furthermore, the generation of the dataset based on the collected network patterns and behaviour, along with the automation of the AI training loop and its consequent mechanism to visualise and summarise the results. The manual configuration and execution of experiments in B5G environments hinder rapid testing and iteration. Automation in experiment orchestration would enhance the reproducibility of results, enable faster experimentation cycles, and improve overall research productivity in real-world 5G scenarios.

Results

- The results of this objective is the sum of all the results described in the next objectives.

Objective 2: To investigate and perform a deep analysis of the B5G-IoT networks' characteristics and innovative technologies.

The purpose of this objective is to investigate and analyse the several technologies and challenges that the 5G and 6G mobile networks present. It could delve into the integration of advanced technologies like AI, the IoT, and edge computing within the context of 5G and 6G networks, clarifying their cooperative effects and innovative applications.

Results

- Comprehensive understanding of the fundamental features of the B5G-IoT network technologies.

KPIs

- **KPI-1:** Number of peer-reviewed research publications generated on novel technologies and characteristics of B5G-IoT networks ≥ 2 .

Objective 3: To identify the research gaps in the cybersecurity field of the AI-enabled B5G-IoT networks.

Detecting the currently existing research gaps in the cybersecurity field of the AI-enabled B5G-IoT networks is crucial in safeguarding the resilience of communication infrastructures. The objective requires a thorough examination of the current state-of-the-art cybersecurity mechanisms employed within these networks and an analysis of their efficacy in mitigating threats.

Results

- Deep analysis of the implications of the AI-enabled cybersecurity solutions in the state of the art for B5G-IoT networks.

Objective 4: To design and implement an emulated B5G-IoT network infrastructure.

The objective pursues the creation of a B5G-IoT network infrastructure; hence it is essential to achieve a deep understanding of the underlying technologies and characteristics of these networks. This implies that the replicated network infrastructure should be able to cover and provide multiple features. Multi-tenancy to simulate the coexistence of multiple virtualised network functions for different service requirements. Multi-stakeholder control planes to enable collaboration and coordination among network operators and service providers. User mobility enables continuous connectivity to the B5G-IoT networks. While 5G networks promise significant advancements in connectivity, the current processes for deploying 5G infrastructure are still largely manual, which limits scalability and efficiency. There is a clear need for more sophisticated, automated systems that can streamline the deployment process, reducing human intervention and the potential for error.

Results

- An automated emulation tool capable of provisioning and deploying multiple B5G-IoT topologies with fundamental features and technologies.
- An extension of the emulation tool to run over distributed physical machines, leveraging the balancing of the computational cost.

KPIs

- **KPI-2:** Time required to provision and deploy the emulated B5G-IoT network topologies in a non-distributed testbed ≤ 5 minutes.
- **KPI-3:** Number of distributed physical machines where the emulated B5G-IoT network topology is provisioned ≥ 4 .
- **KPI-4:** Provision and deploying time required for the emulated B5G-IoT network over distributed physical machines ≤ 20 minutes.

Objective 5: To develop an experiment-based cyber incident testbed over a B5G-IoT network.

The design and implementation of a B5G-IoT network testbed are closely attached to the experiment execution. This objective implies modelling the network cyber threats and the experiments' design. This implies the addition of mechanisms for monitoring, measurement, and performance evaluation within the testbed architecture. Hence collecting empirical data and insights. Some relevant instrumentations are traffic analysers to capture key performance indicators and network flow metrics that will provide insights about the network's behaviour for the different modelled cyberattacks. Current cybersecurity frameworks typically focus on single-layer protection, which leaves systems vulnerable to advanced persistent threats. The absence of a dual concurrent protection architecture—capable of defending against multiple attack vectors simultaneously—represents a critical shortcoming in ensuring robust security for 5G networks.

Results

- The provision of the necessary VFN and control plane components of the B5G-IoT network.
- Multiple DDoS cyberattack models and their automated execution over the B5G-IoT infrastructure.

KPIs

- **KPI-5:** Number of different exploited protocols for DDoS cyberattack models ≥ 3 (Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP), Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), User Datagram Protocol (UDP)).
- **KPI-6:** Number of different emulated infected devices that the system can record their behaviour over the attacked B5G-IoT network infrastructure ≥ 128 devices.

Objective 6: To create an AI-enabled 5G network dataset with multiple DDoS cyberattacks.

This objective aims to design and create a 5G network dataset that combines the network's flow and topology information and behaviour that are insightful for the classification of the modelled cyberattacks within the scope of the core features and characteristics of a B5G-IoT network. This dataset may facilitate the development and evaluation of AI-driven cybersecurity solutions for these telecommunication networks. This involves the identification of benign traffic, malicious network flows, and anomalous behaviour patterns. The effectiveness of cybersecurity research, especially when leveraging AI/ML techniques, heavily depends on the availability of high-quality, domain-specific datasets. Currently, there is a notable lack of comprehensive 5G cybersecurity datasets, which stifles the development and benchmarking of advanced security solutions tailored for 5G environments.

Results

- Novel dataset with realistic B5G-IoT multi-tenant traffic with multiple nested encapsulation network flow headers.
- Aggregated features and metrics for the B5G-IoT network flows over the monitored interfaces.
- Feature selection method for the generated classes in the B5G-IoT dataset.

KPIs

- **KPI-7:** Diversity of network classes for the dataset, mixing legitimate and malicious traffic ≥ 5 .
- **KPI-8:** Number of monitored features and network metrics related to the B5G-IoT network flows and interfaces ≥ 80 .
- **KPI-9:** Number of selected B5G-IoT dataset features for the later ML analysis ≥ 20 .

Objective 7: To explore and enhance AI models for cyberattacks' detection and classification in B5G-IoT networks.

The objective involves developing and enhancing ML models capable of analysing complex 5G network traffic patterns to mitigate cyberattacks. Conducting a deep validation and benchmarking of the designed dataset to assess its diversity, coverage and utility is crucial for this objective. This includes the evaluation of the dataset over multiple scenarios and 5G network topologies, and its compatibility with several AI algorithms and their evaluation metrics. Comparing the performance of different ML models, strengths and weaknesses can be identified, as well as areas for improvement. Although AI has shown significant potential in enhancing cybersecurity, there remains a gap in the development of AI models specifically designed for the unique security challenges posed by 5G networks. Addressing this gap would enable more effective, automated detection and mitigation of cyber threats in these complex, high-performance environments.

Results

- Automated framework for AI-enable solutions creation and evaluation in B5G-IoT networks.
- Performance comparison of multiple ML models.

KPIs

- **KPI-10:** Number of supported ML models to validate the B5G-IoT dataset ≥ 4 .
- **KPI-11:** Number of performance indicators and evaluation metrics for each ML model ≥ 6 .
- **KPI-12:** Accuracy of the ML models in detecting and classifying DDoS cyberattacks in B5G-IoT networks $\geq 95\%$.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This methodology section outlines the process, methods, tools, and objectives followed for this PhD journey. To present some contributions to the scientific field, it is essential to validate and evaluate the objectives and results gathered in this thesis. This chapter designs the framework to answer the research questions detailed in Section 2.2. Moreover, it maps the research objectives (defined in Section 2.3) within an extensive plan to conduct the project. This methodological approach allows that each aspect of the research is correctly addressed, providing a solid foundation for completing the objectives of this PhD project.

3.1 Research method

Among all the known methods to conduct scientific research, researchers typically choose between two main options: qualitative or quantitative methods. The qualitative method aims to answer questions like what, why, and how something changes. Some of the techniques of this method are: interviews, surveys, and phenomenological exploration to gather different perspectives on a particular question. For example, qualitative research might explore quality of experiences or motivations using detailed interviews and their corresponding post-analysis. This approach is valuable for understanding complex phenomena from multiple perspectives and developing theories for real-world scenarios.

On the other hand, the quantitative method focuses on answering how much something changes, most of times, towards enhancing performance metrics. Quantitative research involves the collection and analysis of numerical data from empirical experiments to find patterns, relationships, or trends. Common techniques include experiments and statistical analysis. This approach is essential for testing hypotheses, measuring variables, and making predictions based on empirical data.

Some research questions require a hybrid approach, by the combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, thus providing a comprehensive understanding of the topic. This mixed-methods research can take advantage of the strengths of both approaches. However, this thesis primarily focuses on a quantitative method to address the research questions. The decision to focus on quantitative methods relies with the goal of enhancing the performance metrics and providing measurable, data-driven insights.

3.1.1 Network Emulators for B5G Network Topology Emulation

Network emulators play a crucial role in the design, testing, and validation of B5G network architectures. These tools allow researchers to model and evaluate network behaviors in a controlled environment before deployment in real-world scenarios. The ability to choose the appropriate emulator for a given experiment is paramount, as it directly impacts the accuracy, scalability, and ease of implementation. For B5G networks, where complex, distributed, and dynamic topologies are common, the selection of a suitable emulator must take into account multiple factors such as real-time simulation capability, protocol support, scalability, and ease of integration with the underlying system.

The table provided in this section compares various network emulators that could be used for B5G network emulation. These include Cisco Packet Tracer, Riverbed Modeler, OmNet++, NS3, and Common Open Research Emulator (CORE). Each emulator offers different features, suited to various user needs and use cases. In this section, we will discuss these features in detail to clarify the reasoning behind the selection of CORE for the testbed provisioning used in the contributions of this thesis. Feature Definitions and Considerations

To facilitate a clear understanding of the comparison, the following list explains each feature included in the table:

- **Primary Use:** The intended use case or scenario the emulator is designed to support (e.g., educational, commercial, research-focused).
- **Target Audience:** The type of users for whom the emulator is most suitable (e.g., students, researchers, network designers).
- **Supported Platforms:** The operating systems that the emulator can run on (e.g., Windows, macOS, Linux).
- **GUI:** Whether the emulator provides a user-friendly interface to design and manage network topologies or requires command-line interactions.
- **Protocol Support:** The range of networking protocols that the emulator supports, from simple to more advanced protocols necessary for B5G experimentation.
- **Customization:** The flexibility and ability to modify or extend the emulator's functionality, especially for advanced users.
- **Real-Time Simulation:** Whether the emulator supports real-time, interactive simulations or operates in a simulated time environment.
- **Scalability:** The ability of the emulator to handle small to large-scale network topologies.
- **Licensing:** The availability and cost of the emulator (e.g., open-source, commercial).
- **Ease of Learning:** The learning curve required to use the emulator effectively, considering the user's experience level.
- **Simulation Type:** The type of simulation model used (e.g., packet-level simulation, discrete-event simulation, real-time emulation).

Comparison of Network Emulators

Each emulator discussed in this section offers unique strengths and weaknesses depending on the context of use. Table 3.1 provides a summary of the comparison of the network emulator cited in this work.

Cisco Packet Tracer [9], for instance, is primarily designed as an educational tool for simulating Cisco network devices. It provides a user-friendly interface but is limited in its protocol support, primarily focusing on Cisco-specific technologies. While an excellent resource for students and instructors, Cisco Packet Tracer's limitations in scalability and flexibility make it less suitable for the complex and large-scale requirements of B5G research.

Riverbed Modeler [10], on the other hand, is a commercial tool intended for large-scale network simulations. It supports a broad range of network layers and offers a highly customizable environment through its scriptable models. Its complex graphical interface allows for detailed design, but its commercial nature and lack of real-time simulation limit its utility in experimental testbeds for B5G research, where open-source tools and real-time interaction are often more desirable.

OmNet++ [11] is a research-focused discrete event simulator, widely used in academic circles for network protocol testing and validation. Its high degree of customization, achieved through C++-based modules, makes it a powerful tool for specialized research. However, the steep learning curve and lack of real-time simulation make it less suitable for the dynamic, real-time scenarios encountered in B5G network research.

NS3 [12] is another widely used research tool, particularly popular for its extensive support for real-world protocols. It provides a flexible, open-source platform for simulating complex networks. Like OmNet++, NS3 is highly customizable but operates on a discrete-event simulation model, meaning it does not provide real-time interaction. The complexity of programming in NS3 also poses challenges for quick experimental setups, especially in environments where real-time emulation is necessary.

Finally, CORE stands out as a lightweight, real-time emulator that is easy to set up and use. It supports real-time network emulation, making it particularly suitable for experiments that require dynamic interaction and adaptation, such as those in B5G networks. CORE

provides a graphical interface that is simpler compared to Riverbed Modeler but retains the flexibility to be integrated with real-world network elements. Its open-source nature, combined with its scalability to medium-scale topologies, ensures that it meets the demands of both research and practical testbed deployment.

Feature	Cisco Packet Tracer [9]	Riverbed Modeler [10]	OmNet++ [11]	NS3 [12]	CORE
Primary Use	Educational	Commercial	Research	Research	real-time network experimentation
Target Audience	Students	Network designers	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers, network engineers
Supported Platforms	Windows, macOS, Linux	Windows, Linux	Windows, macOS, Linux	Windows, macOS, Linux	Linux, macOS, FreeBSD
Graphical User Interface	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
Protocol Support	Cisco proprietary protocols	From application to physical layers	Via extensions	Real-world protocols	Real-world protocols
Customization	Limited	C/C++	C++	C++ or Python	Python
Real-Time Simulation	No	No (event-based simulation)	No (discrete-event based)	No (discrete-event based)	Yes (real-time emulation)
Scalability	Limited	Scalable	Research-sized simulations	Large and complex networks	Physical distribution
Licensing	Free (Educational)	Commercial	Open-source (LGPL)	Open-source (GPLv2)	Open-source (BSD)
Simulation Type	Packet-level simulation	Discrete event simulation	Discrete event simulation	Discrete event simulation	Real-time emulation

Table 3.1 Comparison of Network Emulators as B5G testbed infrastructure providers

Rationale for Selecting CORE

The decision to use CORE as the network emulator in this thesis is based on several key factors. First, CORE's real-time emulation capabilities allow for interactive network experimentation, which is critical in B5G networks that demand dynamic and real-time decision-making. Additionally, CORE's simplicity and ease of use, along with its compatibility with Linux, enable efficient testbed provisioning without the steep learning curve associated with more complex emulators such as OmNet++ or NS3.

Furthermore, CORE provides freedom to interact directly with the Linux kernel and underlying network resources, which is crucial for the type of cybersecurity and self-protection loops developed in this work. The ability to distribute the emulated topology across multiple physical machines adds another layer of flexibility, enabling the creation of more realistic network topologies that reflect the distributed nature of B5G infrastructures. Finally, CORE's open-source licensing ensures that it is accessible and customizable for the specific needs of this research, making it the most appropriate tool for B5G network emulation and experiment execution in this thesis.

Further information about the underlying technical aspects of CORE is explained in Section 4.1.2.

3.1.2 Physical resources and testbed

To create the B5G network emulation, physical devices are essential. Throughout this thesis, a set of physical servers has been utilized for these emulations. In Chapters 6 and 9, four physical machines have been employed, illustrated in purple in Figure 3.2. Each machine is characterized by Ubuntu 20.04, an Intel Xeon E5-2650 @ 2.8GHz CPU, and 64GB DDR3 RAM.

Conversely, Chapter 7 utilized a single physical machine with the following specifications: Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, a 56-core Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2660 v4 @ 2.00GHz, and 128GB DDR4 2400 MHz RAM, depicted within a red box in Figure 3.2. For demonstration purposes

related to the ARCADIAN-IoT project ¹, the same set of experiments was conducted with the physical machines shown in Figure 3.1. One of the servers in Figure 3.1, used in validating Chapter 8, has the following characteristics: Ubuntu 16.04 LTS with kernel 4.4.0, a 10-core Intel Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 v4, and 16GB of RAM.

Fig. 3.1 Physical resources and testbed used for validation of Chapters 7 and 8.

¹A workshop video presented for the ARCADIAN-IoT project by the author of this thesis can be found here, where the testbed and achievements of Chapter 7 are presented.

Fig. 3.2 Physical resources and testbed used for validation of Chapters 6, 7 and 9.

3.2 Research work roadmap

This section presents the framework created to successfully conduct the work associated with this research project. To achieve this, the workload has been balanced across four different work packages (WPs), each with distinct objectives. Each WP is linked to one or more research objectives and their respective expected results. To ensure effective project execution, the objectives have been split into tasks directly linked to the expected results and outcomes of this thesis. These tasks are organized in a timeline, providing an insightful understanding of the roadmap followed to complete the underlying work. The WPs and their content are as follows:

WP1: State of the art and background

Every research project consists of a series of research questions and objectives to be addressed. This requires conducting a thorough literature review and gaining proficient knowledge about the relevant topics. This work package is composed of the following two tasks.

Task 1.1. - Conduct extensive literature review

It is important to conduct an extensive literature review on the technologies, techniques, and concepts related to the research topic. This allows researchers to identify potential research gaps that the project can address and to direct their investigative tasks accordingly. Some of the main state-of-the-art research topics to be analyzed include B5G networks, the management and orchestration of network resources, closed control loops for B5G networks, AI/ML-enabled solutions for B5G networks, and cyberattack detection and classification. For the aim of this project, this task remains active for the whole project process due to possible new incoming literature during the execution of the rest of tasks.

Task 1.2. - Acquire of background knowledge

Moreover, the researcher needs to achieve a proficient level of skills and background knowledge related to the main topic of the research project. This involves continuous learning, as

technologies advance and new ones emerge that might be useful or relevant to be included in the research. For this project, proficiency in emulation tools, new programming languages, and AI/ML libraries and concepts is essential. These skills are necessary to effectively perform the tasks and achieve the project's objectives.

WP2: Emulation and B5G infrastructure

This work package involves the initial implementation tasks of the research project, focusing on the emulation of the B5G network infrastructure. It includes a series of tasks related to creating a suitable infrastructure with a minimum of three networking planes: data, control, and management planes. Consequently, the network infrastructure is equipped with various network components and Network Function Virtualization (NFV)s that enables user connectivity and mobility through the emulated B5G network, multiple stakeholders and multi-tenancy over the infrastructure.

Task 2.1. - Design and implement B5G emulated infrastructure data plane

The data plane consists of a series of NFVs that enable user connectivity and mobility through the network infrastructure. Achieving this scenario involves emulating various physical and virtual devices, including User Equipment (UE)s, gNodeBs, Edge and Core physical servers, Distributed Unit (DU), Central Unit (CU), and other B5G components. Mobility for UEs is supported by the GPRS Transport Protocol (GTP) protocol. Additionally, multi-stakeholder and multi-tenancy capabilities are facilitated by networking technologies such as Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation protocol (GENEVE), Generic Routing Encapsulation protocol (GRE), and Virtual Extensible LAN (VXLAN). The combination and orchestration of these technologies build the essential data plane for the B5G infrastructure.

Task 2.2. - Automate the software components provision in the control and management planes

With the provision of the data plane, the B5G network infrastructure also requires control and management planes. The control plane includes components responsible for monitoring the network and enforcing mitigation policies on the data plane. On the other hand, the management plane consists of a series of software components tasked with analyzing threats, planning mitigation policies, orchestrating these mitigation tasks, deploying databases, and enabling communication between software components via a message bus broker. The aim of this task is to provide automated deployment depending on the particular use case of the experiment to be executed.

Task 2.3. - Design and model multiple network traffic patterns

Every research project needs specific use cases, and this task involves developing a DDoS use case for the project. Designing and modeling various network traffic patterns is crucial for analyzing incoming threats. Thus, the project aims to cover at least three exploitable protocols for DDoS attacks with multiple variations in network patterns. Additionally, the project seeks to model legitimate traffic patterns to simulate realistic network behavior, thus providing variability to the resulting dataset.

WP3: Data collection and AI/ML enablers

This work package focuses on researching, advancing, and implementing AI/ML solutions for detecting and classifying various B5G network traffic patterns. The structure of the work package involves configuring data collection for the use case and every executed experiment, creating the final dataset with selected features and metrics, and establishing an ML training testbed. This testbed provides the researcher with the necessary tools to evaluate and select the ML models under study.

Task 3.1. - Configure network sensors' data collection

This task involves enabling multiple network sensors along the B5G control plane. These sensors are responsible for gathering the network state. There are two main domains that the sensors need to monitor. The first domain is the network flow domain, which involves flow metadata and metric information such as Internet Protocol (IP) addresses, packet headers, packet lengths, and other relevant flow metrics. The second domain is the topological domain, which includes real-time information about network interfaces and devices through which the network traffic flows. Configuring these enablers throughout the network infrastructure is essential to collect sufficient information about the behavior and state of the network.

Task 3.2. - Select features and aggregate metrics

For creating a comprehensive and useful dataset for subsequent AI/ML analysis, conducting a deep analysis of the network metrics gathered in the experiments is crucial. Furthermore, selecting relevant features which perform better to the specific use case. Additionally, a significant contribution of this research project is the aggregating metrics from the two domains outlined in Task 3.1. This aggregation offers more detailed insights into both the network flow and the current state of the network interfaces. A set of data analysis techniques and feature selection are performed in this task.

Task 3.3. - Design and implement of the ML training loop

The objective of this task is to create a training loop or framework within the research project, selecting the ML models capable of classifying the multiple network patterns outlined in the use case. This framework enables researchers to load and split the dataset into training and evaluation sets, iterate through multiple hyperparameter configurations, and collect various evaluation metrics. The task aims to include every step of the modeling and evaluation process in a single training loop. Moreover, the task is intended to run multiple configurations over multiple ML models in order to select the most efficient model in detecting and classifying the cyberattacks.

WP4: Automated framework

The main responsibilities of this work package involve automation tasks to develop a fully automated framework. This framework allows researchers to dig deeply into the constraints of B5G network behavior and explore potential AI/ML solutions for the cyberattacks outlined in the project.

Task 4.1. - Automate B5G network infrastructure provision and experiment execution

This task involves automating multiple research tasks outlined in this section, specifically tasks 2.1., 2.2., and 2.3. The goal is to launch different B5G network topologies and attack scenarios. Parameters such as the number of Edge computers, the number of UEs connected to the same Digital Service Provider (DSP), and the presence of multiple DSPs over the physical infrastructure may vary among other topological devices. Additionally, the management and control planes must vary based on the use case, offering different capabilities to the B5G network scenario. Furthermore, the execution of experiments needs to provide multiple network protocols to explore and exploit as part of this project.

Task 4.2. - Automate data collection and feature extraction and aggregation

The main purpose of this task is the automation of the underlying work of Task 3.1. and 3.2. Such automation allows the researcher to collect results from several network metrics and metadata across multiple scenarios, where the topology, volume and traffic patterns are varied. Consequently, the outcome of this task is a collection of data sets from multiple experiments, ready for the AI/ML training and model selection.

Task 4.3. - Automate ML training loop

Similar to the previous tasks, this one involves automating task 3.3. Achieving an automated training loop for each ML model is essential for providing the researcher with insights into each model's performance in various use case scenarios. This loop automates the iteration over multiple configurations of datasets gathered from the earlier steps of the overall

framework. This automation is crucial for efficiently evaluating and refining ML models based on their performance across different scenarios.

Task 4.4. - Integrate all outcomes in a single automated framework

Finally, this task integrates the various automated loops into a unified framework. This integration allows the researcher to configure and execute the desired series of experiments. The process performs the dataset collection, creation, and ML training, finishing with the selection and preparation of the best ML model. By speeding up these processes, the framework enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of the research, enabling deep analysis and rapid iteration over different experimental setups. This approach ensures that the researcher can focus on refining the models and deriving meaningful insights from the experiments.

Mapping tasks and research objectives

Figure 3.3 represents the mapping between the aforementioned work packages, tasks, and research objectives. It is worth noting that multiple research objectives are associated with different tasks. This is because achieving an objective and its corresponding result requires a combination of tasks, sometimes spanning different work packages. For example, Objective 4 is primarily focused on WP2 but needs to be completed in Task 4.1 to enable the automation aspect of Result 3. Result 3 is an automated emulation tool capable of provisioning and deploying multiple B5G-IoT topologies with fundamental features and technologies.

Timeline

Figure 3.4 represents a Gantt chart of the described tasks for this research project and doctoral thesis. The timeline is goes from the beginning of the third quarter of 2021 to the end of the second quarter of 2024, covering the PhD course duration. Each task is assigned a minimum duration of one quarter. Work packages are depicted with blue lines, while task durations are

Fig. 3.3 Mapping between Workpackages, Tasks and Research Objectives.

shown with orange lines. Dependencies between tasks are indicated by red arrows pointing from the end of the dependent task to the subsequent one.

It is worth noting that tasks under work package 1 have an extended duration due to their continuous learning nature, staying updated with the latest research topics and gaps. Task 3.1 depends on task 2.2, as it involves deploying sensors and monitoring tools within the B5G infrastructure, requiring the prior deployment of control and management planes.

Additionally, tasks 3.2 and 3.3 depend on task 3.1. Finally, work package 4 is entirely dependent on multiple preceding tasks, as it aims to automate most of these earlier tasks.

Fig. 3.4 Gantt diagram with timeline for tasks and their dependencies

Chapter 4

Overview

This chapter aims to provide sufficient background knowledge to the reader on the topics, technologies, techniques, software tools, and concepts relevant to this research project. It is not intended to serve as a literature review or present novel contributions, which are covered in Section 5. Instead, the following sections will enable the reader with a thorough understanding necessary for the remaining chapters of this PhD thesis. The chapter covers topics such as network emulation tools, concepts of Edge and Cloud network segments, the B5G network paradigm, and a detailed analysis of closed control loops.

4.1 Emulation of B5G network infrastructure

4.1.1 Simulation vs Emulation

There is an ongoing discussion about the differences between simulation and emulation processes. The distinctions are often small and vague, making it challenging to differentiate between them both, and they are sometimes used as synonyms. The last goal of both concepts is to mimic a real system or process, but each has distinct underlying objectives.

In this project, simulation is understood as designing and implementing a model (often mathematical) that represents the physical interactions, inputs, and outputs of the systems being mimicked. Thus, is a degree of accuracy significantly inferior compared with em-

ulation. Simulations aim to analyze the final state of the model and the results gathered from experiments, typically using algorithms and descriptive processes run by software components. On the other hand, emulation is viewed as replicating not only the systems or processes but also the hardware itself, to recreate an equivalent version of the original system. While simulations may provide better performance or results than real physical systems, emulations often have worse performance due to the high computational cost of replicating multiple hardware devices and interactions on the same physical infrastructure.

The network throughput rate formula can be summarized as data size divided by transmission time. In a simulation environment, traffic patterns can be modeled by varying data sizes, data sources, and transmission times, providing a general idea of throughput behavior. However, when throughput is measured between two virtual machines hosted on a physical computer and connected via OpenvSwitch, additional factors come into play. These include CPU usage for each Virtual Machine (VM), communication protocols, network interface configurations, drivers, and others. This setup provides deeper insights into network behavior, producing results closer to real-world scenarios despite possible performance limitations. Consequently, this project aims to emulate the B5G infrastructure to get accurate, near-reality results and behaviors.

In recent years, a new simulation/emulation paradigm has emerged with the concept of the Digital Twin. This concept aims to create a virtual representation of a real object or system that replicates the same behaviors and outputs as its physical object/system. Digital Twins are often supported by ML techniques and automation processes to address some of the limitations of traditional simulation environments. There are various classifications of Digital Twins, including Process Twins, which aim to operate as real integrated systems on a macro level of emulation [13].

4.1.2 Emulation network tools

There are numerous network emulators available online that the research community frequently uses. These tools vary based on their primary objectives, such as focusing on educational purposes or specializing in wireless communications. Most network emulators

operate similarly: they offer an API for researchers to instantiate network nodes (e.g., computers, switches, routers) and manage communication between them. Additionally, they provide tools for monitoring and analyzing traffic or ongoing experiments. Some notable examples include Cisco Packet Tracer [9], Riverbed Modeler [10], OMNeT++ [11], and NS-3 [12].

This project uses the CORE as the network emulation tool for deploying the B5G infrastructure. CORE is an open-source platform that runs in Linux environments. It is a Kubernetes-like tool and creates network nodes using a set of Linux namespaces (process, network, and user, among others) to establish container-based nodes. These nodes share the same filesystem and Linux Kernel, meaning they have access to the same installed programs and services on the host physical machine. However, processes are isolated in each container due to CORE's namespacing. Additionally, CORE combines these namespaces with Linux Ethernet Bridging tools or OpenvSwitch capabilities to create network links between the nodes. Each network emulated with CORE can connect to different physical devices (interfaces, computers, etc.) to closely resemble real-world scenarios.

When CORE creates a network topology, each instantiated node shares the same resources as the host physical machine (CPU, RAM, GPU, etc.). Although network nodes are relatively small and consume low resources, network communications still need to pass through the same Linux Kernel, which can cause scalability issues. CORE addresses this problem with its distributed feature, allowing the distribution of network topology across multiple physical machines to leverage available resources. This project aims to automate the distribution and execution of these distributed B5G topologies over multiple physical machines and presents a common framework to control both distributed and non-distributed topologies.

CORE provides a GUI with tools for emulating network nodes and running experiments. Figure 4.1 depicts an example of a B5G network topology instantiated with the CORE GUI tool. However, this project focuses on automating every step from the creation of the topology to the collection of results, rather than using the GUI. CORE can be run as a background process using configuration files with the extension of "imn". This "imn" file contains all the information regarding the network topology nodes, their interfaces, and links. An extract

of this topology file is provided in the code block 4.1. Note that all the interfaces of the namespace can be configured before the execution of the experiment, enabling the network engineer with the sufficient tools to twist and custom the network topology at will.

Fig. 4.1 Example of CORE emulator GUI with a sample B5G network topology infrastructure.

Finally, because CORE namespaces' filesystems are on the host machines, users can transfer any type of file, executable, directory, etc., to the node's filesystem. This is possible with Linux tools such as "scp", "ssh", and "rsync", which must be properly configured on both the host machine and within the namespaces. Consequently, CORE provides researchers with complete freedom to control every network node, allowing them to instantiate configuration files, create local variables, execute isolated processes, link with physical and virtual devices, and perform any network experiment. For all of these features and capabilities, CORE has been the chosen network emulator to perform the necessary tasks of the B5G network topologies emulation. Moreover, the "interface-peer" keyword is the reference for the connections between the interface of the host and the node they are attached to.

Code block 4.1 Example node configuration from the topology file for CORE emulator

```
1 node n7 {
2     type router
3     model mdr
4     network-config {
5         hostname EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1 !
6         interface eth0
7             ip address 10.2.0.2/16
8             mac address 40:00:00:02:00:01 !
9         interface eth1
10            ip address 10.1.0.11/16
11            mac address 40:00:00:01:00:05 !
12        interface eth2
13            mac address 40:00:00:05:00:01 !
14        interface eth3
15            mac address 40:00:00:07:00:01 !
16        interface eth4
17            mac address 40:00:00:05:00:03 !
18        interface eth5
19            mac address 40:00:00:07:00:03 !
20        interface eth6
21            mac address 40:00:00:09:00:01 !
22        interface eth7
23            mac address 40:00:00:09:00:02 !
24    }
25    canvas c1
26    iconcoords {210.0 0.0}
27    labelcoords {210.0 30.0}
28    interface-peer {eth0 n6}
29    interface-peer {eth1 n1}
30    interface-peer {eth2 n8}
31    interface-peer {eth3 n10}
32    interface-peer {eth4 n12}
33    interface-peer {eth5 n13}
34    interface-peer {eth6 n14}
35    interface-peer {eth7 n16}
36 }
```

4.2 Beyond 5G-IoT

This research project aims to gather results in the scope of 5G networks and beyond, making it essential to provide the reader with knowledge about these next-generation networks. This section introduces the realm of B5G networks, offering profound insights and discussing the features and capabilities these networks offer. It also provides relevant information about the network components, technologies, and techniques surrounding B5G networks.

B5G networks represent the evolution of 5G technology, focusing on enhancing performance, reliability, and scalability to support emerging applications and services. B5G aims to deliver higher data rates, lower latency, improved energy efficiency, and massive connectivity for various use cases, including IoT, smart cities, autonomous vehicles, and immersive experiences like AR/VR.

4.2.1 5G System and Infrastructure

The term 5G infrastructure refers to the network's physical and virtual components that enable the advanced features of next-generation networks. From a broad perspective, the network is divided into multiple segments, each representing how the network components are geographically distributed based on their purpose. The segments relevant to this research project are: User or Device, RAN, Edge, Transport, Core, and Inter-domain segments.

5G Core network features

3GPP is the global organisation in charge of standardising the 5G and the mobile networks since the 3rd Generation (3G) until the new upcoming 6G of mobile networks. It specified the features that a 5G Core server should have and services that should provide to the user and stakeholders. First, it manages all the network's functionalities, including authentication, security, session management, and traffic routing. Some of these main features include:

- **Service-Based Architecture (SBA):** provides a modular framework deploying multiple network components from different stakeholders. These components are suppliers of

different Network Functions, such as Access Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF), and User Plane Function (UPF).

- **Network Slicing:** is the ability to create multiple and independent networks on the same physical infrastructure, thus supporting multiple use cases such as IoT, enhanced Mobile Broadband, Ultra-reliable Low Latency Communications, etc.
- **Massive Machine-Type Communication (mMTC):** consists on the capabilities to support massive number of connected devices, such as IoT sensors, smart devices, etc. Leveraging the efficient handling of signalling and data traffic.
- **SDN:** this network paradigm provides dynamic allocation of the network resources, improving the overall network efficiency and scalability.
- **Mobility Management:** the standard protocol to provide the user mobility feature is the GTP. Using this protocol with a set of NFV ensures the continuous connectivity and session as users move across different network cells and technologies (e.g., from 4th Generation (4G) to 5G).
- **Multi-tenancy:** is the ability to host multiple isolated network slices or tenants on the same physical infrastructure, often known as DSPs. This feature is enabled by the nested encapsulation of the network traffic with protocols such as GRE, GENEVE or VXLAN.

5G infrastructure and network flow

The User or Device segment comprises the end-user devices, which vary depending on the use case. These devices include UE such as smartphones, IoT wearable devices, tablets, and self-driving cars. They utilize wireless communication to connect to the 5G network, specifically to DUs located at the Next Generation NodeB (gNB) base stations. DUs perform the essential task of transforming wireless signals into the Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) protocol, linking user devices to wired layers. This marks the beginning of the RAN

segment, which connects to user authentication components in the Core network, building what is also known as Core-RAN (C-RAN).

Network traffic reaches one of the Edge segment's physical servers, which are provisioned with part of the RAN components, particularly the virtualised Central Units (vCUs). These Edge servers host multiple vCUs, enabling enhanced 5G system features and allowing different stakeholders and DSPs to share the same physical resources while being isolated. This setup helps on savings for capital costs and physical maintenance. This Edge segment serves as Mobile/Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) services, as it is geographically located closer to the end user, thus reducing the latency of the hosted services.

vCUs from multiple stakeholders can coexist on the same infrastructure provided by the Edge Infrastructure Service Provider (ISP). When the traffic reaches the virtual Central Unit (vCU), it encapsulates the traffic with the GTP, creating a specific network flow for each UE connected to the infrastructure. Before the traffic leaves the Edge server, it undergoes an additional encapsulation with a network protocol such as VXLAN, GRE, or GENEVE, to differentiate which DSP or tenant the UE belongs to. At this point, the network traffic has been encapsulated twice, and further encapsulations may be applied as it passes through the B5G infrastructure.

After leaving the Edge segment, the traffic is routed to the Transport segment. This segment comprises a set of network devices (routers and switches) that connect the Edge with the Core segments. Finally, the network flow reaches the Core segment, and is routed to a 5G Core server. Leveraging the provided set of NFV, the network traffic that reaches the 5G Core server is analysed and the first encapsulation is removed (usually GRE, GENEVE or VXLAN). This way, the Core server knows which DSP the traffic belongs to, and routes it to the specified virtual server. Here, all the SBA functions associated to the DSP take place, and the last GTP encapsulation is removed from the network traffic. If the network flow is intended to reach the internet, the traffic will leave the DSP and the Core ISP to reach the inter-domain segment, where the traffic will finally reach its destination.

Figure 4.2 illustrates an example of a multi-tenant B5G network topology. From bottom to top, it is divided into different segments: Device, 5G RAN, 5G Edge (see 1 in Figure 4.2),

Transport (see 4 in Figure 4.2), 5G Core (see 5 in Figure 4.2), and Interdomain (see 8 in Figure 4.2). The grey, larger boxes represent the physical infrastructure (see 2 in Figure 4.2), while the orange and blue boxes depict different DSPs as tenants sharing the same physical infrastructure (see 3 in Figure 4.2). A Service and Management layer (see 6 and 7 in Figure 4.2) has been added, showcasing components of a closed control loop (see Section 4.3 for reference).

In the Service layer (see 6 in Figure 4.2), a Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) is instantiated to detect possible cyberattacks by mirroring traffic in the transport layer, thus providing a comprehensive view of network traffic and patterns as described in the same section. The Management layer (see 7 in Figure 4.2) includes planning and orchestration components to enable the cognitive capabilities of the closed loops. Communication between components is facilitated by a message bus broker, and event persistence is managed in a DB. Additionally, a GUI is included to monitor the status of the management nodes.

Finally, both the ISP and DSP (see 3 and 5 in Figure 4.2) are equipped with a compute layer that contains sensors and actuators in the network domain, thereby enabling the monitoring and mitigation capabilities of the closed control loops. One of the main contributions of this doctoral thesis is the emulation, provisioning, and instantiation of multiple B5G network topologies, as depicted in Figure 4.2.

Fig. 4.2 Example of multi-tenant B5G network topology infrastructure with Service and Management layers.

4.2.2 5G Advanced and 6G

The 3GPP Release 19 studies focus on advancing multiple aspects of 5G networks to meet the evolving needs of users and applications. One significant study addresses Personal IoT Networks (PIN), aiming to support a coherent and efficient network for personal IoT devices. This includes ensuring the discovery and management of PIN elements, their capabilities, availability, and reachability. Additionally, it enables communication between these elements through a Gateway Capability (PEGC).

Another focus is the enhancement of group management and communication. This study aims to improve the handling of group attributes, status event reporting, and virtual network (VN) group communications. It also explores the ability of UE to simultaneously send data to multiple groups, each with different Quality of Service (QoS), thus facilitating more efficient and flexible group interactions. Moreover, the study on system support for AI/ML-based services seeks to extend AI/ML capabilities beyond network automation, currently supported via 5G Network Data Analytic Functions (NWDAF) to include device-based AI/ML training and inference

Furthermore, the Release 19 studies focus on enhancing UPF integration within the 5G Core SBA. This involves improving UPF event exposure services, including better mechanisms for registration, deregistration, discovery, and consumption of these events by other network functions. Lastly, the study on 5G Access and Mobility (AM) policy aims to refine policy control when user equipment transitions between the AI and the Evolved Packet Core (EPC), ensuring coherent and efficient mobility management.

These contributions to Release 19 aim to establish the necessary bridges to 6G with the essential technical foundation for a formal 6G Study items in Release 20. Hence, the enhanced user mobility, the inclusion of AI/ML capabilities and the network automation are key elements of the 5G Advance and 6G network communications. This project focuses on these particular study items to solve the research questions outlined in Section 2.2.

4.3 Closed control loops

A closed control loop is the concept in control systems and automations where the system continuously monitor its own output and uses this feedback to make adjustments and keep the desired performance. For example, a sensor like a thermometer that is measuring the current room temperature is reporting it to the thermostat (a controller). This controller compares the measured temperature to the desired setpoint and if it differs from that setpoint, the thermostat sends a signal to the heating or cooling system. The new temperature is measured again by the thermometer, and this information is fed back to the thermostat. From the sensing to the last actuation, a control loop has been outlined in a simple use case scenario.

As described before, a closed control loop has a set of key components and mechanisms. First, a sensor, that measures the actual output of the system and provides real-time data. Then, a controller, which compares the measured output against the desired setpoint or reference value. Sometimes these controllers are separated into multiple subcomponents with predefined tasks (analyser, decision maker, orchestrator, etc.). Finally, an actuator, that applies the adjustment to the system based on the controller's instructions.

In computer networks, a closed control loop can be applied to different use cases. It can control and automate resource allocation based on the needs and varying loads on the network at any given time. Additionally, it can enhance security measures by identifying potential threats and automatically implementing mitigation policies to block incoming threats. This doctoral thesis focuses on this control loop paradigm, analyzing B5G network traffic to identify possible attack vectors. Upon detection of such attacks, a self-protection closed control loop is triggered to mitigate the threats.

The closest concept for these kind of control closed loops in the realm of security for computer networks is the Security Orchestration, Automation and Response (SOAR) loop. It enables the security teams to combine different security tools, automate tasks that could be done by the software instead of human intervention, and perform the consequent mitigation responses. The Security Orchestration refers to the combination and coordination of different softwares and hardwares in the B5G security systems. The Security Automation refers to the execution of those repetitive tasks that the control loop can perform. Therefore, the multiple

agents and functional blocks involved in a closed control loop for security in computer networks can be outlined as follows:

- **Monitoring and Analytics:** This functional block serves as the sensing layer of the control loop. It continuously monitors the network from different domains, such as network flow, network devices, and network processes. Depending on the use case, the analysis of the monitored resources is handled by different software components. Isolating the analysis tasks into separate components offers significant benefits, including the distribution of responsibilities and computational costs. For instance, an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) can act as an analysis tool by generating an alert when it identifies a malicious flow detected by the monitoring tool. This alert includes information on the type of attack detected and the specific network resources affected.
- **Planning and Orchestration:** This functional block serves as the core decision-making center that addresses the current problem. After receiving alerts with proper analysis, the next step is to develop a plan for addressing the issue. The output of this layer varies depending on the use case and the specific alert. For example, if the system is experiencing a network layer attack, the detected malicious flow can be dropped. This task may involve a straightforward plan with minimal orchestration regarding the software resources involved in the mitigation process and the specific point in the topology (geographically speaking) where the mitigation should occur. However, more detailed orchestration is required when applying more complex solutions, such as redirecting malicious traffic to a honeynet. In such cases, the redirection processes need to be sequentially orchestrated and may need to be applied at multiple points within the network topology. This complexity underscores the challenges of human intervention in such scenarios and highlights the necessity for automated solutions.
- **Mitigation:** This final functional block comprises the set of actuators throughout the network that implement the mitigation policies defined by the Planning and Orchestration components. These actuators should be deployed within the network infrastructure at points where stakeholders wish to exert control. One challenge in

this process is the involvement of multiple network and computer technologies for a single mitigation policy. For instance, if the control loop's only action is to drop a network flow, the actuator's task is relatively simple. However, if the mitigation policy involves redirecting malicious traffic to a honeynet that is yet to be created in a VM, the process becomes more complex. In such a scenario, the actuator must incorporate a series of sub-actuators to perform all tasks in the order specified by the orchestrator. This includes creating a new VM, establishing a network slice to redirect all flows to the VM, and attaching the malicious flow to the network slice, among other steps. The complexity of coordinating these actions highlights the importance of precise orchestration and the challenges involved in implementing comprehensive mitigation strategies.

Figures 4.3 and 4.4 are sequence diagrams that illustrate the operation of a self-protection loop in a network environment, showing the processes involved in detecting an attack and then mitigating it through different actions. Both diagrams feature three main components: Monitoring and Analysis, Planning and Orchestration, and Mitigation. These components interact sequentially to detect, analyze, and respond to cyber threats.

In Figure 4.3, the self-protection loop initiates when a new attack is detected (see 01 in Figure 4.3). The Monitoring and Analysis component identifies the threat, performs a threat analysis, and raises an alert (see 02 and 03 in 4.3). The Planning and Orchestration component then takes over by creating a set of decisions, leading to the intent of dropping the malicious flow (see 04 and 05 in 4.3). This decision is sent to the Mitigation component, which applies the drop rule to the flow (see 06 in 4.3). After verifying that the flow has been successfully dropped (see 07 in 4.3), an acknowledgment (ACK) is sent back to confirm that the data plane rule has been enforced, completing the mitigation process (see 07 in 4.3).

On the other hand, Figure 4.4 follows a similar initial process but implements a more complex mitigation strategy involving the provisioning of a new network slice. After the attack is detected and analyzed (see 01, 02 and 03 in 4.4), the Planning and Orchestration component decides to provision a new VM and create a network slice (see 04 and 05 in 4.4). This process includes several additional steps, such as provisioning and deploying the

VM, creating the network slice, and attaching the flow to this new slice. Each of these steps involves an intent being sent to the Mitigation component, followed by an acknowledgment confirming the action's success. The final step is the acknowledgment that the flow has been successfully attached to the slice, indicating that the mitigation strategy has been fully implemented (see 16 in 4.4).

Fig. 4.3 Sequence diagram example of a closed control loop to drop a malicious network flow.

Fig. 4.4 Sequence diagram example of a closed control loop to redirect a malicious flow to a new VM.

Chapter 5

Literature review

This chapter offers a comprehensive analysis of the key techniques and the state of the art in current projects and technologies that are closely aligned with the integrated approach of this doctoral thesis. While it provides a broad overview, each of the development chapters (6, 7, 8, and 9) includes a dedicated "Related Work" subsection that delves deeper into the specific topics covered in those chapters, ensuring a thorough exploration of the literature relevant to each aspect of the research.

Table 5.1 presents a comprehensive list of features that are critical for evaluating the research work in the domain of network emulation, automation, and cybersecurity. Moreover, about the AI enablers available nowadays for cybersecurity. Each feature is assigned a letter code for easier reference of use later. These features are explained as follows:

- (A) Emulation or Simulation: considering the differences of emulation and simulation outlined in Section 4.1.1 in this work, the main objective of this feature is to identify whether the reference has simulated or emulated the obtained results. There could also be some which testbeds have been considered as real scenario ones.
- (B) Multi-tenancy: as explained in Section 4.2.1, this is a common enabled feature in our B5G scenarios which provides the physical infrastructure with the isolation of multiple tenants over the same physical infrastructure. Thus, leveraging the orchestration

of virtual resources for multiple actors. The feature aims to point whether or not the cited reference considered this feature for their testbeds and experiments.

- (C) Multi-stakeholder: explained in Section 4.2.1 as well, the multi-stakeholder considers the number of different kind of actors involved in the B5G network. These actors could be such as ISP, DSP, or even particular UEs.
- (D) Detection: considering the steps of a closed loop for cybersecurity, as stated in Section 4.3, the detection of the attack is the first step to mitigate the threat incoming. This feature aims to identify in the cited reference if the authors enabled detection techniques, and how.
- (E) Analysis: after the detection of the attack, an autonomous analysis is required in most of the security systems, to provide the sufficient information to the security engineer about the malicious threat detected.
- (F) Decision-Making: is the capability of the autonomous closed control loops to make proper decisions depending on the analysis received of the attack. Such decisions could imply the mitigation action to use (drop, slice, etc) or best location point to mitigate the threat (close to the source, end-to-end path, etc).
- (G) Orchestration: once the decisions have been made, the system or security team needs to organise and establish a priority list of the mitigation actions to enforce, in a particular order. This orchestration of resources can be automated. The feature aims to identify whether or not the authors of the cited reference considered the automated orchestration of the mitigation actions to stop or mitigate the threat.
- (H) Mitigation: has the referenced solution mitigated the threat automatically? Not all the solutions and research papers focus on the mitigation of the threat. Most of them stop when the attack is detected or they enhance the orchestration of resources. The feature's objective is to identify if the solution has automated mitigation actions in their solution.

- (I) Topology aware: when talking about cybersecurity for telecommunications network infrastructure such as B5G, the network topology is crucial. It varies for the different actors and scenarios possible. Thus, considering the full picture of the topology changes in real time is considered relevant for finding suitable automated solutions for mitigating the cyberattacks. This feature aims to identify whether or not the stated referenced considered the varying of the network topology or different topology scenarios.
- (J) Flow aware: the network flow contains most of the information relative to the network cyberattack. The metadata and metrics related to the network flow provide the engineers with the information and ability to apply different actions over the flow. However, the network flows in B5G network topologies vary in sizes, encapsulation and technologies. Thus, the utilisation of the network flow metrics and metadata to mitigate the threat is the main objective of this feature.
- (K) AI: as crucial part of the contributions of this thesis, the enabling of AI solutions to the cybersecurity problems is another feature to study and identify of the analysed literature.

Table 5.2 uses the letter codes from the first table to evaluate a set of research papers, including your work. Each row represents a different paper, and the columns represent the features from the first table. For the Emulation or Simulation column (A), specific codes are used: S for simulation, E for emulation, R for real environment, and N/A if not available. The presence of a feature in a particular paper is indicated by a checkmark (✓). This structured approach allows for a clear comparison of the different research works based on their features and capabilities. By analyzing this table, one can quickly identify which papers support specific features, providing insights into the strengths and focus areas of each research work.

Letter	Feature	Summary
A	Emulation or Simulation	Experiments simulated or real-time emulation
B	Multi-tenancy	Shared physical infrastructure for virtual tenants
C	Multi-stakeholder	Multiple actors involved (e.g. ISP and DSP)
D	Detection	Automated detection of the cyberattack
E	Analysis	Automated analysis of the cyberattack detected
F	Decision-making	Automated decision-making for the actions to mitigate the cyberattack
G	Orchestration	Automated orchestration of resources when mitigating the cyberattack
H	Mitigation	Automated mitigation of the cyberattack
I	Topology aware	Considered the network topology changes
J	Network flow aware	Considered the network flow changes
K	AI	Addition of AI solution to one or more parts of the cybersecurity system

Table 5.1 Relationship between code-letters and key features of the analysed papers

Paper	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
Asad, Muhammad et al. [14]	E/R	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ansah, Frimpong et al. [15]	S	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-
Vittal, Shwetha et al. [16]	E	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-
Fliess, Michel et al. [17]	S	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-
Salasi, Amir Hossein et al. [18]	R	-	-	-	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-
Leghris, Cherkaoui et al. [19]	S	-	-	-	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	✓
Mazin, Aladhmi Mahmood et al. [20]	E	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-
Nardini, Giovanni et al. [21]	S	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-
Kojima, Fumihide et al. [22]	E	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-
Tang, Xiaoling et al. [23]	S	-	-	-	✓	-	-	✓	✓	-	-
Bommy, M. et al. [24]	S	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓
Bai, Honghao et al. [25]	S	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓
Hajla, Salah El et al. [26]	N/A	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓
Alasmari, Tahani et al. [27]	N/A	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓
Wang, Fang et al. [28]	S	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	-
This Work	E	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 5.2 Key features for B5G network emulation and AI-enabled solutions supported by each analysed paper

Recent advancements in network emulation and automation have significantly contributed to the development of robust and scalable network architectures. Several studies have focused on creating environments that facilitate comprehensive testing and evaluation of network protocols and services. For instance, the development of a large-scale wireless emulation environment integrates both physical and virtual radio nodes for Beyond 5G systems, highlighting its utility in future B5G/6G research and development [22]. This environment successfully emulates various wireless systems, proving its value for preliminary investigations and evaluations.

Similarly, a zero-touch emulation framework for network slicing management in a 5G Core testbed demonstrates a fully virtualized, zero-touch 5G network slice management framework supporting diverse applications with agility and efficiency [16]. This framework provides end-to-end slice services, showcasing the potential of fully automated, virtualized environments for managing complex network scenarios. Additionally, a topology-aware virtual network mapping algorithm enhances service provisioning in programmable networks, emphasizing the efficiency of virtual network mapping in improving resource utilization and service quality [15].

Focusing specifically on 5G network emulation, several studies have highlighted the unique challenges and solutions in this area. The proposal of using network simulators as digital twins for 5G/B5G mobile networks emphasizes the benefits of digital twins for performance evaluation, testing, and optimization [21]. These digital twins integrate network simulators with real-world components, enhancing the accuracy and relevance of performance evaluations. Another study introduces an open dataset for Beyond-5G data-driven network automation experiments, designed to support network automation by using real traffic data to generate realistic performance metrics and validate automation algorithms [15]. This dataset proves effective for validating network automation protocols, contributing to the development of more robust network management solutions.

The integration of network automation within industrial and telecommunications environments has also seen significant advancements. The investigation into the automatic network resource management of OPC UA in 5G highlights the benefits of combining 5G's high band-

width and low latency with OPC UA's interoperability to enhance industrial communication systems [18]. This study demonstrates significant improvements in network resource utilization and management efficiency. Additionally, an analysis of the interaction between network automation tools and network devices using Python evaluates the performance impact of automation scripts on network operations, showcasing significant improvements in network automation efficiency without compromising performance [20]. These studies illustrate how network automation can improve resource utilization and management efficiency, particularly in industrial applications.

Cybersecurity remains a paramount concern in network management, and various studies have explored innovative approaches to enhance network security. A dynamic cybersecurity protection method based on SDN for Industrial Control Systems (ICS) introduces a closed-loop security control mechanism that includes intrusion detection and security response measures [28]. This method employs moving target defense (MTD) strategies like topology transformation and IP/port hopping to enhance security, proving feasible with minimal impact on communication timeliness.

Another study proposes a robust Proportional-Integral (PI) controller design to enhance cybersecurity in nonlinear networked control systems, focusing on maintaining system stability and performance under DoS attacks [18]. The robust PI controller design demonstrates improved stability and performance in the face of DoS attacks, validating its practical applicability. Additionally, the generation of comprehensive security datasets for 5G networks, covering both IP-layer and core network components, underscores the importance of such datasets in developing and validating security solutions [17]. These datasets include a wide range of attack scenarios and normal traffic patterns, providing a robust foundation for security research.

ML has emerged as a powerful tool for enhancing network security and management. Various studies have explored the application of ML techniques to detect anomalies and threats in network environments. The investigation into ML approaches for IoT networks emphasizes the importance of robust anomaly detection systems in maintaining network security [26]. These studies demonstrate the effectiveness of ML techniques in identifying

security threats and abnormal network behaviors, highlighting the potential for improved IoT network security.

The use of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models for DDoS detection showcases the integration of feature extraction and temporal analysis capabilities to improve detection accuracy [27]. This combined approach significantly enhances DDoS detection accuracy, demonstrating its potential for real-world applications. Moreover, the evaluation of intelligent intrusion detection techniques demonstrates significant improvements in detection accuracy and adaptability, showcasing their potential for robust cybersecurity solutions [19]. Additionally, a multidimensional detection and evaluation system for computer network security using ML algorithms offers a robust framework for malware detection with high accuracy and low false detection rates [25]. This system utilizes clustering analysis and artificial neural networks for effective intrusion detection and multi-dimensional identity recognition.

5.1 Machine Learning Models

ML techniques are applied throughout this research to enhance the predictive and analytical capabilities of the system. Four primary models are utilized: Random Forest Classifier (RFC) [29], ExtraTrees Classifier (ETC) [30], Support Vector Machine Classifier (SVMC) [31], and HistGradBoost Classifier (HGBC) [32]. Each model brings unique strengths to specific types of data and analysis contexts, contributing to a well-rounded approach for addressing the research questions.

Overview of Machine Learning Models

RFC is an ensemble method that constructs a multitude of decision trees during training and outputs the mode of their predictions. It is particularly robust to overfitting due to its aggregation approach, making it effective for diverse datasets.

Similar to RFC, ETC also builds multiple decision trees; however, it introduces more randomness by selecting cut-points randomly. This can lead to faster training times and

potentially greater robustness in certain contexts. These decision trees amake predictions climbing down multiple decisions such as “is $x > 100$?” as pointed in Figure 5.1.

SVMC operates as a clustering classifier, constructing a hyperplane that best separates data points of different classes. Its strength lies in finding a maximal margin between classes, which is especially effective for high-dimensional data.

HGBC is a boosting method that iteratively enhances the model by focusing on data points where previous models underperformed. By using histogram-based techniques for training, it achieves efficient computation and is highly suitable for large datasets. This boosting classifiers ensemble new models weithen the incorrect labeled data, achieving new and accurate model such as depicted in Figure 5.2

Comparison of Model Types

Tree-based models, like RFC and ETC, are ensemble classifiers that perform well on complex datasets due to their ability to capture non-linear patterns. SVMC, as a clustering classifier, excels in cases with clear class boundaries in high-dimensional spaces. In contrast, boosting methods like HGBC incrementally improve the model’s accuracy by targeting misclassified data points, making them highly effective for structured data.

Model Evaluation Metrics

To assess model performance, several evaluation metrics are employed:

- **Accuracy:** Provides a straightforward measure of overall classification success.
- **Precision, Recall, and F1 Score:** Particularly useful for understanding performance on imbalanced datasets, as they account for false positives and false negatives.
- **Confusion Matrix:** This metric allows for in-depth error analysis, giving insights into specific types of misclassifications.

Fig. 5.1 Decision Tree classification [1].

5.2 Summary of the reviewed literature

In summary, the reviewed literature provides essential insights and highlights the specific research gaps that this thesis addresses. The literature presented in this chapter, along with the subsequent chapters, outlines the current state of the art in network emulation, network automation, cybersecurity for AI, and advancements in B5G networks. However, this literature can be further expanded through the contributions provided in this thesis.

First, [14] presents a hybrid testbed combining emulated and real environments, utilizing Mininet as a network emulator along with two real Light Fidelity (LiFi) nodes connected to the emulated network. Integrating real devices into network emulation marks a significant advancement in the field, though this feature is notably absent in the other reviewed studies. Additionally, [22] supports multi-tenancy and multi-stakeholder capabilities as discussed

Fig. 5.2 Boosting classification [1].

in this thesis. Nevertheless, none of these works achieve the automation of emulation and provisioning of host and network resources across multiple physical machines, as achieved here. This thesis constructs a fully functional B5G network topology, which can automatically modify connected stakeholders and devices, thus advancing the field of cybersecurity and communications in B5G networks by significantly accelerating research.

Regarding self-protection control loops, most existing literature concentrates on the initial phases: detection and analysis. Studies such as [24–27] implement detection and analysis systems utilizing AI solutions, while [28] accomplishes these steps without any AI components. This thesis, however, establishes a closed-loop self-protection control mechanism encompassing all steps—detection, analysis, decision-making, planning, and orchestration of mitigation actions. This comprehensive system handles the entire process from cyberattack detection through to mitigation, thereby advancing the current cybersecurity literature in telecommunications by integrating all these components with ML-based models into a unified solution.

It is noteworthy that among the papers reviewed for this thesis, those employing AI for cybersecurity ([24–27]) only utilize network flow data. Conversely, studies that consider network topology ([15, 20–23]) do not employ AI solutions. Thus, one of the primary contributions of this doctoral thesis is the integration of both domains—network flow and interface—into a single solution for detecting specific B5G malicious flows traversing network interfaces. This approach establishes a baseline for cyberattack detection by analyzing malicious and legitimate flows, while accounting for network interface conditions and nested encapsulations prevalent in B5G network infrastructures.

Chapter 6

Automated framework to emulate B5G network topologies

Clarification

This chapter, along with all its contributions, is presented as new and innovative information for the research community in the fields of security and automation of B5G network topologies. The content has been meticulously prepared by the PhD candidate to validate and evaluate the proposed framework. Moreover, the contents of this chapter have been submitted as a journal paper to IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, and it is currently under review at the time of this thesis submission, where the PhD candidate of this thesis is the main author and contributor.

6.1 Introduction

With the evolving landscape of B5G and the advent of 6G networks, it is essential to develop a framework that allows researchers to conduct their investigative activities and explore the features of these advanced networking technologies. However, studying multiple use cases, diverse network topologies, and the high variability of real-world scenarios on the internet presents significant challenges and requirements for any researcher. This is where techniques

like emulation become invaluable, enabling researchers to reproduce near-realistic scenarios and run multiple use cases within the same emulated infrastructure. Furthermore, emulation allows the reproduction of behaviors of different technologies and physical machines on a single computer or server, providing insights into the underlying behaviors of proposed solutions.

Network emulators, such as the CORE emulator (see Section 4.1.2 for more details) or NS-3, are effective but often require a steep learning curve and complex instantiation. Thus, automating the deployment of emulated network infrastructure, provisioning of resources, and deployment of software components is crucial. These tasks are typically the most time-consuming for researchers. By automating and simplifying these processes, researchers can focus on fine-tuning the use cases that will provide valuable insights into research gaps, advancing new technologies like B5G and 6G networks. Moreover, the emulation of B5G topologies offers a safe and reusable environment for identifying and addressing potential cybersecurity vulnerabilities. In contrast, conducting such experiments in live production environments could result in significant financial costs for the institutions involved in this research

Automating the creation of B5G network topologies is not straightforward. Numerous features must be enabled in the topology to qualify it as B5G, such as multi-tenancy and user mobility. Multi-tenancy allows the network topology to host multiple, distinct virtualized tenants over the same physical infrastructure without sharing network traffic or information between them, ensuring resource isolation. User mobility refers to the capability of UE to switch from one connected antenna to another without losing connectivity or requiring re-authorization at every moment.

This chapter introduces CORE eXecutor (COREX), a developed architecture that automatically deploys emulated B5G network topologies. COREX enables various capabilities and special features of these advanced networks, provisions network resources on the host machine, deploys the necessary software components to the corresponding network nodes, and executes a set of experiments to collect results, highlighting the status of the network

topology during the experiment. These experiments can include DDoS attacks or other networking cyberattacks and use cases. Key features that COREX contributes to, include:

- A robust orchestration architecture that interacts with the three domains of the experiments tasks: host, emulator and network emulated nodes.
- Automation of tasks related to the deployment of emulated B5G network topologies.
- The automation of experiment deployment and execution with the ability to switch between different pre-defined use cases.
- The distribution and orchestration of the emulated B5G network topology over multiple physical host machines.

These contributions fulfill research objectives 4 and 5, as outlined in Section 2.3 of this doctoral thesis. These objectives pertain to the creation of B5G network infrastructure, the provisioning of network and host resources, and the deployment of all relevant B5G actuation planes, alongside cyber incident testbed creation. The COREX framework, the primary contribution of this chapter, represents the accomplishment of these objectives.

The rest of the chapter is structured as follows: Section 6.2 introduces the related work and the state-of-the-art of similar automation frameworks for network topologies' deployment and orchestration. Section 6.3 dives into the deep details of the architecture and design of COREX as a architecture. Section 6.5 comprises the experiments and testbed followed to validate the developed framework. Lastly, Section 6.6 outline the conclusions reached and draws the future guidelines to follow in order to enhance the work done so far.

6.2 Related Work

The development of robust network emulation environments has been a significant focus in recent research, with several studies contributing to this domain. For instance, the review of Virtualized Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) with management and orchestration capabilities provides a comprehensive overview of how these systems handle resource

allocation, monitoring, and automation within NFV contexts [33]. Similarly, the study on modular, end-to-end next-generation network testbeds emphasizes the full automation of network management tasks, integrating various components into a cohesive testbed for efficient testing and validation [34]. Another notable contribution is the exploration of lightweight containerized environments for emulating Link Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP)/5G networks, which highlights the potential of these platforms to efficiently emulate complex scenarios with minimal re-configuration delays [35]. These works collectively underscore the importance of scalable and efficient emulation platforms in advancing network research.

Focusing specifically on 5G network emulation, several studies have highlighted the unique challenges and solutions in this area. The introduction of the 5G3E dataset, designed to support network automation experiments, demonstrates the value of using real traffic data to generate realistic performance metrics and validate automation algorithms [36]. Additionally, the proposal of a realistic 5G infrastructure emulator for experimental service deployment emphasizes the need for accurate performance evaluation and the replication of real-world network conditions to support experimental services [37]. These studies provide a solid foundation for understanding the complexities of 5G network emulation and the critical role of realistic datasets and emulation environments in facilitating advanced research.

The integration of network automation within industrial and telecommunications environments has also seen significant advancements. The discussion of the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) in enabling intent-based networking within Industry 4.0 showcases the potential for automated and efficient network management by integrating with existing industrial protocols and standards [38]. Moreover, the investigation into the automatic network resource management of OPC UA in 5G highlights the benefits of combining 5G's high bandwidth and low latency with OPC UA's interoperability to enhance industrial communication systems [39]. These studies illustrate how network automation can improve resource utilization and management efficiency, particularly in industrial applications.

Cybersecurity remains a paramount concern in network management, and various studies have explored innovative approaches to enhance network security. The generation of

comprehensive security datasets for 5G networks, covering both IP-layer and core network components, underscores the importance of such datasets in developing and validating security solutions [40]. Additionally, the novel approach to cyber testing using reinforcement learning for continuous emulation of entire attack campaigns demonstrates significant improvements in the efficiency and effectiveness of cyber testing processes [41]. These contributions highlight the necessity of robust security frameworks and the integration of advanced testing methodologies to ensure network resilience.

Terraform by HashiCorp [42] and OpenTofu [43] represent two real-world tools widely used for managing and provisioning cloud infrastructure. Terraform, a well-established solution, and OpenTofu, its open-source counterpart, both enable the declarative management of infrastructure as code, automating the deployment and scaling of resources across various cloud platforms. While these tools excel in providing scalable and efficient infrastructure management, they primarily focus on infrastructure provisioning and lack the comprehensive integration of advanced network security, cognitive self-protection mechanisms, and AI-driven threat detection, which are central to the objectives and results of this PhD thesis. Therefore, while Terraform and OpenTofu offer foundational capabilities in infrastructure automation, they do not fully address the specialized requirements of B5G network emulation, distributed control, and automated cybersecurity frameworks that this research aims to advance.

While there are commercial tools such as Terraform and OpenTofu for managing network infrastructures, they are not designed to support B5G research, leaving engineers with a “do-it-yourself” approach. Section 3.1.1 provides a detailed rationale for selecting CORE as the network emulator, and this chapter elaborates on the extensions and enhancements made to CORE to develop a fully functional framework for emulating B5G network topologies, enabling advanced features such as multi-tenancy, multi-stakeholder support, and user mobility. Furthermore, this framework provisions the management, control, and service planes of the network topology, allowing for the creation of cyber incident testbeds and the execution of experiments with dynamic topological configurations. Thus, the final solution presented in this chapter consolidates the features reviewed in the literature, resulting in

the first automated framework for comprehensive B5G network infrastructure emulation, operable as a standalone or distributed system.

6.3 COREX Architecture

This section details the design of the primary framework developed in this phase of the doctoral thesis. This framework comprises a set of controllers and enablers integrated with the CORE emulator's capabilities (refer to Section 4.1.2 for more details on the emulator). These controllers and enablers interact with three different domains on the machines they are deployed: host, emulator, and emulated nodes. The framework, named COREX due to its extensive features surrounding the emulator, is designed to empower researchers to create emulated B5G infrastructure.

COREX's main purpose is to provide the capability to deploy multiple services over the emulated network nodes, configure networking according to B5G topology, execute pre-configured experiments such as cyberattacks, and finally, gather the corresponding results, logs, and databases containing historical data from the experiment. In summary, COREX automates the experiment cycle, facilitating the generation of datasets with more data and valuable insights.

The main architecture of the COREX framework is depicted in Figure 6.1. As it can be seen in the figure, it consists on multiple components such as an orchestrator and different controllers for different domains. The developed framework is considered the grey box entitled COREX. Its main component is an orchestrator (purple box) that consumes in first instance a configuration file, containing all the information regarding the B5G network topology to be emulated (the contents of this configuration file are further discussed in Section 4.1.2). The orchestrator is the brain of the framework, it has the full view of the systems and domains involved in the experiment. Hence, it has connectivity to the three domains of the COREX: host (yellow box), emulator (orange box) and the emulated containers (red boxes). To control each of these domains, a set of controllers have been developed: the Host Resource Controller (HRC), Emulator Resource Controller (ERC), Node Resource Controller (NRC)

and the Logging Controller (LC). These provide the functional capabilities to the framework to communicate and assist as Application Programming Interface (API)s to the orchestrator.

COREX features an Orchestration functionality that interacts with the other enablers and controllers of the framework. This orchestrator acts as the brain of the program, controlling the iterations and steps performed by COREX. By automating these processes, COREX enables the creation, deployment, and management of emulated B5G infrastructures, allowing researchers to efficiently conduct and analyze experiments. COREX is composed of four main controllers, outlined as blue boxes in Figure 6.1. Their functionalities are as follows:

1. HRC

- **Purpose:** Controls host functions for the experiment such as networking, Network Namespaces (netns) creation, file creation and edition, etc.
- **Functions:** Installs necessary tools and dependencies, loads required Kernel modules, starts, stops, and reloads daemons, and handles other tasks related to the host machine of the experiment.

2. ERC

- **Purpose:** Manages tasks related to the emulator.
- **Functions:** Provides the orchestrator with information such as the ID of the emulated session, the names and interfaces of the network namespaces, evaluates the status of the emulation, and more.

3. NRC

- **Purpose:** Acts as the main controller for the emulated nodes.
- **Functions:** Sends orchestrated instructions to each node based on their roles in the experiment, manages networking relevant to multi-tenancy in the corresponding nodes, starts software components, and launches the experiment phase.

4. LC

- **Purpose:** Handles the collection of logs and results from the experiments.
- **Functions:** Collects logs and results from the emulated network nodes and shares them with the orchestrator, which then creates a log package for the researcher.

Fig. 6.1 COREX functional architecture and design.

6.4 COREX Orchestration Design

When executing COREX to emulate a B5G network topology and gather the corresponding results of an experiment, there are four main and distinct phases of execution. Each of these phases is depicted in a sequence diagram in Figures 6.2, 6.3, 6.4 and 6.5. Moreover, it is described how each COREX controller interacts with the testbed infrastructure.

B5G Network topology creation

This phase of the COREX execution corresponds to the instantiation and deployment of the emulated nodes over the physical infrastructure. Figure 4 depicts the sequence diagram for this particular phase, called the Testbed Manager.

As most networking functions in COREX require elevated privileges on Linux systems, the HRC first checks user permissions at the program's start (see steps 1, 2, and 3 in Figure 6.2). Following this, the orchestrator provides the HRC with a configuration file containing the necessary network information about the emulated nodes to be deployed in the experiment (see step 4 in Figure 6.2). The ERC checks the status of the emulator daemon, cleans any previously created topologies that may be residual, and restarts the emulator (see steps 5 to 9 in Figure 6.2).

Once the emulator is running with no instantiated topology, the ERC instructs the emulator to deploy the desired B5G topology, using the information contained in the topology file. The emulator then interacts with the host to create the network emulated nodes, link them with the appropriate Linux bridges, and generate an emulation session ID (see steps 10 to 14 in Figure 6.2). The ERC retrieves this emulation session ID from the emulator, as it will be necessary for subsequent steps, and passes it to the orchestrator (see steps 15 and 16 in Figure 6.2).

Finally, the NRC connects to the emulated network nodes, configures their roles, deploys their respective software components, and configures them for the specific use case (see steps 17 to 19 in Figure 6.2).

B5G Network functions

This phase of the COREX execution corresponds to configuring the networking functions that enable various 5G capabilities, such as multi-tenancy and user mobility. The steps COREX follows to perform these tasks are described in the sequence diagram of Figure 6.3.

First, the HRC checks if the network drivers and kernel modules are properly installed. If they are absent, it warns the user and installs them (see steps 1 to 3 in Figure 6.3). Once all the necessary modules are loaded, the NRC sends instructions to the compute network nodes to start the Open vSwitch (OVS) module. This step is complex because OVS consists of two main functional planes (User and Kernel), and since the CORE emulator instantiates namespaces with a shared kernel, COREX needs to isolate the user plane for each OVS bridge so they belong to different namespaces and access the kernel via different sockets.

Fig. 6.2 Flow chart of the execution for the CORExLAB for the creation of the emulated B5G network topology and configuration including the HRC, ERC and NRC.

Once OVS is started, the NRC executes a set of OVS bridging commands and configures the corresponding OpenFlow rules in each bridge, depending on the stakeholder's role and node (see steps 4 to 8 in Figure 6.3). Next, the NRC creates mirror interfaces using Traffic Control (TC) from the Core segment of the B5G network to the Service Layers. This allows a NIDS to be deployed in the Service layer to detect cyberattacks (see step 9 in Figure 6.3).

After configuring the OVS bridges, the NRC instructs the nodes to create GTP tunnels, which will encapsulate network traffic, enabling user mobility across the network (see step 10 in Figure 6.3). Finally, the NRC verifies that the datapath is properly configured and that the Service layer records network traffic with multiple nested encapsulations (see steps 11 and 12 in Figure 6.3). Section X provides an extended version of the emulated datapath of the B5G network.

At this point, the B5G network topology has been deployed and has a functional datapath prepared with the different network segments and computing layers ready to execute the desired set of experiments.

B5G Experiment launch

This phase of the COREX execution corresponds to the experiment itself, involving the startup of software components for monitoring, analysis, logs collection, and the subsequent experiment launch, in our running example cyberattack. The steps in this phase are detailed in Figure 6.4. The framework is capable of executing any validation experiment that the researcher wishes to perform, following a prior configuration phase. For the purposes of this project, a DDoS use case has been designed to provide essential and foundational insights into the proposed framework. The framework sets up a use case scenario in which various emulated nodes are instantiated with specific roles, such as computing nodes, management nodes, service nodes, and others. These roles are a crucial part of the experiment, as they define the actors involved in the use case. For example, in a DDoS attack on a B5G infrastructure, the roles include: attackers (infected UEs), ISP and DSP computing nodes, management nodes (software components related to a self-protection loop for analysis, decision-making, and orchestration tasks), service nodes (software components within the self-protection loop responsible for threat detection), and victims (targets of the attackers) that host a service.

The NRC is the primary controller interacting in this phase. It sends instructions to the emulated network nodes to start the previously installed software components. Depending on the use case and the node's role in the experiment, these software components may include

Fig. 6.3 Flow chart of the execution for the CORExLAB configuration of the networking phase and the B5G datapath including the HRC and NRC.

databases (such as MySQL), message bus brokers (like RabbitMQ), monitoring tools (for network flows, interfaces, and other resources), network actuators, or cognitive components for analysis and decision-making tasks (see steps 1 and 2 in Figure 6.4). Once all software components are active, the NRC triggers the pre-configured cyberattack for the experiment

(see step 3 in Figure 6.4). COREX then waits for a predetermined duration to allow the experiment to run properly, enabling monitoring tools to record every possible metric and change, and cognitive layers to perform their analysis and close the self-protection loop with the network actuators.

After the attack concludes, the NRC gracefully shuts down the active triggers and software components. This ensures that all components finish their logging tasks and that all metrics are recorded in the DB before stopping.

Fig. 6.4 Flow chart of the execution for the CORExLAB of the experiment phase including the NRC.

Logging collection

This section covers the last phase of the COREX execution, which involves logging, collecting results, and shutting down the B5G network topology. Figure 6.5 depicts a sequence diagram of the steps followed in this phase.

After the experiment concludes and the software components are gracefully turned off, the LRC instructs the emulated network nodes to retrieve all logs related to the experiment (see step 1 in Figure 6.5). The LRC is composed by a set of enablers that perform, agnostically to the technology, the dump and copy of the logs such as “sql” files, journal files, software components log files, etc. Each node, depending on its role, will dump the relevant logs. For example, a management node hosting a DB will export the DB to a “.sql” file. Other software components will dump their logs into a designated logs directory, creating a package that is returned to the LRC and sent to the COREX orchestrator (see steps 2 to 6 in Figure 6.5).

Once the COREX orchestrator has collected all logs from all nodes into the specific directory tree, the ERC initiates the shutdown process for the B5G network topology. The CORE emulator removes the links from the created bridges, deletes the network namespaces, and closes the session. Finally, the ERC cleans up any residual network topology and gracefully shuts down the emulator (see steps 7 to 11 in Figure 6.5).

At this point, COREX sends the collected logs package to the user, marking the end of the experiment. If multiple experiments and topologies are provided in the initial step, COREX can run them in a loop and provide separate logs packages with unique identifiers for each experiment run.

6.4.1 Datapath design

One of COREX’s most important functionalities is the ability to create the B5G datapath, which enables user mobility and multi-tenancy. While this is briefly touched upon in Section 6.4 during the second phase of the design, this section covers the underlying technologies and techniques used to design and implement the B5G datapath.

First, even after the physical datapath between the Edge and Core segments has been established, it is necessary to instantiate the overlay networks associated with mobile edge computing infrastructures (e.g., multi-tenancy) and B5G networks. Figure 6.6 illustrates an example B5G network topology created using COREX, showing the actual links among the emulated nodes, bridges, and interfaces. OVS is utilized as the primary bridging and tunneling tool, providing the necessary isolation and switching capabilities within each

Fig. 6.5 Flow chart of the execution for the CORExLAB in the logging steps which include the LRC and ERC.

compute network stakeholder (ISP and DSP). Due to the network's complexity, a double-bridge approach is employed in each ISP segment: outer and inner bridges. The outer bridges serve as the edges of each ISP segment: the Edge ISP outer bridge is closer to the final UE, while the Core ISP outer bridge is nearer to the inter-domain segment. The inner bridges, positioned close to each other, encapsulate incoming or outgoing network traffic to isolate it, thus enabling multi-tenancy capabilities in the end-to-end communications between the Mobile Edge Computing infrastructure.

In Figure 6.6, multiple interfaces are depicted across the infrastructure. The blue squares represent the physical interfaces found within the ISP and DSPs (see 1 in Figure 6.6). The yellow ones are logical interfaces, typically seen in the ISP and connected to the DSPs'

virtual machines by the virtual switches (see 2 in Figure 6.6). It's important to note that a DSP will consider its own interfaces as physical, which is why they are shown in blue (see 3 and 7 in Figure 6.6). The red interfaces connect to the management layer, allowing the compute layer to connect with the DB, message bus broker, and other cognitive capabilities hosted in the management plane. There are two main switches per ISP that allow the outer and inner connections between the ISP and the DSPs. The inner switches (see 4 in Figure 6.6) connect the Edge segment with the Core segment, providing the infrastructure with the isolation of the multiple tenants with technologies such as VXLAN, GRE, or GENEVE (see 5 in Figure 6.6). On the other hand, the outer switches connect the ISP with the RAN and Interdomain segments, for the Edge and Core ISP respectively (see 2 and 8 in Figure 6.6). Lastly, the orange squares are used to mirror incoming traffic for monitoring purposes (see 6 in Figure 6.6).

Fig. 6.6 Example of B5G network datapath achieved with COREX.

Code block 6.1 Snippet of ovs start process isolated for each namespace

```
1 #!/usr/bin/env bash
2
```

```

3 ovsdb-tool create "${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_DB_FILE}" "${OVS_PATH}/vswitch.ovsschema"
4
5 ovsdb-server "${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_DB_FILE}" --remote=punix:"${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_SOCKET}"
  " \
6     --unixctl="${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_RUNDIR}/ovsdb-server.ctl" \
7     --pidfile="${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_RUNDIR}/ovsdb-server.pid" \
8     --log-file="${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_LOGDIR}/ovsdb-server.log" \
9     --remote=db:Open_vSwitch,Open_vSwitch,manager_options \
10    --private-key=db:Open_vSwitch,SSL,private_key \
11    --certificate=db:Open_vSwitch,SSL,certificate \
12    --bootstrap-ca-cert=db:Open_vSwitch,SSL,ca_cert \
13    --detach --no-chdir
14
15 ovs-vswitchd unix:"${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_SOCKET}" \
16     -vconsole:emer -vsyslog:err -vfile:info \
17     --detach --no-chdir --monitor \
18     --pidfile="${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_RUNDIR}/ovs-vswitchd.pid" \
19     --log-file="${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_LOGDIR}/ovs-vswitchd.log" \
20     --unixctl="${NODE_PATH}/${OVS_RUNDIR}/ovs-vswitchd.ctl"

```

```

root@EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1:/tmp/pycore.39085/EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1.conf# ovs-ofctl dump-flows br-ctc-n6 table=4
cookie=0x0, duration=328.925s, table=4, n_packets=60, n_bytes=5088, in_port=eth4 actions=load:0x20d0->NXM_NX_TUN_ID[],output:"vxlan_1"
cookie=0x0, duration=328.909s, table=4, n_packets=57, n_bytes=4804, in_port=eth5 actions=load:0x2198->NXM_NX_TUN_ID[],output:"vxlan_1"
cookie=0x0, duration=328.917s, table=4, n_packets=30, n_bytes=2507, tun_id=0x20d0 actions=output:eth4
cookie=0x0, duration=328.902s, table=4, n_packets=33, n_bytes=2828, tun_id=0x2198 actions=output:eth5
root@EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1:/tmp/pycore.39085/EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1.conf#

```

Fig. 6.7 Example of B5G network datapath achieved with COREX.

To achieve the required datapath with OVS, each namespace instance must run its own isolated OVS daemon connected to a shared Linux OVS kernel module via a unique socket. This setup is complex, necessitating a specialized approach to starting OVS. Instead of the standard `ovs-start` command, a new DB schema must be created in the specific namespace's path where OVS is executed. The following bash snippet in Code Block 6.1 demonstrates how to isolate the server and vswitch daemon. Variables such as `NODE_PATH` and `OVS_SOCKET` are automatically defined based on the Linux paths and the names of the emulated network nodes. Additionally, Figure 6.7 shows the output of the OpenFlow rules applied by COREX to achieve VXLAN encapsulation in the inner OVS bridge at the Edge ISP computer within the topology.

6.4.2 Experiment design

An experiment in the context of this work consists of series of configurations and elements:

1. A B5G emulated network topology.
2. A set of software components deployed over the different computing layers of the topology (compute, management and service).
3. The selection of roles and stakeholders among stakeholders and nodes within the emulated topology.
4. A particular use case scenario where the network traffic will have a concrete shape and purpose.

The previous section covered the necessary information about the design and creation of the B5G and multi-tenant datapath to execute the experiment with the proposed framework. This section provides an understanding of the remaining steps needed for the design and execution experiments, such as role selection, software components instantiation, etc.

Starting with the division of roles, for this project, the roles have been categorized into UEs, Inter-domain Servers, Compute, Management, and Service. These roles enable COREX to identify which set of software components need to be deployed on any node configured with a specific role. UEs are equipped with the necessary components or triggers to generate network traffic directed towards the Servers. This traffic traverses the entire B5G network infrastructure, ultimately reaching the inter-domain segment where the Servers reside. These servers may host resources such as video or file servers that the UEs can access.

The Compute nodes are provided with monitoring tools across two primary domains: network flow and topology. These tools record the status of the nodes they are deployed on. Additionally, Compute nodes are equipped with network controllers that enable infrastructure protection by inserting network firewalling rules into the datapath.

The Service nodes have monitoring tools similar to those on the Compute nodes but with enhanced NIDS capabilities to detect and alert on malicious incoming traffic. Finally, the Management nodes host components responsible for data recording, message brokering,

cognitive analysis, and orchestration. These cognitive components and orchestrators form the brain of the closed control loops (see Section 4.3 for further details), providing the network topology with analysis and decision-making capabilities when a cyberattack is detected.

Finally, the use case scenario depicts the type of network traffic the experiment is handling. For instance, UEs might deploy a video stream consumer component. This component connects to the inter-domain servers, which are streaming a video, allowing the UE to start consuming the video and thus creating a specific traffic pattern within the B5G emulated infrastructure.

In a different scenario, the UEs could launch a coordinated DDoS attack using a tool like Bonesi, targeting the same servers and disrupting the video stream services. These varied configurations of the use case provide diverse network patterns and cover a broad spectrum of potential attack scenarios in the context of B5G network cybersecurity. This approach ensures that the experiment addresses a wide range of possible threats and behaviors within a B5G network environment.

6.4.3 Distributed emulation

One of the features of the CORE emulator is its ability to distribute emulated network topologies across multiple physical machines. This approach enhances network throughput and performance by sharing the computational load, such as CPU and memory usage, among several physical components.

COREX has been designed and developed to support this feature with minimal impact on the codebase. The user can simply select a single variable in the scenario configuration to indicate whether the experiment is distributed. When any of the COREX components (HRC, ERC, NRC, or LC) issues an instruction to be executed in any of the domains (Host, Emulator, or Network nodes), the command is evaluated by the function provided in Code Block 6.2. This function returns the appropriate command based on whether the experiment is distributed. This design choice makes COREX robust and simplifies maintenance, as there is only one point in the software where this feature is handled.

Code block 6.2 Snippet of the distributed execution of commands with COREX

```
1 function exec_remote_or_local() {
2     local server_ip=$1
3     local command=$2
4
5     if [ "$DISTRIBUTED_MODE" = true ] && [ -n "$server_ip" ]; then
6         printf "ssh -i %q root@%q %q" "$CORE_PUB_KEY" "$server_ip" "$command"
7     else
8         echo "$command"
9     fi
10 }
```

6.5 Validation

This section discusses the emulation and experiment scenarios designed to validate and evaluate the proposed framework architecture and the associated prototype implemented. The experiments are divided into two main groups: one without distribution of the emulation across different physical machines, referred to as “standalone”; and the same scenarios but distributed across multiple machines. The entire emulation environment has been executed on up to four physical machines with the following specifications: Ubuntu 20.04, Intel Xeon E5-2650 @2.8GHz CPU, and 64GB DDR3 RAM, as discussed in Section 3.1.2.

To efficiently evaluate the performance and limitations of the proposed framework, the experiments utilize a variety of B5G network topologies executed by the COREX framework. In these experiments, UEs are infected by a botnet and perform a DDoS attack through the B5G network infrastructure to a final destination. Additionally, a self-protection loop of three steps is instantiated in each experiment to detect, plan and mitigate the incoming threats. This is just for use case purposes for this experimental setup, as the cyber incident scenario is further described and studied in deeper analysis of Chapter 7.

Metrics are recorded during the attack to provide insights into the behavior of the framework and the emulated infrastructure, whether in standalone or distributed mode. The experimental setup for each topology is summarized in Table 6.1. For each configuration, various plots and graphs have been generated. However, to maintain clarity and ensure that

the validation insights are easily understood by the reader, only the most relevant results have been included.

Configuration	Values	Units
Number of UEs	[2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64]	UEs
Bandwidth each UE	[16, 32, 64]	Mbps
Number of Edge servers	1	Edge servers
Number of Core servers	1	Core servers
DDoS exploited protocol	UDP	protocol
Self-protection loop technology	TC	technology
Emulation mode	[Standalone, Distributed]	mode

Table 6.1 Experiment's configurations, with a total of 36 different experiments.

6.5.1 Time execution comparison: standalone vs distributed emulation environment

The first validation experiment presented in this chapter involves executing the framework to emulate an entire B5G network infrastructure, launch a DDoS attack, and carry out the corresponding cognitive self-protection loop to detect, plan, and mitigate the threat. To achieve this, the initial metrics to be analyzed are execution times. These times are categorized into Setup, Configuration, Experiment, Results, and Restoring, which encompass the following steps:

- **Setup:** This phase involves all checks and file sourcing required for the framework to initiate the B5G network topology emulation. The steps involved are numbered 1 to 16 in Figure 6.2.
- **Configuration:** This phase covers the network and host configurations necessary to prepare the B5G datapath and the software components involved in the specific use case of the self-protection loop that will be executed to counter the cyberattack. The steps range from 17 to 19 in Figure 6.2 and continue from 1 to 12 in Figure 6.3.

- **Experiment:** This phase includes steps 1 to 5 in Figure 6.4, which pertain to the execution of each software component required for the cognitive self-protection loop, the activation of metric recorders, and the coordinated execution of the DDoS attack. For this phase, a 2-minute (120-second) attack duration has been established, after which the botnet will automatically cease the attack.
- **Results:** This phase involves the execution of the framework's agnostic tool responsible for recording all necessary logs to capture the experiment's results. These steps are numbered 1 to 6 in Figure 6.5.
- **Restoring:** Often underrated, this phase is crucial for ensuring a clean and fresh machine, ready for setting up a new emulation environment. The steps required to clean and restore the physical machine to its previous healthy state are carried out in this phase, and they are numbered 7 to 12 in Figure 6.5.

Firstly, Figures 6.8 and 6.9 present the execution times and trends of the proposed framework for standalone and distributed scenarios, respectively, as the topology size increases. Secondly, Figures 6.10 and 6.11 compare the actual versus expected bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the topology for both standalone and distributed methods. These two figures highlight the limitations of the emulation on physical machines under high-load attacks.

Figure 6.8a illustrates the time consumed by a tool emulating 5G network infrastructures for different numbers of UEs. The total time increases as the number of UEs rises, indicating scalability with higher complexity. The phases of the process (Setup, Configuration, Experiment, Results, and Restoring) show varying impacts. Configuration and Results times remain relatively stable, suggesting these phases are not heavily influenced by the number of UEs. In contrast, the Setup and Restoring phases see significant increases, highlighting these as the most resource-intensive stages. This suggests a need for optimization in the Setup and Restoring phases for handling larger numbers of UEs efficiently. On the other hand, Figure 6.8b plot provides a clearer view of the time consumed by the COREX in a log-scale view.

In summary, the framework demonstrates scalable performance with predictable increases in time consumption for specific phases as the number of UEs grows, emphasizing the importance of optimizing the Experiment and Results stages to enhance overall efficiency.

(a) Nominal execution times of the 5 phases of the COREX framework from 2 to 64 connected UEs in standalone emulation mode. (b) Trend lines of the execution times of the 5 phases of the COREX framework from 2 to 64 connected UEs in standalone emulation mode.

Fig. 6.8 Execution times of the 5 phases of the COREX framework for multiple sizes of B5G topology, in standalone emulation mode.

Figures 6.9a and 6.9b represent the time consumed by the COREX 5G network infrastructures, distributing the topology across four physical machines. The experiments, conducted with varying numbers of UEs show that total time increases as the number of UEs rises. The stacked bars illustrate the time spent on different phases: Setup, Configuration, Experiment, Results, and Restoring. Notably, the Setup and Restoring phases experience the most significant increases in the time consumption, while the Configuration and Results times remain relatively stable, indicating that these phases are less impacted by the number of UEs.

In the log-scale view of the same results, the exponential growth in time for the Setup and Restoring phases is more evident, emphasizing the need for optimization in these areas to handle larger numbers of UEs efficiently. The Configuration and Results phases continue to show minimal growth, suggesting they are well-optimized and not significantly influenced by the distribution of the topology across multiple machines. This highlights that while the distributed setup helps manage larger loads, the focus should be on improving the Experiment and Results phases to ensure scalable and efficient performance.

(a) Nominal execution times of the 5 phases of the COREX framework from 2 to 64 connected UEs in distributed emulation mode. (b) Trend lines of the execution times of the 5 phases of the COREX framework from 2 to 64 connected UEs in distributed emulation mode.

Fig. 6.9 Execution times of the 5 phases of the COREX framework for multiple sizes of B5G topology, in distributed emulation mode.

Tables 6.2 and 6.3 provide the whole results of the consumed time for the COREX to execute each experiment, since the Setup to the Restoring phases for each standalone and distributed modes, respectively, and for each number of UEs connected to the B5G network topology.

UEs	Setup	Configuration	Experiment	Results	Restoring
2	12.0	137.0	126.0	252.0	16.0
4	13.0	134.0	126.0	257.0	17.0
8	15.0	133.0	126.0	266.0	17.0
16	19.0	144.0	127.0	308.0	20.0
32	28.0	163.0	130.0	283.0	23.0
64	47.0	189.0	135.0	269.0	29.0

Table 6.2 Execution times in seconds of the 5 phases of the COREX framework for multiple sizes of B5G topology, in standalone emulation mode.

UEs	Setup	Configuration	Experiment	Results	Restoring
2	87.0	168.0	133.0	289.0	40.0
4	95.0	172.0	134.0	257.0	41.0
8	112.0	180.0	134.0	263.0	42.0
16	145.0	196.0	134.0	266.0	44.0
32	212.0	230.0	137.0	285.0	136.0
64	347.0	303.0	140.0	259.0	142.0

Table 6.3 Execution times in seconds of the 5 phases of the COREX framework for multiple sizes of B5G topology, in distributed emulation mode.

6.5.2 Bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the B5G network emulation

The two new plots in Figures 6.10a and 6.10b illustrate the bandwidth achieved during DDoS attacks on a standalone physical machine, comparing the expected bandwidth (yellow bars) with the actual bandwidth achieved (blue bars). Figure 6.10a, with lower bandwidth levels (32, 64, 128 Mbps) and 2 connected UEs, the framework demonstrates close alignment between the expected and actual bandwidths. The actual achieved bandwidths (30.96, 62.00, 124.34 Mbps) are very close to the expected values, indicating that the standalone machine can effectively handle lower attack loads and maintain network performance.

In Figure 6.10b, dealing with higher bandwidth levels (1024, 2048, 4096 Mbps) and 64 connected UEs, there is a more noticeable discrepancy between the expected and actual achieved bandwidths. The actual achieved bandwidths (491.96, 965.55, 1909.94 Mbps) fall short of the expected targets, particularly at higher bandwidth levels. This suggests that, similar to the distributed setup, the standalone machine's efficiency decreases under higher load conditions. Comparing with the previous plots on distributed machines, the standalone setup shows slightly lower achieved bandwidths under high-load scenarios, indicating that distributing the infrastructure across multiple machines helps improve performance and manage higher bandwidth DDoS attacks more effectively.

Figure 6.11 contains two subplots, 6.11a and 6.11b that analyze the bandwidth achieved during DDoS attacks, comparing the expected bandwidth (yellow bars) with the actual

(a) Actual vs expected bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the B5G network for standalone emulation mode for 2 connected UEs. (b) Actual vs expected bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the B5G network for standalone emulation mode for 64 connected UEs.

Fig. 6.10 Actual vs expected bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the B5G network for standalone emulation mode.

bandwidth achieved (blue bars). In the first Figure 6.11a, with lower bandwidth levels (32, 64, 128 Mbps) and 2 connected UEs, the framework closely matches the expected bandwidth values. The actual achieved bandwidths (31.87, 63.88, 127.92 Mbps) are nearly identical to the expected values, indicating that the network infrastructure maintains its performance effectively under lower attack loads.

On the other hand, Figure 6.11b, with higher bandwidth levels (1024, 2048, 4096 Mbps) and 64 connected UEs, there is a noticeable discrepancy between the expected and actual achieved bandwidth. The actual achieved bandwidths (532.30, 1050.43, 2089.25 Mbps) fall short of the expected targets, especially as the attack bandwidth increases. This suggests that while the network performs well at lower bandwidth levels, its efficiency decreases under higher load conditions, indicating potential areas for improvement in managing high-bandwidth scenarios. Moreover, note that in the distributed approach depicted in Figure 6.11, the achieved bandwidth increases by 51.01%, whereas in Figure 6.10, it reaches 46.62%.

This indicates a slightly better performance for the distributed approach compared to the standalone version.

(a) Actual vs expected bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the B5G network for distributed emulation mode for 2 connected UEs. (b) Actual vs expected bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the B5G network for distributed emulation mode for 64 connected UEs

Fig. 6.11 Actual vs expected bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment of the B5G network for distributed emulation mode.

6.5.3 Cognitive self-protection loop performance

So far, the standalone version of the experiment has outperformed the distributed one in terms of the time required to execute the experiment. However, when comparing the achieved bandwidth in the Edge segment of the emulation environment with additional network emulated nodes, the distributed version performs slightly better, reaching almost 1 Gbps more than the standalone version. While this difference may not seem significant enough to favor the distributed approach for this type of experiment, it's important to remember that the experiment involves more than just executing a DDoS attack—it also includes the automated execution of a cognitive self-protection loop to mitigate the incoming threat. For this reason, the following two Figures 6.12 and 6.13 offer a new perspective on the results, demonstrating how the distributed approach outperforms the standalone version in stopping the attack.

Figures 6.12a and 6.12b compare the bandwidth measured in different parts of the 5G network during a DDoS attack. The blue plot represents the bandwidth at the edge, closest to the attack source, while the orange plot shows the bandwidth at the core, where the attack has either been mitigated or is being managed by the self-protection loop. In Figure 6.12a with 8 UEs, the edge bandwidth remains significantly higher than the core bandwidth throughout the experiment, indicating effective mitigation as the core bandwidth stabilizes at lower levels despite the ongoing attack at the edge.

In the second Figure 6.12b with 32 UEs, a similar pattern is observed but with much higher values, reflecting the increased load. The edge bandwidth reaches much higher peaks compared to the core, which shows substantial reduction due to the self-protection measures. The disparity between edge and core bandwidth is more pronounced with 32 UEs, underscoring the effectiveness of the self-protection loop in handling higher volumes of traffic. This comparison demonstrates that the self-protection mechanism consistently reduces the impact of attacks from the edge to the core, even as the number of UEs increases, although the overall efficiency slightly diminishes under heavier loads.

(a) Bandwidth before (orange) and after (blue) the topology location of the mitigation of the DDoS attack for standalone emulation mode for 8 infected UEs. (b) Bandwidth before (orange) and after (blue) the topology location of the mitigation of the DDoS attack for standalone emulation mode for 32 infected UEs.

Fig. 6.12 Bandwidth before (orange) and after (blue) the topology location of the mitigation of the DDoS attack for standalone emulation mode.

Figure 6.13a represents the experiment with 8 UEs, the edge bandwidth remains significantly higher than the core bandwidth throughout, similar to the standalone machine scenario. However, the core bandwidth in the distributed setup stabilizes at lower levels more quickly, indicating efficient mitigation of the attack. This suggests that distributing the network infrastructure across multiple machines enhances the effectiveness of the self-protection loop in handling attacks.

On the other hand, Figure 6.13b that depicts the experiment with 32 UEs, the edge bandwidth peaks are much higher, but the core bandwidth shows a more pronounced reduction compared to the standalone machine setup. The mitigation process is clearly more effective in the distributed setup, as evidenced by the consistently lower core bandwidth levels despite the higher edge load. This comparison indicates that the distributed setup significantly improves the network's ability to manage and mitigate DDoS attacks, especially as the number of UEs increases, highlighting the advantages of a distributed infrastructure in maintaining network performance under heavy attack loads.

(a) Bandwidth before (orange) and after (blue) the topology location of the mitigation of the DDoS attack for distributed emulation mode for 8 infected UEs

(b) Bandwidth before (orange) and after (blue) the topology location of the mitigation of the DDoS attack for distributed emulation mode for 32 infected UEs.

Fig. 6.13 Bandwidth before (orange) and after (blue) the topology location of the mitigation of the DDoS attack for distributed emulation mode.

In Figure 6.12b, the system becomes completely unstable, unable to mitigate the cyber-attack. In contrast, as shown in Figure 6.13b, under the distributed approach, the system

successfully mitigates up to 50% of the attack during the two minutes it was launched. This demonstrates the importance of distributing the B5G emulated topology, as it provides a more stable testbed for validating and evaluating the self-protection components.

6.6 Conclusions

This chapter presents a novel automation framework designed to deploy B5G topologies and execute experiments focused on cybersecurity in telecommunications. The framework is characterized by its robust architecture and orchestration capabilities, interacting seamlessly with the three key domains of the experimental tasks: host, emulator, and network emulated nodes. The primary objective has been to automate the deployment of emulated B5G network topologies, facilitate the execution of experiments, and enable the ability to switch between different predefined use cases. Additionally, the framework supports the distribution and orchestration of the emulated B5G network topology over multiple physical host machines.

The experimental evaluation demonstrates the framework's effectiveness and efficiency. The results shown in Section 6.5 provide comprehensive insights into the performance and scalability of the framework.

Performance and Scalability

- **Standalone vs. Distributed Execution Times:** The execution times for both standalone and distributed scenarios show that the total time increases as the number of UEs grows. However, the distributed setup generally does not reduce the overall execution time, from 699.00 seconds for the fastest distributed experiment, to 1191.00 seconds for the lowest. Thus highlighting the relevant necessity of studying carefully the use case to be investigated, and decide whether the execution time of the experiment is crucial to the results or not, as the distributed offers other key benefits such as higher bandwidth.
- **Bandwidth Achievements:** The results indicate that while the standalone setup meets the expected bandwidth at lower loads with up to a 97.14% of the total bandwidth achieved in the Edge segment, it struggles under higher loads, leading to a total of 46.62% of the achieved bandwidth when executing up to 4096 Mbps of DDoS attack. In contrast, the distributed setup achieves closer to the expected bandwidth values (99.93% for 128 Mbps), even at higher loads with a 51% of achieved bandwidth

when executing 4096 Mbps, demonstrating the framework's capability to maintain performance under stress.

Effectiveness in self-protection Experiments The framework's ability to automate the deployment and execution of experiments is evident from the consistent results across different scenarios. Under the use case of a self-protection loop, the experiments effectively measure the framework's capacity to detect, plan, and mitigate cybersecurity threats in B5G networks. The metrics recorded during the experiments provide valuable insights into the behavior of both the framework and the emulated infrastructure.

Key Benefits

- **Robust Architecture:** The framework's architecture efficiently handles the interaction between hosts, emulators, and network nodes, ensuring smooth orchestration and management of complex B5G topologies.
- **Automation Capabilities:** Automating the deployment and execution of experiments significantly reduces manual effort and potential for human error, enhancing the reliability and reproducibility of cybersecurity experiments.
- **Scalability:** The distribution of emulated topologies across multiple physical machines demonstrates the framework's scalability, making it suitable for large-scale B5G network emulations.

Future work will focus on enhancing the framework's capabilities by incorporating more advanced features such as dynamic topology adjustments during runtime and improved resource allocation strategies to further optimize performance under varying load conditions. Additionally, we aim to integrate ML algorithms for more sophisticated attack detection and mitigation, increasing the framework's adaptability to emerging cybersecurity threats. Expanding the scope of predefined use cases and supporting a broader range of network protocols will also be prioritized to make the framework more versatile for various research and industrial applications.

In conclusion, the proposed automation framework for B5G topology deployment and cybersecurity experimentation shows significant promise in enhancing the efficiency, scalability, and reliability of network emulation tasks. Its robust architecture, comprehensive automation features, and ability to distribute workloads across multiple machines make it a valuable asset for researchers and engineers in the field of telecommunications and cybersecurity.

Chapter 7

Topology aware Self-Protection Framework for 5G-IoT Security

Clarification

This chapter, along with all its contributions, is directly related to one of the accepted and published outcomes of the PhD candidate entitled “Topology-aware Cognitive Self-protection Framework for Automated Detection and Mitigation of Security and Privacy Incidents in 5G-IoT Networks” and found in [44]. Additionally, it has been enhanced and expanded with a completely fresh and new testbed that enables the reader with a comprehensive understanding of the impact of the research done within this topic.

7.1 Introduction

The deployment of IoT systems is growing rapidly worldwide, fuelled by 5G technology [45]. 5G is a key technology able to provide mass connectivity for IoT devices whilst delivering high data rates, higher bandwidth, and low latency in IoT landscapes, allowing it to meet the challenging demands and QoS parameters of new use cases otherwise unforeseen in 4G/LLDP networks. Similarly, the amount of security incidents is proliferating as IoT

scenarios are rolled out, involving a huge number of unattended, resource-constrained, and hence vulnerable, IoT devices and sensors. Simultaneously, cyber-attacks are becoming more sophisticated, thus demanding strengthened cyber security capabilities, along with more effective mechanisms for attack detection and mitigation.

As defined by 5G PPP in [46], there are different stakeholders involved in the provisioning of network resources in 5G-IoT networks. A major role is played by DSPs, supplying a range of digital services to different verticals, industries, or end-users. virtual Infrastructure Service Provider (vISP) provide and operates virtualized physical infrastructure comprising networking and computing resources, offering Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) to DSPs. Hence, different DSPs can share a common physical multi-tenant infrastructure provided and managed by the same vISP, resulting in savings in Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX).

However, the deployment of 5G-IoT multi-tenant networks implies the use of overlay networks with different levels of nested encapsulation to support user mobility, e.g. GTP, and tenant isolation, using protocols such as VXLAN, or GRE. Therefore, an advanced security solution for this type of network must provide protection not only for traditional IP traffic but also for fine-grained security capabilities to handle the complex network traffic associated with multi-tenant network topologies.

Moreover, a major challenge facing the field of cybersecurity in telecommunications is the rapid adoption of new techniques and technologies, which continuously expand network infrastructures and topologies. This results in dynamic, constantly evolving B5G network topologies, where multiple stakeholders are frequently introduced. Additionally, actors within the topology may appear or disappear automatically due to orchestration systems such as Kubernetes. Consequently, cybersecurity engineers must maintain an up-to-date, comprehensive view of the topology in real time to design effective security and mitigation strategies. For the purposes of this chapter, we refer to this concept as “topology-awareness,” which is a primary contribution of the cognitive self-protection framework developed herein.

The main contribution of this research work is the design, prototyping, and validation of a novel automated Cognitive Self-protection framework with topology awareness capabilities

for the detection and mitigation of security and privacy incidents in the wired segments of 5G-IoT multi-tenant networks (i.e., Edge and Core). The following are the main innovations presented in this chapter:

- A novel dynamic IDS for detecting security and privacy incidents, designed to handle the complexity of 5G-IoT multi-tenant network traffic, introduced as the Network Flow Monitoring (NFM) in this chapter.
- An automated, fine-grained mitigation location finder (subcomponent of the Network Self-Healing (NSH)) enabling the topology-awareness, allowing precise enforcement of mitigation actions within the 5G-IoT network topology.
- Development of an automated self-protection loop, integrating the three main software components into a single framework, validated and evaluated across various network topology configurations and mitigation technologies (TC and OVS).

The rest of the chapter is organized as follows. Section 7.2 briefly overviews the current state of the art in 5G-IoT network security. Section 7.3 describes the design, architecture, and functionality of the proposed solution. Then, Section 7.4 discusses the empirical results gathered to validate and evaluate the proposed framework. To conclude, in Section 7.5 we discuss the conclusions and outline our future research lines.

7.2 Related work

The significant number of research activities related to security in 5G-IoT networks is clear evidence of the interest and concern this topic arouses within the research community. A number of publications and surveys such as [47] and [48] highlight security and privacy aspects in 5G-IoT networks as one of the major challenges to be addressed in such architectures.

In [49], authors present a framework able to detect malicious traffic at the IoT-Edge layer and thus, to identify possible infected IoT devices in a botnet network. The analysis is carried out using Sparsity Representation and Reconstruction Error Threshold techniques.

They used the NB-IoT data set to train the ML models and only benign traffic data is used to calculate the threshold error. This framework, however, is not able to protect all segments across the 5G architecture. Moreover, the authors have not considered the classification of 5G multi-tenant traffic.

In [50] and [51], both perform detection, analysis, and mitigation of the attack. [50] presents IoT Botnet Detection and Analysis (IoT-BDA), a framework based on honeypots for detecting, analyzing, identifying, and reporting botnets circulating on the Internet. On the other hand, [51] presents a framework running on the firmware of IoT devices. It tries to use Deep Learning (DL) techniques by using the LSTM algorithm to detect the attack. The mitigation technique is to disable infected IoT devices. Although the above contributions are of great interest, they do not present a solution that can perform fine-grained attack mitigation in overlay networks inherent to 5G multi-tenant deployments.

Authors in [52] propose a self-healing model to detect and mitigate DDoS attacks for SDN deployments with OpenFlow protocol, using POX and RYU as SDN controllers. They reach an accuracy of over 80% in filtering malicious traffic.

A novel SDN-based architecture to identify suspicious nodes in 4G/5G IoT networks and redirect their traffic to a secondary network slice is proposed in [53]. By following this approach, potential threats can be detected at an early stage and limit the damage by DDoS attacks originated in IoT devices.

Authors in [54] propose a self-healing protocol for automatic discovery and maintenance of the network topology in SDN deployments. It provides layer two topology discovery and autonomic fault recovery to enhance the control plane robustness. Preliminary results in a simulated testbed show the proposed protocol recovers the control topology efficiently in terms of time and message load. Similarly, in [55], authors implement a new topology discovery approach on the widely used POX controller platform, and evaluate it for a range of network topologies.

In [56], authors propose an agent-based approach called SHAPE to self-heal and self-protect the system from various kinds of security attacks including DDoS whilst dealing with hardware, software, and network faults.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, none of the existing state-of-the-art publications provides a self-healing mechanism for the detection and mitigation of cyber-attacks in 5G-IoT multi-tenant networks. In other words, detect and stop malicious traffic with no human intervention whilst enabling the enforcement of fine-grained security policies in the data-plane of complex overlay networks. This is the major contribution and innovation presented in this work.

7.3 Cognitive Self-protection framework

Fig. 7.1 Topology-aware Cognitive Self-protection framework flow chart (architectural components and message exchanges).

The Cognitive Self-protection framework presented in this work is composed of three main components whose responsibilities are divided into the accurate detection of the threat (Network Flow Monitoring), analysis, and decision of the action to be taken (Network Self-Healing), and enforcement of the mitigation strategy in the data-plane (Network Self-protection). The following subsections explain the functionality of each component, its responsibility, and its impact on the system as part of the Cognitive Self-protection framework. As depicted in Fig. 7.1, the communication and cooperation between the components are provided by means of a message bus tool. It grants communication between the different architectural components through a publishing/subscription paradigm. The proposed framework uses RabbitMQ [57] as message bus software since it is one of the most popular open-source message brokers. Fig. 7.1 shows the 4 message exchanges implemented for the interaction between the framework components: Network IDS Events, Topology, Network

Healing Instructions and Network Self-protection Confirmations. This section also overviews a 5G-IoT Multi-tenant infrastructure that matches the case of study in this contribution and provides a realistic scenario to validate and empirically evaluate the proposed solution.

7.3.1 5G-IoT multi-Tenant network infrastructure

Fig. 7.2 depicts the 5G-IoT multi-Tenant network infrastructure proposed in this work. Six different network segments can be seen from a bottom-up perspective: (i) the Radio Access Network to connect the IoT devices to the 5G-IoT network through the gNBs and the DUs, (ii) the MEC segment where the multi-tenancy feature is depicted by two different DSPs (notice the orange and blue boxes) sharing the same physical infrastructure provided by one vISP (see the grey boxes), (iii) the transport network connecting the Edge and Core segments, (iv) the core segment with expanded service capabilities, scalability agility, and 5G core network functions such as the SMF, the AMF and the UPF, (v) the service and management layer where the centralized components of the proposed framework are deployed, and finally (vi) the Inter-Domain network segment to reach the internet and other domains.

7.3.2 Network Flow Monitoring

The NFM component is responsible for the detection of the attack. This component relies on the mirrored traffic from the transport network, as depicted in Fig. 7.2. The mirrored network traffic is sent to the Service layer, where this component is centralized and deployed to analyze the traffic introducing almost no additional latency in the primary data-plane.

The detection is carried out by the use of an enhanced NIDS, which will trigger an alert when a threat is registered in the system. The main contribution of this component is the extension of the traditional NIDS to provide detection in complex overlay networks and 5G-IoT network segments, information that traditional NIDS lacks. These extensions allow the accurate detection and classification of a malicious flow with specific, granular and effective alerts. The information provided by this component is separated into three categories differentiated by their purpose: first, metric information of the NIDS, such as the

Fig. 7.2 5G-IoT multi-Tenant network infrastructure with the topology-aware Cognitive Self-protection framework components deployed.

number of total packets of a specific technology that have been filtered or the dropped packets ratio, type of the attack, etc.; second, 5G network information relative to the malicious flow metadata such as information extracted from inner headers, number and types of overlay tunnelling and encapsulation protocols (e.g. VXLAN, GTP, GRE, etc.); and third, additional

alert useful information such as alert type, alert impact, causes of the alert and if the flow is already stopped or not. The NFM extends Snort [58] as the base NIDS. The NFM publishes each alert to the RabbitMQ Network IDS Events exchange, where the following component of the framework is subscribed and will receive it.

7.3.3 Network Self-Healing

The NSH is the component in charge of analyzing the alert triggered by the NFM and deciding where should be stopped the attack. To do so, this component is divided into two different sub-components:

- The Resource Inventory Agent (RIA) is a distributed software deployed in the data-plane (see deployment locations in Fig. 7.2) periodically reporting the information about the network topology (see Topology exchange in Fig. 7.1). This topological information is one of the main innovations of this work as it enables the NSH to determine the best optimal location to stop the attack following a logic predefined by the programmer, such as “near the source”, “near destination”, “n hops from the source”, etc. More details about RIAs’ architecture are presented in [59].
- The Self-Healing Decision Maker (SHDM) receives and aggregates the information about the topology to have a full view of the network. Then, when SHDM receives an alert from NFM, it uses the entire status of the topology to decide the optimal mitigation point where the attack can be stopped. Finally, the SHDM sends a Network Healing Instruction (see Network Healing Instructions exchange in Fig. 7.1) that will be received by the Network Self-Protection component. This instruction contains an action such as performing a drop, redirecting traffic, or mirroring the flow in a specific point of the datapath. These actions can be automated by the administrator through a policy engine in order to define different strategies for each type of attack.

The use case selected to validate this project is a DDoS attack. Such attacks are most effectively mitigated when stopped as close to the detected source as possible. Therefore, the

decision configured by the NSH in this chapter regarding “where to stop the attack” is set to “close to source”. By doing so, the malicious flows are dropped at the nearest point to the origin of the attack, thereby ensuring that the majority of the 5G-IoT network topology remains unaffected and secure.

7.3.4 Network Self-Protection

The Network Self-Protection (NSP) component is responsible for providing the self-protection capabilities in the wired segments of the data-plane, enforcing a set of protection policies. It is based on the well-known virtual switch OVS on which significant extensions have been undertaken to extend the data-plane programmability. The Network Self-protection architecture consists of three sub-components:

- **Protection Decider (PD):** Responsible for deciding on every instant what subset of rules from the complete set of protection rules located in the PD will be enforced in the following sub-component.
- **Datapath Security Controller (DSC):** It processes the network traffic and eventually enforces the protection rules into the data-plane. Every packet through the data-plane is deep inspected and classified, and an action is taken based on the subset of protection rules active at the moment.
- **Protection Control Agent (PCA):** It provides a North Bound Interface (NBI) for the communication with the NSH component (see Network Healing Instructions exchange in Fig. 7.1). The exposed NBI is an intend-based interface receiving technology-independent instructions that are translated into technology-dependent commands to be enforced in the data-plane. It also provides dynamic management of the life cycle of the set of protection rules (installation, modification, and deletion) to the NSH.

7.3.5 DDoS use case

In a UDP DDoS attack, the attacker floods the target system with a high volume of UDP packets, overwhelming the system resources and causing it to become unresponsive. The attacker typically spoofs the source IP addresses to make it challenging to trace the origin of the attack. Since UDP does not verify the recipient's readiness or response, the flood of incoming UDP packets quickly saturates the target's network bandwidth, CPU, and memory resources. Consequently, legitimate traffic cannot reach the intended service, leading to a denial of service for legitimate users. Due to the huge impact of this attack on the overall system performance, this kind of attack has been chosen to demonstrate the suitability of the proposed solution in stressful scenarios. The design of the attack is as follows:

- The Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU) is set to 1500 Bytes.
- The Payload of the sent packets is nearly the maximum MTU, being 1250 Bytes.
- The expected maximum length of the network packet headers through the network is 132 Bytes, as depicted in Fig. 7.3.
- For each experiment, the UEs are configured with a specific bandwidth configuration in order to perform the DDoS attack. This is achieved by configuring the packet rate and packet size of each infected UE. The configurations are summarised in Table 7.1.

Fig. 7.3 5G-IoT multi-tenant network traffic encapsulation pattern.

7.4 Results and empirical validation

7.4.1 Testbed for empirical evaluation

To demonstrate the functionality and feasibility of the framework proposed in this research work, we have developed a testbed environment where a large number of experiments have been executed to gather results for further analysis. The testbed has been an emulated 5G network infrastructure matching the one depicted in Fig. 7.2. The infrastructure is compromised by a UDP DDoS attack launched from the infected IoT devices. In order to empirically validate the proposed framework, it has been tested in two different scenarios. The first scenario (A) has been designed as depicted in Table 7.1 where the key element is the increase of the number of attackers, varying the number of UEs connected to each gNB. Moreover, for each of this configurations, the consumed bandwidth for each UE is set to [4, 8, 16, 32, 64] Mbps, in order to gain sufficient insights about the behaviour of the self-protection loop when the attack bandwidth is increased. The rest of the network elements of the topology are fixed to 1 gNB connected to each DSP, 2 DSPs hosted on each ISP (multi-tenant isolation feature), and 2 Edge nodes connected to 1 Core node. The second scenario (B) has been designed to evaluate a more complex network topology and increase the possible action points where the attack could be mitigated. For scenario B, the number of attackers is the same as in A, but the topology is built as follows: 2 gNB connected to each DSP, 2 DSPs hosted on each ISP, and 4 Edge nodes connected to 1 Core node.

Table 7.1 Network topology for test bed in scenarios A and B.

Scenario	A				B			
No UE x gNB	4	8	12	16	1	2	3	4
No gNB x DSP	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2
No DSP	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
No Edge	2	2	2	2	4	4	4	4
No Core	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Total attacker	16	32	48	64	16	32	48	64

The emulation tool used to deploy both scenarios is CORE [59]. It uses Linux netns to emulate each of the different devices and networks on the infrastructure. The physical

machine where the experiments have been executed has an Ubuntu 20.04 LTS distribution with kernel version 5.15.0. As physical resources, it has a 56-core Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2660 v4 @ 2.00GHz and 128GB DDR4 2400 MHz of RAM, as discussed in Section 3.1.2.

The execution of the experiments consists of the creation of each scenario by running an automated script that performs the following sequence of steps for the creation of the environments leveraging CORE emulator functionalities (see Chapter 6 for further details):

1. Provide network topology information using configuration files.
2. Configure logs and outputs during experiment execution.
3. Set up network protocols and performance configurations for all the interfaces and connections between nodes.
4. Provision nodes with specific software based on their roles (Edge, Core, management, service, IoT device) in the experiment.
5. Create necessary tunnels (VXLAN, GTP, GRE, etc.) to provide multi-tenancy and user mobility features.
6. Launch the attack and activate the Cognitive Self-protection framework components.
7. Conclude the attack, gracefully shut down the topology, and retrieve logs, results, and outputs.

7.4.2 Results

A first set of results are described with Fig. 7.4, which correspond to the configuration shown in Table 7.1 with a fixed bandwidth of 100 Mbps coordinated by all the UEs. This graph is divided into two different parts separated by a vertical red line: the left one related to scenario A and the right one to scenario B. Both parts show the same number of infected IoT devices on the X-axis, as mentioned above (16, 32, 48, and 64). The Y-axis represents the average consumed time for the Cognitive Self-protection framework from the detection to

the mitigation of the attack. This time is represented in seconds and each colour represents the time consumed for each of the three components (blue for NFM, orange for NSH, and green for NSP).

Fig. 7.4 Average time consumed by the Cognitive Self-protection framework, Scenario A (left) against Scenario B (Right).

The collected results can be analysed by considering the overall performance of the framework and by evaluating the individual overhead and behaviour for each component. Fig. 7.4 clearly indicates that, in both scenarios, the overall behaviour of the framework shows good scalability. In the worst case in scenario A, the attack is stopped in less than 41 seconds. In scenario B, with a more distributed network topology, the attack is mitigated in less than 23 seconds for the worst case with 64 infected IoT devices transmitting malicious traffic simultaneously. At first glance, the architectural component that introduces the most overhead is the NSH.

With respect to the individual impact of each component, the NFM outperforms in the overall framework. It shows a stable performance throughout every scenario (A and B) and also when the number of infected IoT devices is increased. For the worst-case setting (64 IoT devices), the time spent by the NFM is 2.06 seconds in scenario A and 2.20 seconds in scenario B. The NFM shows promising results regarding scalability.

As it can be observed by comparing the NSH behaviour in both scenarios, the execution time increases linearly when growing the number of IoT devices. However, the execution time in scenario A is higher for all the different settings when compared to scenario B. For the worst-case setting (64 IoT devices), the NSH required 33.8 seconds in scenario A and 19.4 seconds in scenario B. In scenario A, the topology consists of 2 Edge Compute nodes and 2 gNBs that are connected to each of the DSPs, thus the number of action points to enforce the mitigation of the attack is 4. As the SHDM is the centralized and cognitive component of the Cognitive Self-protection framework that will produce as an output the location to mitigate the threat with the promise of “close to source” (see Section 7.3.3 for more details), all the workload for the study of the best location to mitigate the attack will be carried by itself. However, when switching to scenario B, not only the number of action points to mitigate the threat rise but also the number of distributed RIA components that are responsible for notifying the network topology information in real-time. This is why the NSH in Fig. 7.4 shows a better performance for scenario B. Distributing some workload when the number of attackers is the same is always improving the system.

Regarding the NSP, it shows a higher consumption time for scenario A than scenario B, but remains stable for all settings within each scenario. NSP required roughly 5 seconds in scenario A and approximately 1.5 seconds in scenario B to enforce the healing instructions in the data plane and eventually stop the attack. The NSP has a different response time due to its distributed deployment. This component is distributed over the different compute nodes on the topology, thus the workload is levelled by the number of NSP instances deployed across the infrastructure. Leveraging this distributed feature, Fig. 7.4 shows a better performance in the NSP when the topology grows whilst the number of IoT devices remains constant.

Therefore, the results of the experiments discussed above demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed solution to detect and mitigate cyber-attacks in 5G-IoT networks in an automated manner with no human intervention, showing promising preliminary results.

Comparing mitigation technologies

To effectively validate and evaluate the proposed tool in this chapter, an extended set of experiment has been launched that consists on providing multiple bandwidths and mitigation technologies to perform the “drop close to the source”. Therefore, the following results correspond to that extended set of experiments which relate to the Table 7.1 and each of those scenarios will be set with [4, 8, 16, 32, 64] Mbps of bandwidth for each UE, and the mitigation technologies with OVS and TC. Hence, the total number of executed experiments, which results are explained in this section, is 80.

Figure 7.5a displays the mean times taken by the self-protection loop to detect, plan, and mitigate incoming DDoS attacks across various scenarios. The x-axis represents the number of 5G-IoT devices, and the y-axis represents the bandwidth each IoT device uses to launch the DDoS attack. As the number of devices and their bandwidth increase, the mean time generally rises, with the most significant delays observed at the highest combinations of devices and bandwidth (e.g., 64 devices at 64 Mbps). This suggests that the self-protection loop’s efficiency decreases as the scale and intensity of the attacks grow, highlighting potential areas for optimization in high-load scenarios.

The second heatmap 7.5b illustrates the number of DDoS attacks mitigated by the system under the same conditions. The system’s effectiveness varies, with a general trend of increased mitigation success as both the number of devices and their bandwidth increase. However, there are notable variations, such as lower mitigation at specific high-load points, indicating that while the system can handle increased loads, its performance is not uniformly consistent. This comparison suggests that while the self-protection loop can effectively mitigate attacks, its response time and efficiency can be impacted significantly by higher numbers of devices and greater bandwidth, necessitating further improvements for handling peak loads.

(a) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop to perform the mitigation task. (b) Average number of mitigated malicious flows.

Fig. 7.5 Results for 2 Edge configuration and TC as mitigation technology.

Comparing the heatmaps from the experiments with 4 Edge servers in Figure 7.6 to those with 2 Edge servers in Figure 7.5 reveals notable improvements in the system's performance and efficiency. The mean times for the self-protection loop in Figure 7.6a generally show lower or more consistent values compared to the 2 Edge server setup, indicating that distributing the control layer across more servers reduces the time needed to detect, plan, and mitigate DDoS attacks. Specifically, high-load scenarios with many devices and high bandwidths see less dramatic increases in mean time. The number of mitigated attacks in Figure 7.6b also shows a more consistent and generally higher rate of success in the 4 Edge server configuration. This improved performance suggests that a distributed control layer across more Edge servers enhances the system's ability to handle larger and more intense DDoS attacks, providing better overall network protection and stability.

The two graphs in Figure 7.7 represent the time consumed by the components of the self-protection loop (NFM, NSH, and NSP) to detect (NFM), plan (NSH), and mitigate (NSP) DDoS attacks. The first graph shows the results with 2 Edge servers, and the second with 4 Edge servers.

In the 2 Edge server setup in Figure 7.7a, the total execution time increases significantly as the number of infected 5G-IoT devices grows. The NFM component, responsible for detection, consistently takes the longest time, followed by the NSP (mitigation) and NSH

(a) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop to perform the mitigation task. (b) Average number of mitigated malicious flows.

Fig. 7.6 Results for 4 Edge configuration and TC as mitigation technology.

(planning). As the number of devices increases from 16 to 64, the mean execution time rises sharply, highlighting the strain on the system when fewer resources are available.

In contrast, the 4 Edge server setup in Figure 7.7b shows a more balanced and efficient distribution of tasks. Although the NFM component still consumes the most time, the overall execution times are significantly lower, especially for higher numbers of infected devices. This setup demonstrates a marked improvement in handling increased loads, with the mean execution times being more stable and less prone to dramatic increases as the number of infected devices grows. The results indicate that distributing the control layer across more Edge servers enhances the system's ability to detect, plan, and mitigate DDoS attacks more effectively, leading to better scalability and performance.

In the 2 Edge server setup in Figure 7.8a, the mean times for the detection (NFM), planning (NSH), and mitigation (NSP) of DDoS attacks increase with the number of 5G-IoT devices and their bandwidth. The overall times are higher than those observed with TC, indicating that OVS may be less efficient in this configuration. As the number of devices grows, especially at higher bandwidths, the mean times show a significant rise, highlighting the increased strain on the system.

For the 4 Edge server setup in Figure 7.9a, the times are generally lower than in the 2 Edge server configuration but still higher than those observed with TC. The NFM component

(a) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop components to perform the mitigation task for 2 Edge servers. (b) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop components to perform the mitigation task for 4 Edge servers.

Fig. 7.7 Results for 4 Mbps each UE and TC as mitigation technology.

consistently consumes the most time, followed by NSP and NSH. The increased number of Edge servers helps distribute the load more effectively, but the execution times still indicate room for improvement, especially in handling higher bandwidth scenarios.

(a) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop to perform the mitigation task. (b) Average number of mitigated malicious flows.

Fig. 7.8 Results for 2 Edge configuration and OVS as mitigation technology.

In the 2 Edge server setup in Figure 7.8b, the number of dropped malicious flows varies significantly with the number of devices and their bandwidth. The effectiveness of mitigation fluctuates, with some scenarios showing lower dropped flows than expected. This

inconsistency suggests that the OVS technology struggles to maintain consistent performance under varying load conditions.

The 4 Edge server setup in Figure 7.9b shows more consistent and higher numbers of dropped flows compared to the 2 Edge setup. The system performs better in mitigating attacks, indicating that distributing the control and mitigation processes across more servers enhances the overall effectiveness. However, the performance still does not surpass the results achieved with TC, especially under high-load conditions.

(a) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop to perform the mitigation task. (b) Average number of mitigated malicious flows.

Fig. 7.9 Results for 4 Edge configuration and OVS as mitigation technology.

In the 2 Edge server setup in Figure 7.10a, the execution times for each component (NFM, NSH, NSP) increase with the number of infected devices. The NFM component consistently takes the most time, reflecting the complexity of detection. The overall times are higher compared to the TC setup, suggesting that OVS is less efficient in a limited Edge server configuration.

The 4 Edge server setup in Figure 7.10b shows improved performance over the 2 Edge setup, with lower execution times for each component. However, the times are still higher than those observed with TC, indicating that while OVS benefits from a distributed setup, it remains less efficient than TC in handling DDoS mitigation tasks.

The comparison between TC and OVS technologies for DDoS mitigation reveals key differences in performance and efficiency. TC generally outperforms OVS in both 2 and

(a) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop components to perform the mitigation task for 2 Edge servers. (b) Average time consumed by the cognitive self-protection loop components to perform the mitigation task for 4 Edge servers.

Fig. 7.10 Results for 4 Mbps each UE and OVS as mitigation technology.

4 Edge server configurations, showing lower mean execution times and more consistent mitigation of malicious flows. While distributing the load across more Edge servers improves the performance of both technologies, TC remains more efficient and effective, especially under high-load conditions. OVS, while benefiting from a distributed setup, still shows higher execution times and less consistent mitigation results, indicating a need for further optimization to match the performance levels of TC. Notice that the technologies are under evaluation regarding the self-protection loop components, not as technologies as themselves. While TC performs better as a mitigation technology within the self-protection loop, OVS outperforms TC in the datapath, enabling the handling of high-speed data paths exceeding 10 GB.

7.5 Conclusions

This work presents a novel topology-aware Cognitive Self-protection framework suitable for 5G-IoT multi-tenant networks able to detect and mitigate in an autonomous way cyber-attacks coming from compromised IoT devices and sensors. The proposed solution copes with complex network traffic with multiple levels of nested tunnelling and encapsulation protocols inherent to such infrastructures, such as GTP, VXLAN, or GRE, for example.

Empirical validation and evaluation have been conducted in an emulated testbed using CORE emulator to deploy the 5G-IoT topology. Preliminary results demonstrate the proposed solution stops a DDoS attack from 16 up to 64 infected UEs in less than 41 seconds in the worst-case scenario, showing better performance in more complex scenarios with 4 Edge nodes and 16 gNBs (23 seconds to mitigate the malicious traffic).

Regarding the second set of experiments, it is worth noting the slightly better performance of the system when performing the mitigation with TC instead of OVS. It has been demonstrated that the emulated system does not perform well for high number of UEs, as it is not able to mitigate all the malicious network flows in the time window that the researcher decided to execute the experiment (a maximum of 2 minutes) when reaching 64 infected UEs.

As a future line of work, authors will explore the scalability, efficiency, and performance of the proposed approach in terms of network size (number of UEs, Edge nodes, and CORE nodes). Moreover, the distribution of the Management and Control planes along the different stakeholders of the B5G topology is another future work to have into account in order to enhance the efficiency of the self-protection loop capabilities.

Chapter 8

Distributed Autonomous Loops for DDoS Protection in 5G/6G-IoT Networks

Clarification

This chapter, along with all its contributions, is directly related to one of the accepted and published outcomes of the PhD candidate entitled “Distributed dual-layer Autonomous Closed Loops for Self-Protection of 5G/6G IoT Networks from DDoS Attacks” and found in [60].

8.1 Introduction

We are currently witnessing an exponentially increasing use of IoT devices to date, and growth is expected to remain the same trend [61]. One of the open research questions to be addressed, according to Kaspersky [62], is whether to prioritize the protection of IoT devices or to protect the networks from IoT device attacks. This is due to the interest that wearables, Smart TVs and other gadgets have risen in cyber-criminals, who see an opportunity to use such IoT devices as bots or zombies in cyber attacks. These devices can be used to deploy DDoS attacks, creating botnets capable of leaving large companies and communities without service, and even countries. As reported in October 2017, more than 2 million IoT devices have been infected by Reaper, an evolution of the old Mirai DDoS, and it is considered more

virulent than its predecessor due to the ease of device infection [63]. The current 5G and the foreseen 6G multi-tenant networks are the most predominant networks to be used to scale up the communication networks that interconnect such IoT devices. Therefore, they are also considered susceptible targets of those attackers.

One of the main characteristics in the development of the new generation (5G and 6G) networks that has been promoted is the softwarization and virtualization of network services. In this way, different virtualized systems can be hosted on the same physical infrastructure, providing service to several companies, and sharing space and physical resources. This sharing capabilities is commonly refereed as multi-tenancy. The virtualization of network devices and the usage of tunnelling of network traffic, allows maintaining isolated traffic among the tenants that host the physical infrastructure. However, the usage of tunneling techniques entails new security challenges in the detection of cyber attacks as it may hampers the detection of the attacks. Moreover, the costs associated with the deployment of 5G and 6G infrastructures for RAN and transmission may increase from 60% to 300% [64]. Thus, solutions must be sought to reduce costs, both capital and operational, in the network infrastructure. This mission is hampered by the problems associated with the massive number of connected IoT devices, which expose significantly higher vulnerable perimeters for possible DDoS attacks. An example is the one that happened repeatedly in 2021 on the Voipfone DSP in United Kingdom, which suffered from this type of attacks between September and October, leaving no Voice over IP (VoIP) services to companies that used their products [65]. They indicated the impact caused by such attacks on companies: “if businesses are deprived of their services, they are deprived of business”. This means not only capital loss but also loss of confidence in their services. One of the last Cloudflare’s DDoS report [66] show that network-layer DDoS attacks increased by 109% in 2022 Q2. They also state that for those network-layer threats, attacks Telecommunication companies grew a 66%.

Figure 8.1 presents an approximation of the architecture of a 5G/6G system (5GS/6GS) used to connect IoT networks, consisting of four layers. The IoT Device layer is composed by smartphones and other IoT devices, connected to the corresponding RAN layer provided by the base stations (e.g., 5G gNBs). These gNBs are a set of physical and virtualised

components, starting with the DUs [67], which support the lower layers of the protocol stack such as Radio Link Control (RLC), Medium Access Control (MAC) and physical layers, and ending in the Virtualised Central Units (vCUs)[67], which support different protocols such as Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP) [68], Radio Resource Control (RRC) [69] and Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) [70]. The RAN layer then connects to the Edge layer through the CUs as they are virtualised and deployed in the MEC Network [71] [72] [73]. The aim of this layer is to bring the functionality and computing capacity geographically closer to the end user. Therefore, in addition to network functions, other applications that could be categorised as MEC can also be brought closer. The 5G/6G Core layer provides functions such as SMF, UPF and AMF. These functions have been virtualised. As in the Edge layer, cloudified functionalities in the Core layer can offer Cloud as a Service applications, running in the core network of the infrastructure with a greater computational capacity and a centralisation of resources.

The 5G/6G System (5GS/6GS) architecture presents different stakeholders that are involved in the provisioning of network resources, as presented in the View on 5G Architecture by the 5G Infrastructure Private Public Partnership (5GPPP) [74]. A major role in the provision of 5G/6G services is the DSP, which offers digital services such as enhanced mobile broadband and IoT to various vertical industries, and the role of (Virtual) ISPs offering infrastructure as a service.

Either a DSP or an ISP can implement individual closed control-loops without any human intervention in order to fully automate the response against cyber-attacks in their respective administrative domains. If, in fact, both stakeholders simultaneously do so, each system will work completely independently focused on the protection of the infrastructure of its respective owner. However, it is important to emphasize that all the traffic that is being received by the DSP has necessarily trespassed the ISP domain as the DSP is embedded (virtualized) inside of the ISP domain. Thus, even if both systems work fully independent, the automated cyber-security loop of the DSP may perceive the actions done by the ISP loop and vice versa due to the side-effect that their respective actions cause in the system of the other stakeholder. Thus, if the ISP cyber-security system stops a malicious flow that has

Fig. 8.1 IoT architectural layers coupled with the 5G architecture.

been intended to transverse the DSP, then as a side-effect the DSP cyber-security system will perceive that such malicious flow is not existing anymore (although it will never know the reason for that to happen). Notice how this side-effect causes that they end up collaborating to perform a more effective and efficient mitigation of the attacks even if the two loops operate independently on their respective administrative domains. This is the main hypothesis investigated in this manuscript. The benefits of the dual closed control loop proposed in this chapter is of paramount importance for each of the stakeholders. If the mitigation system only

operates in one of the stakeholders (ISP or DSP), it would be fully responsible for keeping the integrity and availability of the system in the event of an attack, and it could be saturated when the volume of the attack reaches exacerbated proportions. However, by placing such a system in both stakeholders, they will act independently for the mitigation of the same attack, mitigating parts of the ongoing attack and sharing the computational load without even the need to communicate between each other. This means that the DSP will mitigate part of the attack on its infrastructure while the rest of the attack that may go unnoticed will be mitigated by the ISP due to independent operations in their own administrative domains. The same happens in the implementation of a multi-tenant architecture, where each of the tenants, together with its corresponding host, will act cooperatively to mitigate the same attack.

The main contribution of this research is the design, prototyping and validation of a distributed dual-layer cognitive dual loop system to self-protect a multi-stakeholder multi-tenant 5G-IoT infrastructure from DDoS attacks without human intervention. The following contributions and innovations are achieved in this work.

- Autonomous DDoS mitigation system suitable for 5G/6G networks without collateral damage has been achieved through the development of a complex autonomous system, including detection of malicious flows and triggering fine-grained alerts, analysing the attack and determining a plan of intervention, orchestration that arranges the assembled plan and launching the plan at a predetermined time and location.
- distributed DDoS mitigation system between two of the stakeholders, achieving a dual concurrent closed control-loop. The first control loop runs in the ISP concerned with defending its own physical infrastructure and maintaining isolation and continuous operation of its services. The second loop runs in the DSP responsible for the management and safekeeping of its Virtualised Infrastructure Services and Digital Services.
- Distributed DDoS mitigation system involving all the locations that are exposed as part of the perimeter of the infrastructure instead of the traditional centralized approach where the enforcement point is carried out in only the central location.

The rest of the chapter is organised as follows. Section 8.2 exposes the related work with different approaches to the detection, analysis, and mitigation of DDoS attacks in IoT and/or 5G IoT environments. Section 8.3 describes the approach of this contribution by showing the design and architecture towards a self-managed protection for IoT networks. Section 8.4 describes in detail the flow of the contribution in this work, detailing how the collaboration between each of the stakeholders is done. Section 8.5 presents the evaluation and performance of the proposed architecture and system. Section 8.6 concludes the chapter together with future work.

8.2 Related work

Table 8.2 shows a summary of the contributions that have been analyzed to represent the state of the art of this work. Key relevant characteristics have been established and compared to give an overview of the main contribution of our contribution. In order to have a readable table, the column names have been explained in table 8.1 to allow the reader to better understand the analysis carried out.

Table 8.1 Challenges to achieve distributed dual-layer self-protection closed cognitive loop for IoT networks against DDoS attacks.

Group	Code	Description
Stakeholders	I	Supported data and management planes for ISP stakeholder
	II	Supported data and management planes for DSP stakeholder
	III	Supported distribution of mitigation tasks between stakeholders (ISP and DSP)
5G System involved	IV	Traditional IP network traffic
	V	Multi-tenant Overlay Network (MON) with VXLAN/GRE/GENEVE (Cloud infrastructures)
	VI	5G/6G IoT device network traffic over a tenant
	VII	5G/6G IoT device mobility across gateways
	VIII	Geographical distribution of machines (Edge & Core)
Cognitive Loop capabilities	IX	Accurate detection of the attack
	X	Analysis of the detected threat
	XI	Decision generation for mitigation actions
	XII	Planning of the mitigation actions
	XIII	Orchestration of the plan to mitigate the threat
	XIV	Actuation and enforcing of mitigation rules
XV	Enforcement of the mitigation rules in the overlay networks datapath	
Others	XVI	Real environment (a), emulated (b), simulated (c)
	XVII	DDoS network protocol: UDP (u), TCP (t), HTTP (h), Signalling (s), N/A (-)
	XVIII	Centralised mitigation (cm), Distributed mitigation (dm), both (b), N/A (-)

Table 8.2 Analysis of the state of the art with respect to our contribution against the challenges required to achieve distributed dual-layer self-protection closed cognitive loop for IoT networks against DDoS attacks.

Reference	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XIV	XV	XVI	XVII	XVIII
Tzagkarakis et al [75]	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	-	c	-	-
Trajanovski and Zhang [76]	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	c	h	c
Salim et al [77]	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	c	-	c
Liu et al [78]	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	c	u	c
Hussain et al [79]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	-	c	s	-
Baig et al [80]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	-	a	t	-
Silva et al [81]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	c	s	c
Liu et al [82]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	c	h	c
Li et al [83]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	-	c	-	-
Candal Ventura et al [84]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	c	-	c
Paloalto [85]	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	a	s	c
Serrano et al [86]	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	b	u	b
Our work	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	b	u	b

In [75] a framework is presented that allows the detection of malicious network traffic at the IoT-Edge layer and thus identify possible infected IoT devices in a Botnet network. The analysis is carried out using Sparsity Representation and Reconstruction Error Threshold techniques, which allows it to recalibrate the decision point on which the traffic is being classified. The dataset used to train the ML models is the NB-IoT and only benign traffic data is used to calculate the threshold error. This framework however is not presented to act in across all layers of the 5G/6G architecture and its effectiveness for multi-stakeholder environments has not been studied either. In addition, the authors have not consider the classification of 5G/6G traffic, then resting credibility on the validation of the approach.

[76] and [77] present similar work in terms of the characteristics represented in this chapter. Both perform attack detection and subsequent analysis of the attack, in order to take action and mitigate the attack. [76] specifically presents IoT Botnet Detection and Analysis (IoT-BDA), a framework for detecting, analysing, identifying, and reporting botnets circulating on the Internet. The framework consists of two main blocks: Botnet Capturing Block (BCB), which is composed of a set of pre-prepared honeypots with vulnerabilities that can be exploited by botnets. The BCB will continuously report the activity that is occurring on its system to the next action block of the framework. Botnet Analysis Block (BAB), which consists of an API, parsers, sandbox, analysers and reporters. It executes or replicates the actions of the honeypots on the sandbox so that the analysers, using anti-malware programs

and techniques, can detect whether the traffic being generated comes from a botnet or not, as well as applying analyses to discover whether these botnets use anti-analysis techniques, anti-forensics, etc. Once a potential botnet has been identified, it is reported. On the other hand, [77] presents a framework which acts on the firmware of IoT devices. It tries to use DL techniques by using the LSTM algorithm in order to detect the attack that is happening through its network. To mitigate the attack, it analyses the infected device and disables it. The framework continues to listen and re-enables the devices to confirm whether or not they are still infected and, if so, disables them again. Although the above contributions are of great interest, they do not present a solution that can perform the mitigation of attacks in the overlay networks available in the 5G system.

[78] presents a two-level DDoS attack detection method based on information entropy and deep learning for SDN environments. The first level is based on the entropy detection mechanism detects suspicious components and ports in coarse granularity. The second one executes a fine grain packet-based detection by a CNN model to distinguish normal traffic from suspicious traffic. In the end, the controller is in charge of the mitigation of the attack by the interception of it. They use the open dataset CICIDS2017 to train their model and gather deep insights of the complete analysis they do for their work. The experimental results show that the two-level detection mechanism has high detection accuracy and efficiency. The above contributions are limited to traditional IP networks, without getting involved in the complexity of the overlay networks presents in 5G multi-tenant systems.

[79], [81], [82] and [83] present works that, in addition to obtaining an accurate detection of the attack for subsequent analysis, they perform their tests on simulated environments for 5G systems, allowing the execution of their work on the Network Operators' infrastructure. [79] presents a framework capable of detecting Silent Call Attack, Signalling Attack and SMS Flooding Attack DDoS attacks in the communications infrastructure for 4G LLDP-A architecture. This detection is carried out by a DL CNN, which analyses in a pre-processing of the traffic in the CORE of the network using ResNet-50 model to finally classify the type of traffic and discern from one attack or another. To train the DL model they use an open dataset from Telecom India. [81] presents REPEL, a new framework capable of

detecting signalling DDoS attacks for 5G environments but focusing on prevention by scaling virtualised network services. They do not explaining the architecture of their IDS and instead focus their arguments on the load balancing associated with prevention and action strategies in the 5G control plane, as well as proposing an attacker obfuscation system. [82] presents Umbrella, a defence mechanism against DDoS attacks which is deployed at the ISP, thus acting at the network level. They claim that, thanks to their multiple layers of work, they can stop different types of DDoS attacks at the network level, however, they depend directly on the continuous response of the victim, which must provide a list of trusted IPs that it has in its history. Finally, [83] propose an IDS based on ML techniques in 5G systems for Software Defined Networks. The architecture of this framework consists of three different abstraction layers, which are: forwarding, where network traffic is generated by OpenFlow-controlled entities (OFs); Management and Control layer, in charge of flow and packet collection as well as anomaly detection; data and intelligence layer, where ML algorithms are executed for the analysis and classification of traffic that has been detected as anomalous. On the other hand, [80] presents an interesting approach to a framework capable of the detection of DDoS threats in IoT networks. They analyse the performance of six different classifiers, A1DE, A2DE, Naïve Bayes, Bayesian Network, C4.5, and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). Finally they conclude that their ADE-based Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack detection scheme demonstrate a good performance for the different experiments that it has been tested with. The main difference with our contribution is observed in the scenario where the tests have been carried out, in addition to the complexity of the task once the attack has been detected. They have not used a test environment consistent with reality but have used simulations to be able to approximate a possible solution to a simulated problem.

In the article [84] a framework capable of detecting IoT devices susceptible of being infected for 4G and 5G networks is presented. The attack mitigation is performed by placing the traffic of these devices in quarantine on a Network Slice (NS) dedicated to this task, where it will then be analysed in depth to classify it as a malicious attack. This detection is carried out by an application running on top of the SDN controller, which will generate a distrust threshold as the number of flows in the quarantine NS varies. However, this contribution

lacks of mitigation capabilities in the DSP, being limited only to ISP, as opposed to ours contribution that focuses on the collaboration of all stakeholders involved in the infrastructure for the protection of its physical and virtual resources.

Paloalto Networks [85] offers Strata, a next-generation physical firewall that enables a security layer to be applied to 5G Network Operators to act against signalling attacks. It enables this network security to be applied across the 5G infrastructure, providing user mobility through the GTP encapsulation. It allows the network engineer to standardise different NS to be able to classify the traffic that is occurring along the infrastructure, in addition to being able to apply different control rules on the flows. Although it is one of the closest solutions to ours contribution, [85] does not present a clear solution for the entire 5G infrastructure, with only the Core infrastructure being protected and not Edge.

Serrano et al [86] have demonstrated successfully a close control-loop suitable for performing the self-protection of 5G networks. Our approach follows the same approach where we have significantly extend that work with new capabilities to perform parallel cognitive control loops involving different stakeholders.

It has not been possible to find in the literature any example of concurrent close control-loop for self-protection of infrastructure where both ISP and DSP loops are executed as a way to establish a collaboration between them. This lack of results in this critical area of security has motivated the writing up of this manuscript.

8.3 Towards a self-managed protection architecture for IoT networks

The system proposed in this work is explained in detail in the following sections. Firstly, an introduction to the 5G multi-tenant networks, which are an essential part of the proposed system to achieve the objectives mentioned in Section 8.1, is provided. Secondly, a more detailed explanation of each of the software components of the self-protection control loop proposed as a contribution to this work and the innovation they entail is explained, and these

are described in different subsections: Snort Monitoring Agent (SMA), Analyser, Decision Maker, Planner, Orchestrator and Flow Control Agent (FCA).

8.3.1 5G Multi-tenant network traffic

As explained in Section 8.1, there are several stakeholders involved in a 5G/6G system, all of them with different business models to satisfy their customers. This is why each of these stakeholders will have a different purpose in terms of acting on the data flow that is happening in their infrastructure (either physical or virtualised). This means that, along the entire route that a data flow must take, from its creation in the IoT device, to its destination, passing through the entire 5G/6G communications infrastructure, it will have variations in its morphology, despite its invariability in content. To achieve this, various encapsulation mechanisms are used to isolate traffic from each of the tenants that may be installed on the same infrastructure. VXLAN [87] is one of the examples, which is used to create the so-called multi-tenancy, isolating the traffic for each of the tenants which are occupying the infrastructure. This technology allows to create a first encapsulation of the data flow to achieve such isolation which will be used to identify the tenant. GTP is used as a second encapsulation, according to the standards of the 5G and expected in the forthcoming 6G mobile networks, allowing end-user mobility. This is described in detail in [88] in case the reader is interested.

Our proposed architecture is validated against 5G/6G network traffic in order to meet the associated requirements and challenges, such as the feasibility of multi-tenancy, self-adaptation to topology variations and mobility. To deploy this architecture, it has been followed an approach as described in this paper [89] where a Hybrid and Extensible architecture is run to achieve ISP and DSP deployment.

Figure 8.2 shows the architecture of the 5G-IoT network used in our research work. It shows the different domains where the network intervenes, starting with the IoT devices in the Device layer (see 1 in Figure 8.2). These IoT devices send the messages, in our case a raw DoS attacks, to the 5G RAN layer, where the antennas, together with the UEs, route the traffic (see 2 in Figure 8.2) to their respective Edge Computing infrastructures. The DUs

have been tasked with using the CPRI protocol to encapsulate the raw data from the devices so that it can be correctly routed by the ISP's physical devices. Once traffic arrives at the Edge Computing layer (see 3 in Figure 8.2), it is redirected to the DSP in concerned by the first virtual switch it encounters (represented by a purple rectangle). This DSP, boasting the functionality of a vCU plus MEC capabilities, is responsible for non-real-time, higher L2 and L3 (network layers) and stack functions (see 4 in Figure 8.2). When the packet leaves the DSP (represented by a yellow rectangle), it is already encapsulated in GTP and passes through a final virtual switch at the ISP to be encapsulated by the VXLAN protocol on its exit (see 5 in Figure 8.2). On leaving the ISP in the 5G Edge Network, the packet is routed directly to the central physical switch/router in the Transport Network (see 6 in Figure 8.2), where it will be routed to the appropriate ISP in the 5G Core Network. When the packet arrives at the ISP in the 5G Core Network, it comes with all the above encapsulations (see 7 in Figure 8.2), so the first step that the very first virtual switch it encounters is to undo the VXLAN encapsulation that the ISP in the 5G Edge Network has performed. Again, the packet is sent directly to the corresponding DSPs (see 8 in Figure 8.2), where thanks to the GTP encapsulation it is known which one it belongs to. The relevant tasks are performed in the DSP, the GTP encapsulation is undone and the packet is sent back to its destination, passing through the last virtual switch of the ISP where, if the packet is inspected, it can be seen that only the raw (IP) information sent by the UE in the first instance remains, with the information referring to its destination. Both in the infrastructure provided by the ISP and the DSPs, all traffic is being replicated by a switch that acts as a mirror to the service layer (see 9 in Figure 8.2) where the first component of the protection loop discussed in this chapter, the SMA, is installed so that, in case an alert is registered, it will communicate with the Management layer (see 10 and 11 in Figure 8.2) where the alert will be analysed and the appropriate steps described in the following Subsection 8.3.2 will be executed. Finally, the packet is sent to its destination through a switch that routes its traffic to the internet (see 12 in Figure 8.2) in order to reach its destination server. It is important to mention that VXLAN traffic simply does not exist from the point of view of the DSP as all its services will never see such protocol and thus the mitigation of traffic done by the DSP will be completely

different in terms of the packet structure from the one carried put by the ISP due to the different encapsulations available in each point of the infrastructure.

Fig. 8.2 Example of multi-tenant B5G network topology infrastructure with distributed Service and Management layers by stakeholder.

8.3.2 Self-protection Close Control-Loop Components

The self-protection close control-loop presented in this chapter is the composition of different software components that are architecturally chained to conform a close loop. Each of these components has a specific task and the combination of all of them results in the accurate detection of an attack, the analysis of its cause and the subsequent action against the threat. The communication between each of the components is done by a Message Bus software. This capability grants communication for the components through a publishing/subscription architecture. Here is where the concept of “Exchange” or “Topic” is used to describe where the information is published and where the components must subscribe to receive such information. The current implementation supports two different Message Bus technologies: Apache Kafka [90] and RabbitMQ [91]. For this work, it’s been considered to use only RabbitMQ as communication technology between the self-protection loop components.

As an introduction, the tasks and functionalities of each of the loop components are explained in the following subsections, giving an overview of the role of each of these components in the system, their responsibilities and their impact on the system in order to justify their participation in the loop.

Resource Inventory Agent (RIA)

The RIA is a component responsible for providing information about the topology of all network devices, ports and connections between ports and devices available on each machine. The information that RIA discovers in order to supply it to the rest of the components is: (i) Physical machine and its logical and virtual network interfaces, (ii) VMs and their virtual network interfaces, (iii) Containers and their network interfaces, (iv) Software switches, (v) Specialised physical devices such as Software Defined Radio (SDR) and their network interfaces, (vi) Interconnection between network interfaces, and (vii) Multi-tenant information of VMs. This component is also instantiated in all the machines of the infrastructure: Service and Compute layers of each Edge and Core segments and for each stakeholder. The capabilities and performance of this component are detailed in [92], and a specific use case for the topology information that the component discovers is specified in [93].

Security Flow Monitoring (SMA)

The SMA component has been developed with the main objective of enhancing and extending the capabilities provided by a traditional IDS. This is due to the fact that the capabilities of the traditional NIDS lack of 5G infrastructure and network information. In that case, this SMA has the responsibility of the fluent communication with the NIDS and the addition of relevant metrics and information of the 5G infrastructure regarding to the malicious flow that the NIDS has alerted. The traditional IDS that is being used for the purposes of this work is Snort[94]. The SMA is the combination of this Snort IDS together with a 5G multi-tenant traffic classifier created by us that allows the collection of relevant information about the 5G network tenants and allows the generation of concrete, granular and effective alerts. This fine-grain alerts allow to minimize the collateral damage of the attack as, they allow to stop only the malicious flows without affecting to the legitimate ones. The information provided by this component is separated in three categories differentiated by their purpose: first, metric information of the NIDS, such as the number of total packets of a specific technology that have been filtered or the percentage of the dropped packets; second, information about the malicious flow relative to the network information; and third, metadata information of the specific topology discovered by the RIA component that matches with the malicious flow structure. The capabilities and performance of this sensor are detailed in [95].

Analyser

The Analyser is the first component deployed in the management layer. Its purpose is to analyse the metrics that the previous component (SMA) has reported to the Metrics Exchange. This analysis is performed using the spatial and temporal information provided as metadata together with the metrics reported by the SMA. To have a better understanding of the purpose of this component, it is necessary to state that the NIDS with the SMA are reporting tons of flows produced by the DDoS attack. In that case, the system would only need to stop the specific flow that is causing the attack and not the repeated ones that might be being reported to the Analyser. Therefore, the Analyser executes its logic to retrieve the specific information of the malicious flows gathered by the SMA and specifies additional information such as:

alert type, alert impact, causes of the alert and if the flow is already stopped or not. This analysis is intended to be reported in the form of an Alert to the Alert Exchange when there is something detected from the reported metrics and metadata. Such Alert will be consumed by the next component of loop, the Decision Maker.

Decision Maker (DM)

The Decision Maker is the component responsible for generating a decision. It will indicate This decision is asserting what action should be taken and where. The actions can be diverse, such as performing a drop, redirecting traffic or mirroring the flow. On the other hand, the location on where should be enforced is determined following logic predefined by the programmer, such as “near the source”, “near destination”, “n hops from the source”, etc. These actions can be automated by the administrator through a policy engine in order to define different strategies for each type of attack. The decision is taken by the analysis of the alert triggered by the previous component in the loop, the Analyser. In the case of this work, the decision that is executed has as a DROP action in the closest place to the source of the attack that is happening through the network.

Planner

The Planner component is responsible for generating a plan. This plan is a the extension of the information provided by the Decision in order to achieve a set of implementable actions into the real system with the intention to complement any missing information not indicated in the decision with aspect such as: “default duration”, “default way to perform the action”, etc. These set of steps define precisely what action to take, where to take it, how to take it, how long to keep it active and when to take it, among others. Furthermore, this component is in charge of the computing of this “close to source” location where the attack must be stopped. This is made possible by the information that the RIA component is periodically reporting about the 5G network infrastructure and topological information. The Plan is published to the Plan Exchange.

Orchestrator

The Orchestrator component is in charge of executing the plan previously organised by the Planner. This is because the plan may contain a set of actions to be performed at different times and locations, as well as different points of action for the same attack that is happening throughout the network. The Orchestrator is the last component deployed in the management layer. Thus, additionally, the Orchestrator has the responsibility, which is to route the messages so that they can reach their previously indicated destination, i.e., each of the actuators deployed in the infrastructure are to receive the step of the plan that is being executed at that moment. Each step is published to the Intent Exchange and will be consumed by the FCAs that have been installed along the network infrastructure as explained in the next sub-section. Thus, different FCAs across the network will be responsible of enforcing different actions depending on the location they are instantiated in.

Flow Control Agent (FCA)

The FCA component is an agent whose main function is to expose network traffic control. Each of the computers that are present in the infrastructure have an FCA agent associated and installed which enables the control of the network traffic that exists between its physical and virtual machines. It differs from other agents such as SNMP and OpenFlow as it is an abstraction layer on top of different control technologies such as iptables, OpenFlow, SNMP, Traffic control (tc), etc., capable of exposing functionality to the management plane. The FCA component is able to provide distributed mitigation as it is multi-instantiated across the whole infrastructure and it will serve as an API with the protocol compatible with the different implementations in the data path. The capabilities and performance of this component are detailed in different manners in the following citations [96–98]. As described in the previous component (Orchestrator), the FCA will be instantiated in the different Compute layers across the 5G infrastructure. It will receive the organized information provided by the Orchestrator in order to enforce the actions in the dataplane. For the purpose of this work, the control technology that is being used in the experiments is tc.

8.4 Self-protection loop: integration of software components

To clarify the relevance of the intervention of each of the components in the self-protection system, it is necessary to study Figure 8.3, which represents the sequence diagram that the system follows to achieve the goal: to protect the infrastructure (physical and virtual) in an autonomous and distributed way. As can be seen in the diagram, the beginning of the loop takes place in the datapath of the infrastructure in the scenario to be monitored, where the Flow Monitoring Agent (FMA) and RIA are periodically monitoring their resources (network flow and compute, respectively) and are sending the information of the discovered network flows and components to the RabbitMQ exchange. This is crucial part of the Continuous Monitoring phase of the loop.

- **[01]** Get new B5G network flows: The system initiates by retrieving new network flows within the B5G infrastructure.
- **ACK:** New B5G network flows: An acknowledgment is sent confirming that new B5G network flows have been received.
- **[02]** Classify B5G network flow: The system classifies the incoming network flow to determine its characteristics.
- **[03]** Push new B5G network flow: The classified network flow is then pushed forward within the system for further processing.
- **[05]** Get new B5G network topology info: The system retrieves new information regarding the B5G network topology, which is essential for understanding the current state of the network.
- **ACK:** New topology node: An acknowledgment is sent confirming the receipt of new topology node information.
- **[07]** Push new B5G network topology node: The new topology node information is pushed within the system for further processing.

Fig. 8.3 Sequence Diagram for the self-managed protection loop.

- [08] Get new B5G network flow: The system continues to retrieve additional B5G network flows as part of the ongoing monitoring process.

Attack Detection Phase

- [09] If malicious flow detected: The system checks if any of the newly retrieved network flows are identified as malicious.
- [10] Build B5G flow (malicious alert) and nodes alert: If a malicious flow is detected, the system constructs an alert related to the malicious B5G flow and the affected network nodes.
- [11] Push new malicious flow detected: The system pushes the information about the detected malicious flow forward for further action.

Orchestration and Mitigation Phase

- [12] Pull new malicious flow detected: The system pulls the information about the newly detected malicious flow to start the mitigation process.
- [13] Provide attack analysis: The system provides an analysis of the attack, answering critical questions like “What is the cyberattack?”, “What are the affected network flows?”, and “How relevant is the cyberattack?” This analysis is crucial for determining the appropriate mitigation strategy.
- [14] Push new B5G Alert: The system pushes a new alert within the B5G infrastructure, signaling that a cyberattack is in progress.
- [15] Pull new B5G Alert: The system pulls the alert information for further decision-making.
- [16] Create a set of decisions: Based on the attack analysis, the system creates a set of decisions regarding the best response strategy. This includes choosing the best data path technology, determining the optimal location for mitigation, and deciding on the enforce mode.

- **[17] Push new Decision:** The system pushes the new decision to be implemented in the network.
- **[18] Pull new Decision:** The system retrieves the newly made decision for execution.
- **[19] Pull B5G malicious flow:** The system pulls detailed information about the detected malicious flow as part of the mitigation process.
- **[20] Pull B5G topology:** The system retrieves the B5G network topology, which is essential for implementing the chosen mitigation strategy.
- **[21] Prescriptive analytics:** The system uses prescriptive analytics to find the best location in the B5G topology to enforce the mitigation. It also creates a set of ordered steps necessary to enforce the mitigation effectively.
- **[22] Push new Plans:** The system pushes the new plans based on the prescriptive analytics for execution.
- **[23] Pull new set of Plans:** The system retrieves the newly created set of plans to enforce the mitigation.
- **[24] Intent: Enforce rule #1:** The system issues an intent to enforce the first rule as part of the mitigation process.
- **[25] Enforce rule #1:** The system enforces the first rule in the network to mitigate the threat.
- **ACK: Rule #1 enforced:** An acknowledgment is sent confirming that the first rule has been successfully enforced.
- **[27] Intent: Enforce rule #n:** The system issues an intent to enforce the nth rule as part of the ongoing mitigation process.
- **[28] Enforce rule #n:** The system enforces the nth rule in the network to mitigate the threat.

- **ACK:** Rule #n enforced: An acknowledgment is sent confirming that the nth rule has been successfully enforced.
- **[30]** All rules enforced: Finally, the system confirms that all the necessary rules have been enforced, completing the mitigation process.

Figure 8.4 depicts the different planes on which the protection loop operates, as well as a clear distinction between the stakeholders involved in the infrastructure. Notice how the scenario has multiple separated management planes, each per each of the DSP present in the architecture plus an additional one for the ISP. This allows to run parallel control loops where each of the loop is in charge of providing self-protecting capabilities to the portion of the infrastructure they are in charge of. The figure allows the reader to understand that the reaction of one of the management planes will have side effects in the behaviour of the other management planes due to the fact that the traffic transverses across all of them. Let's take this Figure 8.4 as an example to explain the flow that the self-protection loop is using in case of an attack. Assuming a potential attack that is passing through the network to the internet, it will be redirected (as well as the legitimate network traffic) to the mirror switches that are connected to the specific stakeholders' Service layers (see 1 in Figure 8.4. Here, the dataplane is being red by the first component, the SMA that is capable of the detection of this attack (see 2 in Figure 8.4. It is important to note that the encapsulations of each flow affect to the performance of the SMA; if there are more nested encapsulations (i.e. VXLAN over GTP over CPRI) the analysis of the information will be slower. Also, as the traffic is being mirrored to each of the stakeholder's Service layer with the only information that they can only gather (ISP will be able to get VXLAN encapsulations but not DSP). Here starts the collaboration without exchange of any information between stakeholder, because each of them are only working with information they can gather on their own. The information provided by the SMA will be published to its messagebus exchange and the following component (Analyser) will make use of it in the Management layer, where 4 of the rest of the components take place (see 3 in Figure 8.4). Once the Orchestrator finishes its task, the FCA in the specific Compute layer for the specific stakeholder will be in charge of

Fig. 8.4 Cognitive Self Protection Loop components relationships.

enforcing the action to be taken in order to protect the infrastructure (see 4 in Figure 8.4. In the case of a DSP, it will not be able to enforce a protection rule in the ISP infrastructure, nor the ISP in the DSP infrastructure. However, whether the attack is mitigated by any of the stakeholders, the goal of this contribution will be accomplished and the resources will be healed and protected, without interchange of any kind of acknowledge or information between the stakeholders and leaving the tightness of each network operator unspoiled.

8.5 Validation

To demonstrate the functionality of the system described in previous chapters of this work as a novel innovation, a testbed has been developed in which a 5G IoT network topology has been emulated and exposed to a series of DDoS attacks varying its volumetry. Two substantially opposite scenarios have been compared to test the effectiveness and benefits of the proposed system: the first scenario is based on the installation of the self-protection loop in a single stakeholder of the 5G IoT network, i.e. in the ISP; the second scenario is the contribution of this work itself, where the loop is installed in each of the management layers of the stakeholders involved in the network, creating a distributed dual-layer self-protection loop of the network.

8.5.1 Testbed and experiments design

All the software components described in section 3 have been designed, prototyped, deployed and validated in real 5G mobile edge computing infrastructures. They are all implemented in Java 17 with the only exception of FCA, which is implemented in Python 3. SMA uses Snort 3.0 underneath to perform the detection of attacks. RIA makes use of a collection of tools and mechanisms including OpenStack (Wallaby or higher), OpenAirInterface 5G (W44 2022 or higher), LLDP, CDP and iproute2 (v1.9 or higher) Linux stack to detect the topologies. We employ RabbitMQ 3.6 as Message Broker and MySQL 8.15 as DB. Analyzer, Decision Maker and Planner are based on a MySQL 8 engine as a way to allow the usage of SQL to express Analytical policies, Decision Making policies and Planning policies. The orchestrator is a Java implementation and FCA relies on OpenVSwitch 2.17.3 and iproute2 (v1.9 or higher) to enforce the mitigation actions.

To validate the effectiveness of the contribution of this work, CORE [59] has been employed as the emulation tool of network topologies, which makes use of Linux netns to emulate each of the different devices and networks on the infrastructure, being able to share the same file system and kernel, but generating their own private network and process environments. This, combined with the Linux Ethernet bridging tools provided by the

Linux environment itself, allows any type of network to be emulated, including the wireless ones needed to faithfully represent the infrastructure detailed in this chapter. The physical machine used in this work generated a VM, on which the experiments have been run, with a Linux operating system, in its Ubuntu 16.04 LTS distribution and kernel 4.4.0. The 10 cores of the Intel Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 v4 and 16 GB of RAM have been added to this VM, as discussed in Section 3.1.2. The CORE Emulator is a proven tool remarkably like Kubernetes, Docker Compose or OpenStack but it has the additional capability of allowing describing any topology in a graphical interface in a drag-and-drop fashion. Therefore, we have decided its usage in this experimentation. Notice that under any of such icons presented in Figure 8.5, there is a completely functional Ubuntu 16.04 Linux distribution.

CORE is one of the projects with the greatest vision in the field of academic research in networks and communications, and that is why it offers a wide range of tools and possibilities to develop each of the projects that are to be carried out with it. This facility has allowed the development of a system for the creation, configuration, provisioning, emulation and execution of different experimental scenarios. Figure 8.5 shows the CORE GUI, where a loaded scenario of one of the experiments launched in this work is shown. This experiment consists of 32 infected IoT devices, which are represented under the orange discontinuous box, the UE label, which in turn, are connected to their respective antennas (5G gNB) and these leave their Devices and Radio Access Network domain (see 1 in Figure 8.5) and route their traffic to the corresponding DSP in their EDGE Network (see 2 in Figure 8.5). As can be seen, there are several antennas connected to each EDGE Networks according to the spatial topology of the network, being represented within the green squares and indicated by an EDGE-1 and EDGE-2 label. In turn, traffic is routed to the Core network through the transport switch (see 3 in Figure 8.5), represented as a purple square containing the machines acting as ISPs and DSPs (see 4 in Figure 8.5). All traffic is mirrored to the service layer (see 5 in Figure 8.5), represented as an orange square, where the first reactive component of the loop presented in this work (SMA) is located and that, once detected the flow that is considered potentially dangerous, starts to execute the self-protection sequence that is performed in the Management layer in each of the stakeholders, represented as the blue

squares and annotated with MGMT-ISP, MGMT-DSP1 and MGMT-DSP2 labels (see 6 in Figure 8.5). As the last part of the created infrastructure, there are the servers outside the network domain that act as victims and where the attacks are targeted (see 7 in Figure 8.5). It is important to allow the reader to see how in both EDGE and CORE network segments the computers of the ISP are hosting different DSPs inside of virtual machines, creating a multi-tenant infrastructure.

The building of the scenario mentioned in the previous paragraph, consists of a sequence of steps in the creation of the environments executed by the CORE emulator so that the architectures and surroundings desired by the researcher can be emulated efficiently and the series of results can be collected. These steps are:

1. The CORE emulator loads the specified topology *IMUNES imn* file with information about name of nodes, links and connections between nodes, interfaces and network information such as IP and MAC addresses. These nodes represent all computers, IoT devices, virtual machines and physical infrastructure that take place in the scenario.
2. Each node in the scenario has a role, and each role needs specific configuration to be run. The IoT devices will have the role of attackers in the scenario, so at this step they will be provisioned with their specific information to launch the DDoS attack. This information is about the target ip they are focusing, type of attack, bandwidth consumed, Packets per second (pps), etc. For the rest of roles: ISPs and DSPs will have information to create mirroring and tunnelling protocols, Compute layers and Service layers will get information regarding to the software components that need to be installed, and so on with the remaining roles.
3. For each experiment, the scenario will have different number of IoT devices, Compute and Service layers to instantiate, even different Edges per Core segments. This is why some configurations must be dynamically done in the automation of these steps. All nodes are provided by a global configuration at the beginning of the experiment, however, this configuration is re-written for each node (i.e. the network IPs allocation

- for each attacker or the mirrored interfaces to the Service layers when the number of Edge segments vary).
4. Each role has specific goal to accomplish and different software to run, so another step is necessary to install all software dependencies for each node depending on the software they are running. The Service layers will be provided by the dependencies necessary to run the SMA and RIA, as well as the Management and Compute layers with the specific dependencies to run the rest of software components that have been described in Section 8.3.2.
 5. After all nodes have their network and software configurations, it's time to deploy the desired encapsulations in order to achieve tenant isolation and user mobility. First, the DSP isolation is granted applying VXLAN tunnelling at the ISP interfaces as shown in 5 Figure 8.2, similar to the OpenStack dataplane. The VXLAN encapsulation allows the ISP to redirect effectively the traffic that belongs whether a tenant or to another. The tool that is being used to create the VXLAN tunnelling in this work is Open vSwitch [99]. Second, the GTP encapsulation permits the user mobility and connects the IoT device to the destination server via TUN/TAP devices [100]. In this particular, the communication created is end-to-end and is the GTP server created with osmo-ggsn [101] software is responsible of the allocation of dynamic and ad-hoc IP for each device connected to it. This osmo-ggsn is compabilty with the dataplane of any 5G vendor such as Nokia, Ericsson and OpenAirInterface. Finally, it is selected which interfaces in the infrastructure are going to be mirrored to their respective Service layers. Whether the stakeholder is ISP or DSP, the mirrored interfaces will be done in ingress and egress mode to allow the detection of the direction of the malicious flow. With these 2 nested encapsulations and port mirroring the configuration step of the experiment finishes.
 6. Once the configuration of the scenario and the experiment is done, the software components are started in order per each node. The Service, Compute and Management

layers will run their software components and they will start listening to the traffic that is being mirrored. The scenario is ready to be tested and validated at this step.

7. Bonesi [102] is the tool installed in the IoT devices that creates botnet traffic with a chosen target IP. It can be modified to focus on different targets at the same time or to implement different types of DDoS attacks. For the purpose of this work, it will be launched a large UDP flooding attack from the IoT devices to the Servers. This UDP flooding attack works primarily by exploiting the steps that the server takes in order to answer UDP packets sent to one of its ports. As the server is receiving a huge amount of packets (deeper explanation is shown in Section 8.5.2) it will be overwhelmed and not able to respond to legitimate packets.
8. Finally, the experiment is completed and the results are gathered by the collector nodes installed in the Management layers of each DSP and ISP. The state of the machine is restored: cleans all temporary files of the experiment, deletes bridges that have been communicating the host machine to the emulation environment, all created sub-processes are stopped, etc.

When all the infrastructure to be emulated has been created, configured and provisioned with the necessary software, the emulation of the DDoS attack by the IoT devices is carried out. The number of devices in the network has been varied in powers of 2, with a minimum of 4 attackers and a maximum of 256, which perform a UDP port flooding DDoS attack whose victim is a server that has been installed on a machine outside the network domain to be emulated. This is why all the attackers have each of the points of the network to be studied as a route, and it will be the network itself that effectively detects the attack, analyses it and determines a decision to act, orchestrates a plan and executes the appropriate actions to mitigate the attack that is happening as soon as possible in order to protect both its physical and virtual infrastructures. At all times, a series of software collectors that have been installed in the administration layer. They are collecting everything that happens in each of the components of the loop. This is why, at the end of the DDoS attack and once it

has been correctly mitigated, these collectors finish gathering the necessary information to report it in this manuscript.

Fig. 8.5 32 IoT infected devices in a multi-stakeholder collaborative self protection system over CORE GUI.

Since the main contribution of this work is to demonstrate the viability and benefits obtained by installing a self-protection loop (such as the one developed for this work) in each of the stakeholders involved in the network, it has been considered convenient that its functionality be directly compared with an opposite system, in which the same self-protection loop is only installed in the stakeholder that owns the physical infrastructures of the network. This system will henceforth be referred as a standalone system, comparing it qualitatively with the distributed system offered as an innovation in this chapter. The distributed system is composed by 3 different cognitive control loops running simultaneously. One is running for the ISP and one is running for each of the two different DSPs deployed in the distributed system. It has been designed to deploy two DSP in order to really show the multi-tenancy aspect where multiple tenants (DSPs) are sharing the same physical (ISP). This qualitative comparison of the performance of each system has focused on three key functional aspects:

how effective the loop is in mitigating an attack, i.e., how many attackers the loop can stop out of all those that have been launched and whether it has managed to completely mitigate the attack; how long it takes to execute the self-protection loop, in order to know empirically how much overhead the self-protection system can withstand in the face of a massive DDoS attack; and as a third key point, studied along side the previous two, the responsiveness of the system when the number of attackers are being increased - with a minimum of 4 to a maximum of 256 in steps of powers of 2.

8.5.2 Functional results

The results shown here have been obtained by using the arithmetic mean on the indicator in question to be analysed. This is due to the fact that each experiment has been run 15 times and, while maintaining the same performance trend and times in each of the runs, there are slight changes in the results.

The first indicator to be studied is the average execution time of the self-protection loop. This is presented in Figure 8.6, where a two-bar graph is shown. The green-coloured bar represents the average loop execution time for the standalone system, together with its trend curve of the same colour. On the other hand, the blue bars represent the result for the distributed system, together with its trend curve of growth as the number of attackers increases. It can be seen how, for a small number of attackers, the standalone system seems to behave more efficiently in terms of execution times, this being represented by the green area which narrows until it intersects with the following blue area between 16 and 32 devices, a point where, although the average time value for the standalone system is slightly higher than the distributed one, it is shown that its growth trend is already much more accentuated than its counterpart. From this point on wards, it can be verified that the growth in execution times for the standalone system follows linearly the growth in the number of attackers. On the other hand, the distributed system presents a high load balancing between the different stakeholders of the system, so that its growth in line with the number of attackers is not as sharp as that of the standalone system. The use of the proposed system for a small group of attackers might not be worthwhile as a single security solution would be able to cope

Fig. 8.6 Average time consumed by the self protection loop, standalone system (green) against the distributed system (blue).

with the whole attack. However, it is also worth mentioning that there is a continuously growing large number of additional devices being connected to the network considering the trends such as Internet of Things and Bring Your Own Devices, and thus it makes sense to assume that the number of devices will be even higher in the future to justify the purpose and effectiveness of the proposed system. In addition, it is worth to mention that for the more severe attack, there is an improvement of 316% in the execution time of the distributed system with respect to the standalone own. Each of the attacks is sending 10000 pps of 160 MTU, totaling 2.56Mpps.

The second indicator is the ability of each of the systems to detect and stop attacks. This is represented in Figure 8.7 below, where, again, a series of bars represents the results for each of the systems. The number of attacks that the system should have stopped has been represented with yellow coloured areas so that the performance of each of the systems is more clearly reflected. In addition, the contribution of each of the stakeholders to the distributed system has been represented in different shades of blue. As in the previous Figure 8.6, the green bars represent the standalone system. It can be seen how, as in the previous figure,

Fig. 8.7 Average number of stopped attacks by the self protection loop, standalone system (green) against the distributed system (blue).

when going from 16 to 32 devices there is a saturation in the standalone system that causes its first significant increase in time and the beginning of the decrease in the number of attacks stopped. This decrease will continue for the remaining number of attackers, demonstrating a trend of system saturation that is solved. It is worth to mention that for 128 simultaneous attackers, the distributed system is able to stop 100% of the attackers while the standalone counterpart is only able to stop a 15% of them, clearly demonstrating the benefits of this collaboration.

Figure 8.8 shows the performance of each of the systems in a proportional way. The green line represents the results of the standalone system, while the blue line shows the values obtained for the distributed system. A blue area has been filled in to observe the drastic difference in performance offered by each of the systems, and to ensure that the load balancing provided by the distributed system to the network infrastructure can be beneficial for the stakeholders involved in it. It can be seen that for the highest number of attackers (256 attackers) the distributed system has barely dropped to 78.12% performance, while the standalone system is providing 4.75% performance. It is worth to mention that this reduction

Fig. 8.8 Performance by the self protection loop, standalone system (green) against the distributed system (blue).

of efficiency is also due to the fact that the whole experiment involving management, control and data plane is being executed in the same physical same machine and thus the components of the loops are also indirectly affected by the attack which is in our humble opinion a way to show as well the resilience of the architecture proposed.

There are two concrete scenarios that are worth studying more in deep. The first one is the last one that achieved the efficiency of 100% of attack mitigation on the distributed system (i.e. 128 attackers) and the second one is the one with highest number of attackers showing some saturation for both systems, i.e. (256 attackers).

Figures 8.9a and 8.9b, both representative of the results for a number of 128 attackers. Both graphs are plotted on the contribution of each of the stakeholders involved and, separated by a vertical dashed red line, both systems, the standalone (represented as ISP-ST) on the left of each graph against the distributed system on the right of each graph. In addition, it has been considered of special interest the representation of the times of each of the components involved in the loop, as follows: the blue coloured area represents the Analyser time; secondly, the red coloured areas represent the average Decision Maker time; the yellow

areas represent the average execution time of the Planner component; finally, the green areas represent the Mitigation time, which is the time consumed by the Orchestrator component and the addition of the rule by the FCA component to the point of the network suitable for stopping the attack that has just been analysed.

(a) Average execution time of the loop components (b) Average number of attacks stopped by each in the standalone system is represented as ISP-ST stakeholder. Standalone system is represented as (left) and ISP, DSP-1 and DSP-2 represent the ISP-ST (left) and ISP, DSP-1 and DSP-2 represent the distributed system (right).

Fig. 8.9 Experiment results for a number of 128 attackers as the average number of attacks stopped by each stakeholder and the average execution time of the loop components.

In Figure 8.9a, a first significant change is the average time consumed by the Planner component. In the standalone system it shows a slightly lower performance, due to the saturation of resources at that time - it is recalled that in Figure 8.7, the standalone system showed a rather steep trend as the number of attackers increased, and 128 has been a number where high saturation has been shown - while, on the other hand, the Planner component for the distributed system shows significantly lower times. This is due to the load balancing of the system resources, which allows the loop to act more smoothly and efficiently in stressful situations such as a DDoS attack. On the other hand, there is also a significant change in the Intention times. While they are somewhat lower for the standalone system, the distributed system shows a certain degree of saturation. It is undoubtedly the component that contributes the most delay to the system. However, the distributed system still maintains average times below the standalone system. Figure 8.9b shows the contribution of each of the stakeholders

to the number of stopped attacks. It shows how for 128 attackers, the standalone system barely manages to stop 25 attacks on average (19.78%), while the distributed system shows a load balancing that allows it to stop up to 128 (100%) attackers. It is very relevant to see how the vast majority of the cyber attacks are stopped by the DSP, thus leaving the percentage of resources consumed by the ISP at minimum (8%) even with 100% of the attackers have been stopped in the distributed system. This result clearly show how each system is benefiting of a mutual collaboration against the same cyberattack even without any information exchanged between them.

(a) Average execution time of the loop components in the standalone system is represented as ISP-ST stakeholder. Standalone system is represented as (left) and ISP, DSP-1 and DSP-2 represent the distributed system (right). (b) Average number of attacks stopped by each stakeholder in the standalone system (left) and ISP, DSP-1 and DSP-2 represent the distributed system (right).

Fig. 8.10 Experiment results for a number of 256 attackers as the average number of attacks stopped by each stakeholder and the average execution time of the loop components.

The same graphs have been plotted in Figures 8.10b and 8.10a for a number of 256 attackers. In the Figure 8.10a, the same trend can be seen: the standalone system is saturated, causing the execution times of the self-protection loop to be drastically increased, while, on the other hand, the distributed system shows a great load balancing between each of its stakeholders, achieving more reasonable execution times of the self-protection loop than its counterpart. The same is depicted in Figure 8.10b, which shows the number of attacks stopped by each of the systems, with the standalone system being really affected by the saturation of the network itself, as opposed to the load balancing offered by the distributed

system, which stops an average of 200 attackers. Notice how the distributed system has increased the percentage of efficiency from 4.75% to 72.18%, clearly demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed architecture.

8.6 Conclusions

Throughout this work the novelty of a distributed self-protection system between different stakeholders of a 5G/6G network has been studied, supporting both Edge and Core networks in order to detect, analyse and orchestrate the mitigation of a massive DDoS attack. This approach manages to provide protection and security to the stakeholders involved in the network, with the benefit of not exchanging information with each other, working distributedly yet autonomously at the same time. It has also been possible to test the effectiveness of the self-protection loop composed by a NIDS and followed by the subsequent components: SMA, Analyser, Decision Maker, Planner, Orchestrator and FCA, with which the detection, analysis and coordination of the mitigation for the protection of its network resources is conducted.

It has been observed that the same system is equally effective for different network topologies that may occur dynamically, and can be sufficiently intelligent and reactive to the change and addition of new infected IoT devices to maintain a good rate of detection and mitigation of attacks. The results of the experiments have shown that the main contribution of this chapter (which consists of spreading the work of the protection layers among the different stakeholders involved in the system as mentioned in Section 8.1), achieves a better performance both in execution time and the number of attacks mitigated compared with the traditional approach where the infrastructure provider has always been the only one concerned with protecting its networks and services, whereas, as has been demonstrated, other stakeholders are also interested in keeping their digital services available and secured. Based on industry surveys, network downtime reaches up to \$5,600 per minute of capital costs, which is over \$300K per hour [103]. In addition, 36% of companies experiencing more than five DDoS attacks suffer an average downtime of seven to 12 hours[104]. This

contribution has empirically demonstrated that the proposed solution is able to stop and recover the resources from a DDoS attack involving a large number of attackers with a low response time that is less than a minute. The contribution can thus directly reduce the average capital and operational costs from \$3M to less than \$1,900 per incident, as the highest response time for this contribution is 20 seconds, 1/3 of a minute.

The advantage of the simultaneous execution of the loops in different stakeholders is a naturally created multi-layer protection with enhanced distributed capabilities against cyber-attacks and this improves the usage of distributed resources in different stakeholders' domains for advanced protection purposes. Consequently, the performance of the whole protection capabilities is significantly strengthened.

Furthermore, the architecture of the self-protection loop developed in this work is completely modular and extensible. New functionalities can be added so as to optimise the levels of protection and security within the system to be protected, depending on the new use case to be studied. The number of rules and mitigation strategies to be followed can also be further expanded depending on the type of attack or threat.

In future work, firstly, it has been concluded that resource limits are considered a major bottleneck when it comes to replicating the scenarios and attacks carried out. This is why, as future work, the use of one of the functionalities of the CORE emulator that allows the creation of distributed environments on different machines is proposed, being able to completely isolate the management layers from the rest of the infrastructures, thus not being affected by the consumption of resources by the infected devices on the same machine. Another point of interest to be studied is the possible addition of a new component to the self-protection loop endowed with AI and capable of a more precise analysis of the attack that may be occurring on the network and that could replace the NIDS based on checking rules. In addition, it is planned to continue improving the performance for the distributed system in terms of the execution times of the loop and the number of stopped attacks for even larger DDoS attacks, with the ambition to be able to stop the 100% of the attacks launched in the ranges of 4096 to 16384 infected devices.

Chapter 9

Intelligent DDoS Protection Strategies for 5G-IoT and Beyond

Clarification

This chapter, along with all its contributions, is directly related to one of the outcomes of the PhD candidate under review entitled “Enhanced Protection of 5G-IoT and Beyond Infrastructures: Evolving Intelligent Strategies for DDoS Attack Multiclass Classification”.

9.1 Introduction

According to the last report of the European Telecommunications Network Operators’ Association (ETNO) [105], above 80% of the population in the multiple global peers under the study (Europe, South Korea, US, Japan and China) have 5G mobile network coverage. This growth has been noticed from years behind, as well for the trend of new connected IoT devices to those networks, stated in the same report as well. This creates multiple vulnerable vectors in the security field where intruders can take control of a bunch of devices and connect them to a botnet or swarm of infected devices to perform a coordinated attack. Cloudflare (security company owning over 95% of the market share for the network security sector [106]) studies their traffic volume for the solutions they have spread for multiple sectors

and domains in a tool called Cloudflare radar[107]. There, Cloudflare states that 36% of the attack volume is considered DDoS. Additionally, in the same report, 30% of the total traffic is considered from bots. Hence, it could be said that there's a high trend to recreate botnets to launch multiple DDoS attacks, and the security sector must be consistently evolving to prevent and mitigate such threats.

5G systems and infrastructures for mobile communications are continuously evolving. Two of the main features that 5G has to offer to users and stakeholders are user mobility and tenant isolation. User mobility is the capability for the UE to keep full connectivity when moving across multiple coverage cells within the same user authentication, typically using GTP protocol for encapsulation. Tenant isolation is the capability of the 5G infrastructure to keep the multiple tenants' traffic isolated from one to the other, thus coexisting various digital service providers over the same physical infrastructure, typically using VXLAN as the encapsulation protocol. Both features provoke the rise of new and complex networks, solutions, and threats. Considering that 89% of the vertical target domains of the threats recorded by Cloudflare are Internet and Telecom providers[107], it can be regarded as mandatory to investigate new techniques and solutions that can adapt to the 5G ecosystem and detect never-seen threats.

The main contribution of this research work is the study and analysis of multiple classification ML models over a newly produced data set of multiple DDoS attacks through the wired segments of 5G-IoT multi-tenant networks (i.e., Edge and Core). The following are the main innovations presented in this work:

- Novel first draft of a data set with realistic 5G-IoT multi-tenant traffic with multiple nested encapsulation headers.
- Up to 6 network traffic classes (3 benign traffic patterns and 3 attack traffic patterns) to be classified by the ML models.
- Aggregated features and metrics of the 5G-IoT network flows over the 5G interfaces being monitored, thus providing fine-grained metric information about the behaviour of the flows and the network.

- The selection of a highly resilient ML model (HGBC) for network flow classification in two topology scenarios achieving high F1 scores of 99.42% and 98.62%, respectively.

The rest of this document is organised as follows. Section 9.2 describes the current literature for ML and DL solutions and techniques for the classification of network threats. Section 9.3 introduces the proposed testbed and the experiments set up, additionally to the network topology scenarios used for the experiments in this work. Furthermore, the metric aggregation contribution is explained. Section 9.4 discusses the results achieved by the empirical evaluation of the generated dataset by the ML models. Finally, Section 9.5 outlines the conclusion of this work and the future research steps to extend this presented project.

9.2 Related work

In [108], the authors start by noting the prevalence of imbalanced datasets in public research. They use two network-based and five IoT network-based datasets to detect anomalies. They introduce a new method using CORE to balance data and improve detection. They then test this method with a Feed Forwarded Neural Network (FFN), showing promising results. However, they don't address 5G network considerations or other key features, as well as the perspective of topology technologies and other characteristic features of 5G systems.

[109] presents a new method for securing primary segments of the 5G network using hierarchical detection and Reinforcement Learning (RL). This method works with distributed attack detection systems to update defence strategies and spot both current and future threats. Results show it's effective in detecting new malicious behaviours with minimal computation. However, it's unclear if the authors focus solely on 5G infrastructure. They discuss the 5G architecture but don't specify the features used for accuracy in monitoring modules. So, it's hard to tell if they considered important 5G characteristics like user mobility and multi-tenancy features in their dataset as this work is presenting.

Authors in [110] introduce a distributed computing framework for anomaly detection in IoT applications by using three different datasets. While only one relates to IoT network traffic, the framework lacks consideration for 5G features or overlay networks. A central

mediator coordinates data processing tasks, employing LSTM neural networks for prediction-based online anomaly detection, aiming for high accuracy and low latency. Evaluation of the LSTM model shows high accuracy across the datasets. The work focuses on communication architecture rather than network malicious classification, treating anomaly detection as binary classification.

The work [111] proposes an IDS incorporating real-time monitoring, risk assessment, and dynamic decision-making using AI engines. The architecture is designed based on the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture and aims to provide information security in non-trusted networks. Even if they use multiple metric collectors along the different points of the 5G architecture, what is interesting to consider, they do not present any ML algorithm to detect or classify network anomalies. This absence gives the impression of a proof of concept rather than a fully developed solution.

In [112], authors present a novel approach by combining security layers and anomaly detection before an intelligence layer. They suggest using a RFC model for feature selection and K-Means plus AdaBoost for traffic classification. The selected ML algorithms show better accuracy and reduced false alarm rates in flow-based classification. However, the solution lacks integration with 5G infrastructure, focusing only on the solution's layer organization. Moreover, they rely solely on the open NSL-KDD dataset [113] for flow classification, overlooking multiple encapsulation flows.

[114] introduce a novel approach for detecting DOS and DDoS attacks in 5G scenarios. However, they utilize the NSL-KDD dataset, which has been generated in 2009 and lacks relevance to 5G systems. Their experiments, conducted with real data, utilize a Raspberry Pi-based testbed, diverging from a 5G infrastructure. Notably, there is no information provided regarding the technologies or features specific to 5G systems in their research.

The work [115] introduces a framework using deep CNN and real network data to detect DDoS attacks in 5G networks. While achieving high accuracy in identifying normal and under-attack cells, the study doesn't fully address the implications of 5G systems. Despite an innovative approach using Call Detail Record (CDR) data to model user behaviour and attack

patterns, the framework overlooks key characteristics of 5G systems and network topology information.

An anomaly detection task for 5G systems with the comparison of three different models: Decision Tree Classifier (DTC), SVMC and MLP, is presented in [116]. Each dataset has unique metrics, trained separately, with the labelling process explained. However, the authors don't specify the architecture of the test bed for assessing attacks or anomalies. This suggests they may have overlooked other 5G technologies like overlay networks, despite having metrics from the O-RAN infrastructure.

The authors in [117] introduce MEOADL-ADC, a method for detecting DDoS attacks in 5G networks using a combination of Modified Equilibrium Optimization Algorithm (MEOA) and DL techniques. They employ an LSTM model to classify attacks with high accuracy on the Kitsune Network dataset [118]. However, the work doesn't directly relate to 5G networks, and the classification performed is binary, not multi-class. They also compare their solution to other DL and ML models, demonstrating its superiority.

Despite the high trend in the research area to look into the anomaly detection and classification of network attacks, none of the discussed publications overcome the contributions presented in Section 9.1 in this work regarding specific multi-tenant 5G-IoT features and metric aggregation on network interfaces.

9.3 Design and methods

To acquire the network intrusion dataset along with the mentioned contributions, the authors enhanced prior work regarding topology instantiation and experiment execution, detailed in references [119–121]. The emulation tool used to deploy the scenarios is CORE [59]. It uses Linux netns to emulate each IoT device and network interface deployed in the infrastructure. Thanks to the distributed feature of the CORE network emulator, the topologies and experiments have been launched in a distributed infrastructure composed of 4 different physical machines with the following specifications: Ubuntu 20.04, Intel Xeon E5-2650 @2.8GHz CPU, and 64GB DDR3 RAM, as discussed in Section 3.1.2.

9.3.1 Testbed for data gathering

To collect and validate the novel security network dataset, two different multi-tenant 5G-IoT network topologies have been deployed (scenarios A and B listed in Table 9.1). Additionally, Fig. 9.1 depicts the 5G network topology for the testbed created to carry out the experiments for this work. These topologies are composed of 16 to 48 UEs connected to 2 gNB via radio access links (see 1 in Fig. 9.1). The DU are linked to 2 geographically-distributed Edge servers hosting 2 CU which belong to different DSP (see 2 in Fig. 9.1). The virtual switches instantiated in each physical machine route the network traffic to the specific tenant and perform the encapsulation/de-encapsulation of the network traffic via VXLAN protocol, thus enabling the multi-tenancy and multi-stakeholder capabilities (see 3 and 4 in Fig. 9.1). The servers composing the Edge segment are connected to a main Core server via a transport router (see 5 in Fig. 9.1), that provides the physical infrastructure to the associated UPF of the attached DSP (see 6 in Fig. 9.1). Finally, the traffic is sent to the inter-domain segments and leaves the premises' domain of the testbed, with a server as a target (see 7 in Fig. 9.1). Whereas the network traffic is routed through the 5G network, the multi-level encapsulated traffic is also mirrored to a Service and Sensing layer (see 8 in Fig. 9.1). In this step, the traffic is monitored and analysed by the multiple sensors and metric aggregator components to build the desired dataset (see 9 in Fig. 9.1). This last step is further explained in Fig. 9.3 as one of the main research innovations presented in this manuscript.

Table 9.1 Network topology for test bed in scenarios A and B.

Scenario	No UEs	No gNB	No DSP	No Edge	No Core
A	16	2	2	2	1
B	48	2	2	2	1

Fig. 9.1 5G network topology infrastructure emulated in the experiments and linked to Table 9.1.

The dataset obtained consists of both legitimate and malicious network traffic for UDP, TCP and ICMP protocols. For both kinds of traffic (legitimate and malicious), the network flow path is always the same: the UEs are connected to a final server through a 5G multi-tenant infrastructure, thus being this infrastructure under attack if the UEs target the final server. Fig. 9.2 shows an example of the encapsulated traffic pattern for a UDP packet in an attack scenario. This particular example shows how the UE payload is encapsulated by the GTP protocol to provide user mobility across the 5G infrastructure, additionally to the VXLAN encapsulation to isolate the tenant traffic over the physical infrastructure. Hence, the deployed testbed emulates realistic multi-level encapsulated 5G-IoT traffic to be mirrored to the service layer for monitoring and data set generation purposes which is one of the main contributions of this research work. The design of the cyberattack is as follows:

- The DDoS attack is launched with the Bonesi tool [102], and configured for each protocol.
- The MTU is set to 1500 Bytes.
- The Payload of the packets is modified and its length is set closely to the maximum MTU 1250 Bytes.
- The expected maximum length of the network packet header for every kind of attack (UDP, TCP and ICMP) varies from 132 to 250 Bytes.
- The emulated UEs consume a total combined bandwidth of 1Gbps during each attack. The transmission rate for each UE differs based on the total number of connected devices to the network, from 1875 to 5600 pps.

On the other hand, the legitimate traffic for each protocol is designed as follows:

- **UDP:** The UEs consume a video in stream mode that the Server is casting.
- **TCP:** The UEs download a video from a web service by the Server node consuming a total combined bandwidth of 1Gbps.

- **ICMP:** The UEs constantly send ping messages to the server consuming a total combined bandwidth of 1Gbps.

Notice that TCP and ICMP legitimate traffic experiments could be configured to consume the same bandwidth as the malicious traffic experiment (1Gbps). However, the UDP video stream could only be modified by the number of UEs connected at the same moment of the transmission, thus the network consumption is directly related to the packet size, video resolution and video frame rate. With the completion of this part, this project achieved the creation of 6 different classes to be classified by the ML developed models (UDP, TCP, ICMP for both legitimate and harmful traffic).

Fig. 9.2 Packet structure example of the nested encapsulation network traffics for multi-tenant 5G networks.

9.3.2 Dataset configuration

To gather the data from the 5G network topology, the traffic passing through the Core segment of the network is mirrored to the Service and Management layer. In this layer, there are three main sensors allocated to gathering real-time metrics. The three sensors are configured to report metrics every second only if there are any changes in the metric:

- **Flow collector:** This sensor is a network packet inspector for 5G network topologies. It extracts metadata information about the flow and provides multiple real-time network flow metrics to the dataset.
- **Interface Collector:** it is a network interface inspector for 5G network topologies. It extracts metadata information about the interface and underlying technologies associated with it. Moreover, provides real-time interface and port metrics to the dataset.
- **Snort Collector:** this traditional IDS is configured with zero detection rules, thus no alerts are raised. However, it is configured in Packet Performance Monitoring (PPM) mode, which provides real-time security metrics of the interface that Snort is attached to.

Fig. 9.3 depicts the workflow of the three sensors, plus the addition of the aggregation metrics functionality to the system. The flow starts with the collection of the network flow metrics (see 1 in Fig. 9.3). For each network flow passing through an interface, the Flow Collector retrieves the available metrics. Concurrently, the Interface and Snort Collectors are also retrieving the metrics of the network interfaces they are attached to (see 2 in Fig. 9.3). Later, all the metrics are sent to the Metric Aggregator (see 3 in Fig. 9.3), where they are ordered on a timestamp basis (see 4 in Fig. 9.3). This aggregation is translated into a CSV format file, in which every row defines the metrics over the time of a flow and the interface it is attached to, thus providing multi-domain network metrics (flow and interface) to the data set. A subset of the metrics and features selected for each of the sensors are:

- **Flow collector:** Number of bits per a specific interval, number of packets per a specific interval, number of octets in the headers, inter-packet latency, etc.

Fig. 9.3 Workflow of the metric aggregation between the three sensors (Flow collector, Interface collector and Snort collector).

- **Interface Collector:** Total bandwidth consumed for ingress and egress network traffic, pps, current consumed bandwidth, etc.
- **Snort Collector:** Number of TCP and/or UDP sessions created, Packet stats and drops, Stream timeouts, etc.

Datamodel

The cited collectors store various metrics in a relational SQL database with three entities or tables. These entities and their relationships are shown in Figure 9.4. As illustrated, each entity has a primary key, a unique identifier called “resource_id.” The “resource_type” field indicates the type of entity, such as “flow,” “interface,” or “metric.”

It is important to note that there are no separate tables for each collector. Instead, all collectors log their metrics for the same entity (Metric), with foreign keys linking each metric to the specific entities (flow or interface) it relates to. Thus, each row in the SQL database for

the Metric entity represents a single metric record associated with a specific related entity. To align timestamps across these records, a component called the Metric Aggregator is used, as shown in Figure 9.3.

While the core of the dataset comprises recorded metrics, these are associated with specific network flows passing through particular network interfaces. This information is essential for building the dataset, as it provides context on where a malicious flow is detected. Figure 9.4 shows the metadata captured for each entity. For the Flow entity, metadata includes multiple encapsulation layers, specified as “inner” and “outer” prefixes for details such as source and destination IPs, ports, protocols, encapsulation IDs, etc. This approach contributes to the literature by providing the first B5G network dataset for cybersecurity with multi-tenancy and multi-encapsulation support. One flow entity may have none or multiple associated metrics.

Similarly, the Interface entity records metadata specific to each network interface, such as the interface name (e.g., eth0, ens0s3), associated IP, mask, MAC addresses, MTU, configured speed, and state (up or down). These interfaces are monitored by the Snort and Interface Collectors, and their metrics are linked between the Interface and Metric entities. Like the Flow entity, the Interface entity can have none or multiple associated metrics.

Fig. 9.4 Relationship datamodel of the three entities, Flow, Interface and Metric stored in the SQL database.

Every time an experiment is launched, whether it is an attack or legitimate traffic, all metrics are stored in a MySQL DB. Here, the metrics are stored on a timestamp basis of

Table 9.2 The subset of metrics recorded by the three sensors (Flow, Interface and Snort collector).

Sensor	Metric Name	Unit
Flow Collector	Bits per Interval	bits
	Packets per Interval	packets
	Sum Inter-Packets per Interval	ns
	Header Octets	octets
	Sum Inter-Packet lag	ns
	Last packet received	ms
	Total bits	bits
	Total packets	packets
Interface Collector	TX Bytes per second	Bps
	TX BW Consummed	bps
	TX Packets per second	pps
	RX Bytes per second	Bps
	RX BW Consummed	bps
	Current BW Consummed	bps
Snort Collector	Kpackets per second	kpps
	New UDP sessions	sessions
	Packets stats and drops	packets
	Stream timeouts	timeouts
	TCP sessions timeout	sessions
	Total UDP sessions	sessions
	Mbit per second	Mbps

one second, but the records don't usually match with each other. This is because each sensor reports every second only if changes have been seen. I.e., if a metric has not changed in the last 10 seconds, only 2 records are stored in the DB (at moment 0 and 11, when changes are noticed). This makes the dataset collection challenging, should the metrics be aligned in an ordered time-space where every metric has a value at every moment. That very challenge has been solved in this work, wherein a time frame of one second all the metrics are aligned for every topology and experiment into a single dataset. This step also applies some data-cleaning techniques to remove duplicates and invariable features. Those duplicates and non-changing features may apply noise to the ML performance. To avoid over-fitted ML models, it has been applied a last correlation feature technique to get the

similarities of the distribution of each feature. A list of a pair of features is returned, and the system drops one of the features if it is highly (directly or indirectly) correlated to its pair.

An imbalance problem has been found in the dataset related to the classes of UDP and TCP legitimate traffic. To tackle this issue, an under-sampling technique has been applied. This technique consisted of training a non-supervised K-Means ML model, thus applying clustering over the 6 different classes. By doing so, it has been possible to understand the behaviour of each of the classes composing the dataset. Later, the majority classes have been under-sampled to the minority class, leaving each class with a maximum of three thousand samples. Finally, the dataset has been randomly shuffled and split into two main stages, 70% for the training step (2100 samples) and 30% for the test step (900 samples), and saved into a CSV file.

Advantages and limitations of the dataset

The created dataset addresses several gaps identified in the literature concerning cybersecurity ML datasets. It combines two critical domains frequently considered by security engineers when mitigating threats: network flow and network topology, providing the system with topology-awareness and B5G capabilities as detailed in Chapter 7. Consequently, the dataset offers a comprehensive view of network flows traversing a specific network interface, with labeled flows to identify which network flows constitute attacks.

However, one limitation of the dataset is the challenge of achieving variability across experiments. This is a recognized drawback of most synthetic cybersecurity datasets, as generating sufficient variability to accurately reflect real-world conditions is complex and time-intensive.

The resulting cleaned dataset is a combination of every topology and scenario (A and B, specified in Section 9.3.1), thus providing one of the main contributions of this work to be considered by the ML developed models.

9.3.3 ML training loop

This section covers the process carried out to train and evaluate the ML models. First, it is worth noting that four different ML models are under evaluation for this dataset. The models are: RFC [29], ETC [30], SVMC [31] and HGBC [32].

To effectively validate the dataset and the ML models, a training loop has been created. This loop consists of a set of functions and steps that are replicated over the four different ML models in the same way. As a sequence, it can be summarised as follows:

- The train and test datasets are loaded to their respective variables. The splitting of the labels for classification purposes is done as well in this step.
- The model is cross-validated with the k-fold technique, which splits the dataset into a set of train and validation sets to ensure that the model is not suffering from over-fitting. With this technique, the dataset is trained with a subset of the first split training set and looks for a new set of hyper-parameters. Then, the resulting training dataset is slightly smaller than the previous training dataset. This resulting training set divided for the k-fold technique which approaches more to the average value of the F1-score metric is saved.
- This new training set is finally fed to the ML model to be trained with the saved hyper-parameters.
- The trained model is evaluated using the test dataset considering the following classification score metrics: accuracy, recall, precision, F1-score and inference time.

To select which of the presented models achieves better performance, the F1-Score metric has been prioritised among the others, though the rest have been considered as well. Accuracy is a relevant metric. However, it measures how many samples have been correctly classified by the model, both positive and negative (6 classes to consider in this research work). The accuracy is calculated as shown in Equation 9.1. However, accuracy is not the preferred metric to determine the highest performance for possible imbalanced datasets. On the other hand, the F1-Score metric calculates the harmonic mean between precision and

Table 9.3 Hyperparameter configuration for each topology scenario (A and B) and each ML model.

Model	Hyper parameter	A	B
RFC	bootstrap	false	false
	criterion	entropy	entropy
	max_depth	15	null
	min_samples_leaf	1	1
	min_samples_split	5	2
	n_estimators	100	200
SVMC	C	94.5	94.5
	gamma	scale	scale
ETC	criterion	gini	entropy
	max_depth	15	null
	min_samples_leaf	1	1
	min_samples_split	2	2
HGBC	learning_rate	0.1	0.1
	max_leaf_nodes	3	10

recall (specified in Equation 9.2), thus the difference between both metrics (accuracy and F1-score) acts as an alert of a possible imbalance between the selected classes.

$$Accuracy = \frac{T_p + T_n}{T_p + T_n + F_p + F_n} \quad (9.1)$$

$$F1 = \frac{2 * T_p}{T_p + 0.5(F_p + F_n)} \quad (9.2)$$

The confusion matrix and the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve are essential tools for evaluating model performance. The confusion matrix provides a visual representation of the classification outcomes, displaying the number of true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative predictions. This allows for a quick assessment of model accuracy by highlighting instances of correct and incorrect predictions for each label. In this study, the confusion matrices reveal how model accuracy is impacted by increasing the number of connected UEs.

The ROC curve, on the other hand, illustrates the model's ability to distinguish between classes across different threshold values. The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) is often used as a summary metric to quantify the model's performance, with values closer to 1 indicating better classification. The ROC curves in this section provide insights into each model's stability and sensitivity, especially under different topological configurations. Together, the confusion matrix and ROC curve provide a comprehensive view of model performance, allowing for detailed comparisons between the ML models tested in this work.

9.4 Results discussion

This section presents an analysis of the results obtained from executing the ML models specified in Section 9.3 (RFC, ETC, SVMC, HGBC) and their evaluation. Both topological scenarios (A and B, as described in Section 9.3.1) were tested with these models. Figures 9.5, 9.6, 9.7, and 9.8 summarize the performance and key findings of each ML model (RFC, ETC, SVMC, and HGBC, respectively). Each of these figures contains four subfigures, showing the confusion matrix and AUC for each testbed configuration (for 16 and 48 connected UEs).

In a confusion matrix, the Y-axis (rows) represents the actual or true classes of the data points, while the X-axis (columns) shows the predicted classes. Each cell in the matrix displays the count of instances where the actual and predicted classes intersect, offering insight into the model's performance, including true positives, false positives, false negatives, and true negatives.

For an ROC curve, the Y-axis represents the True Positive Rate (sensitivity), while the X-axis represents the False Positive Rate. This plot demonstrates the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity, showing the model's ability to distinguish between classes. The AUC indicates the overall performance.

Figures 9.5 and 9.6 reveal a degradation in model performance, specifically in terms of accuracy, in both the confusion matrices and AUC. The predicted labels on the Y-axis show lower accuracy for the configuration with 48 connected UEs compared to the configuration with 16 connected UEs.

Additionally, the SVMC model, as shown in Figure 9.7, performs the worst among the evaluated models. Its confusion matrices display significant degradation in label prediction accuracy for both scenarios, with an even more pronounced decline at 48 UEs. Similarly, the AUC appear unstable for each label, indicating inconsistencies in the model’s performance.

Finally, Figure 9.8 represents the results of the HGBC model, which outperforms the other evaluated models. Only a slight degradation in label prediction accuracy is observed in the confusion matrices when increasing from 16 to 48 connected UEs. Moreover, the AUC remain stable across both scenarios, indicating robust performance.

(a) Confusion Matrix of the RFC for 16 connected UEs. (b) Confusion Matrix of the RFC for 48 connected UEs.

(c) ROC of the RFC for 16 connected UEs. (d) ROC of the RFC for 48 connected UEs.

Fig. 9.5 Confusion Matrix and ROC of the Random Forest Classifiers for both validation scenarios.

(a) Confusion Matrix of the ETC for 16 connected UEs.

(b) Confusion Matrix of the ETC for 48 connected UEs.

(c) ROC of the ETC for 16 connected UEs.

(d) ROC of the ETC for 48 connected UEs.

Fig. 9.6 Confusion Matrix and ROC of the Extremely Randomized Trees Classifiers for both validation scenarios.

(a) Confusion Matrix of the SVMC for 16 con-

(b) Confusion Matrix of the SVMC for 48 con-

(c) ROC of the SVMC for 16 connected UEs.

(d) ROC of the SVMC for 48 connected UEs.

Fig. 9.7 Confusion Matrix and ROC of the Support Vector Machine Classifiers for both validation scenarios.

(a) Confusion Matrix of the HGBC for 16 connected UEs.

(b) Confusion Matrix of the HGBC for 48 connected UEs.

(c) ROC of the HGBC for 16 connected UEs.

(d) ROC of the HGBC for 48 connected UEs.

Fig. 9.8 Confusion Matrix and ROC of the Histogram-based Gradient Boosting Classifiers for both validation scenarios.

Figures 9.9 and 9.10 depict a summary of the metric scores achieved by each model. On the Y axis, the ML models are specified, while the X axis represents the metric scores. The colour determines the effectiveness of the metric. The first 6 metrics represent a better behaviour or result when the colour is darker. On the other hand, the inference time is expected to be as little as possible, hence the colour will be lighter. It's worth noting that the values of the results have been scaled from 0 to 1, except for the resulting inference time which is represented in seconds. This analysis aims to look for a balanced model with high accuracy, F1-Score and low inference time.

Fig. 9.9 shows the results achieved for the scenario A. It can be seen that the RFC, ETC and HGBC models outperform compared to the SVMC. This is because of how the tree-based models and boosting models do their classification compared with the SVMC one. SVMC expects a wider difference between the analysed samples to perform better, though the provided topology is not suitable for that task in this specific scenario. The variability of the metrics along the entire experiment seems to be closely related but spread enough to be classified accurately by the ML models. As it can be seen in Fig. 9.9, the F1-Score and accuracy for three of the models surpass the 99.42%, whereas the SVMC model reaches a maximum F1-score of 61.09%.

On the other hand, Fig. 9.10, representing the results of scenario B, shows slightly lower performance than the results achieved for scenario A. The behaviour of the models remains the same: SVMC achieves a much lower accuracy and results than the tree-based and boosting classifiers. However, it is worth noting that the performance of the tree-based classifiers (RFC and ETC) had a more significant fall than the HGBC. The tree-based models could achieve up to 86.37% for their F1-Score metric (a fall in the performance of 13.22%), whilst the HGBC could keep a steady performance of 98.62% (a fall in the performance of a 0.8%).

The main differences between both scenarios results show that the increase in the number of 5G network flows to be analysed and aggregated to the corresponding interface metrics leads to an increase in the complexity of the classification tasks of the ML models among the 6 different classes specified in this research work (UDP, TCP and ICMP for both legitimate

Fig. 9.9 Model results for topology scenario A.

and malicious traffic). Additionally, results demonstrate the high efficiency and resilience of the HGBC model for both scenarios compared to the tree-based and SVMC models. Hence being the preferred method to solve the particular problem of this kind of network flow classification considering the interface's behaviour. Therefore, the results obtained in this work demonstrate the feasibility of this new intrusion detection paradigm in the field of network security with the aggregation of the network flow metrics and the corresponding interface metrics in multi-tenant 5G-IoT networks.

Fig. 9.10 Model results for topology scenario B.

9.5 Conclusions

The research work introduces a novel dataset featuring 5G-IoT multi-tenant and multi-encapsulated traffic, comprising six network traffic classes for ML model classification. It incorporates aggregated features and metrics of the 5G-IoT network flows over the monitored network interfaces, offering detailed insights into flow and network behaviour. Furthermore, it highlights the selection of the HGBC, known for its high resilience, to classify network flows across different topology scenarios.

The results demonstrate metric aggregation's importance in achieving fine-grained metrics that will feed an AI model for classifying 5G network threats. This study has analysed the performance in terms of accuracy and F1 score of four ML models with the designed and gathered dataset: RFC, ETC, SVMC, and HGBC. Among the ML models evaluated, the HGBC outperforms the experiments presented in this work, achieving accuracy and F1-scores above 98.62% for both scenarios.

As future guidelines, the authors will explore new ML models like XGBoost Classifier (XGBC), that might fit properly with the scope of the problem to be solved. Moreover, the research of a DL model, like an LSTM, might be beneficial to future research lines. It is worth mentioning that the authors will work on expanding the dataset, providing new features and more complex scenarios to achieve higher variability and resilience to continuously changing scenarios inherent to multi-tenant 5G IoT networks.

Chapter 10

Critical Analysis

This research work has been successfully accomplished the research questions and objectives depicted in Chapter 2. The core of this PhD thesis relies on 4 development fundamental chapters (6,7,8, and 9) that demonstrate with empirical results the research objectives and KPIs planned for the thesis. Additionally, this work has been taken under the umbrella of two European projects where the candidate has actively participated in the development of software components and the integration tasks, demos, as well as participating in the consortium meetings, review meetings and writings of the proposed deliverables by the projects. Moreover, the practical work presented and evaluated in this thesis has also been validated through multiple peer-reviewed publication where the candidate has been the main author or co-author. This made possible to integrate and test the proposed solutions in realistic use cases and scenarios along the European projects and peer-reviewed papers.

How the objectives and KPIs have been addressed is briefly explained in the following sections, where the narrative will tackle each KPI one by one.

Objective 1: To create a framework for automated B5G-IoT network deployment, experiment execution, results collection, and AI models' training.

The combination of all of the development chapters in this thesis demonstrate the achievement of this first objective, where an automated framework for emulating distributed or standalone B5G network topologies has been achieved and presented in Chapter 6. Moreover, the addition of result collection, dataset creation and AI models' training loop has also been presented in Chapter 9. Additionally, the rest of development chapters make use of the automation tool to validate its feasibility.

Objective 2: To investigate and perform a deep analysis of the B5G-IoT networks' characteristics and innovative technologies.

Chapter 4 provides the fundamental insights and analysis of multiple key features and characteristics of the technologies and techniques used to perform this PhD thesis. These are:

- Deep analysis between what differs from simulation and emulation systems.
- What emulation tools are available right now and what are the main features they offer.
- Deep analysis on the fundamental features of the B5G networks regarding its infrastructure and possible advancements for the 6G.
- A thorough study on closed control loop systems for cybersecurity countermeasures against cyberattacks.

Moreover, **KPI-1** has been achieved with 2 published peer-reviewed research papers [44] and [60], where the candidate is the main author of them. In addition to other 2 publications where the candidate has actively participated with his work presented in this thesis as co-author of the papers.

Objective 3: To identify the research gaps in the cybersecurity field of the AI-enabled B5G-IoT networks.

Chapter 5 provides a deep analysis on the related work of this PhD thesis, compiling different approaches such as B5G Network emulation and automation, as well as AI-Enabled solutions for cybersecurity in mobile networks. Additionally, each of the development chapters have a specific related work section that tackles the particular use cases presented in each of those chapters, thus enabling the reader with an extended understanding of the underlying concepts and existing work of the techniques and technologies used in this work.

Objective 4: To design and implement an emulated B5G-IoT network infrastructure.

This research objective points directly to the practical results achieved and presented in Chapter 6. There, it has been demonstrated how an automated emulation tool is capable of provisioning and deploying multiple B5G-IoT topologies with fundamental features and technologies whether or not it is deployed in a single machine or distributed along multiple physical machines.

Final KPIs

- **KPI-2:** Time required to provision and deploy the emulated B5G-IoT network topologies in a non-distributed testbed ≤ 5 minutes.
- **Achieved: 3,93 minutes for the worst case scenario 6.2.**
- **KPI-3:** Number of distributed physical machines where the emulated B5G-IoT network topology is provisioned ≥ 4 .
- **Achieved: 4 physical machines.**
- **KPI-4:** Provision and deploying time required for the emulated B5G-IoT network over distributed physical machines ≤ 20 minutes.

- **Achieved: 10,83 minutes for the worst case scenario 6.3.**

Objective 5: To develop an experiment-based cyber incident testbed over a B5G-IoT network.

This research objective is validated by Chapters 7, 8 and 9. There, it has been demonstrated the effectiveness of an automated and cognitive self-protection closed loop for detect, plan and mitigate DDoS attacks in B5G networks.

Final KPIs

- **KPI-5:** Number of different exploited protocols for DDoS cyberattack models ≥ 3 (ICMP, TCP, UDP).
- **Achieved: 3 network protocols 9.3.1.**
- **KPI-6:** Number of different emulated infected devices that the system can record their behaviour over the attacked B5G-IoT network infrastructure ≥ 128 devices.
- **Achieved: stable 64 UEs in 6 and 128 UEs in 8.**

Objective 6: To create an AI-enabled 5G network dataset with multiple DDoS cyberattacks.

In Chapter 9 it has been shown how the B5G network dataset has been created to perform the classification of multiple exploited DDoS attacks (ICMP, TCP, UDP) and the respective legitimate traffic with regard the same network protocols. Moreover, **KPI-8** refers to the total number of metrics that are being recorded in the network prior to the dataset configuration, and they are more than 90 when merging both domains and the three sensors (snort collector, flow collector and interface collector). On the other hand, **KPI-9** refers to the selected features in the dataset.

KPIs

- **KPI-7:** Diversity of network classes for the dataset, mixing legitimate and malicious traffic ≥ 5 .
- **Achieved: 6 network classes, 3 attack and 3 legitimate 9.3.1.**
- **KPI-8:** Number of monitored features and network metrics related to the B5G-IoT network flows and interfaces ≥ 80 .
- **Achieved: > 90 features 9.3.2.**
- **KPI-9:** Number of selected B5G-IoT dataset features for the later ML analysis ≥ 20 .
- **Achieved: = 21 features 9.3.2.**

Objective 7: To explore and enhance AI models for cyberattacks' detection and classification in B5G-IoT networks.

Finally, this research objective is fully validated in Chapter 9, where the B5G dataset has been validated and evaluated against multiple ML models. Their performance have been evaluated with help of multiple performance indicators such as the F1-score, accuracy or inference time. Moreover, the results shown in that chapter provide promising insights about the future action roadmap to tackle in this research area.

Final KPIs

- **KPI-10:** Number of supported ML models to validate the B5G-IoT dataset ≥ 4 .
- **Achieved: = 4 ML models SVMC, RFC, ETC and HGBC in 9.4.**
- **KPI-11:** Number of performance indicators and evaluation metrics for each ML model ≥ 5 .
- **Achieved: = 5 evaluation metrics in 9.4.**

- **KPI-12:** Accuracy of the ML models in detecting and classifying DDoS cyberattacks in B5G-IoT networks $\geq 95\%$.
- **Achieved: = 98.62% of accuracy in 9.4.**

Chapter 11

Limitations

The field of telecommunications and cybersecurity is continuously evolving, making it challenging for researchers to stay updated of the latest advancements and emerging technologies. This rapid pace of development introduces complexities in research, particularly when working on the cutting edge of technologies such as 6G networks. While there is currently no universally accepted definition of 6G, numerous European projects and funding initiatives are actively pursuing the development and formalization of this next-generation network. These efforts underscore the dynamic nature of the field and the inherent difficulties in conducting research that remains relevant and forward-looking in such a fast-paced environment. In this context, it is crucial to acknowledge the limitations encountered during this research journey, as they provide valuable insights into the challenges faced and help guide future work in this ever-evolving landscape.

11.1 General limitations

In the realm of cybersecurity research, particularly within the detection phase of cyber incidents, the field is highly competitive. This phase, being the first and arguably the most crucial step in the security loop, has attracted significant attention from researchers. Consequently, much of the existing research focuses on developing and refining detection strategies. However, this does not imply that the area is saturated or that enough research has

been done—on the contrary, the detection of cyber threats remains an evolving and critical topic with numerous avenues for further exploration. The continuous emergence of new threats and the development of more sophisticated attack vectors ensure that the detection phase will remain a hot topic for years to come.

Despite the intense research activity, one of the major limitations faced in this field is the scarcity of open data related to B5G network flows and systems under cyberattacks. Telecommunications companies, understandably, are often reluctant to share their data due to the need to protect client privacy and maintain security integrity. This reluctance creates a significant barrier for researchers who rely on access to real-world data to develop and validate their detection methods. The lack of open data forces researchers to either work with limited datasets or attempt to replicate B5G network flows and systems, which introduces another set of challenges.

When attempting to replicate B5G network flows and systems for research purposes, the variability in network patterns and the range of cyberattacks that can be emulated is inherently limited. This limitation constrains the breadth and depth of experiments that can be conducted, potentially affecting the generalizability of the research findings. While creating synthetic datasets and emulated environments can provide valuable insights, they may not fully capture the complexity and unpredictability of real-world scenarios. Consequently, there is a continuous need to innovate and develop more realistic emulation techniques that can better mimic the diverse and dynamic nature of B5G networks and the cyber threats they face.

11.2 Specific limitations

11.2.1 Automated framework to emulate B5G network topologies

In the first development Chapter 6, the primary objective has been to design and implement an emulation framework capable of creating B5G network topologies, executing cyberattack scenarios, and recording relevant metrics and results. While the framework successfully

achieved these goals, several specific limitations have been identified that may impact the overall effectiveness and applicability of the system.

One of the key limitations is related to the scalability of the emulation framework. The framework has been designed to operate in both standalone (single physical machine) and distributed (multiple physical machines) environments. However, the experiments have been constrained by the availability of only four physical machines. While the distributed setup provided some improvements, particularly in terms of bandwidth, having access to a greater number of physical machines could further enhance the achievable bandwidth and offer additional insights from different perspectives. The limited number of machines restricts the scope of the experiments and may not fully capture the potential of the framework in larger-scale deployments.

In the standalone system, it has been observed that the self-protection loop became unstable when emulating 64 UEs, leading to suboptimal performance. The distributed emulation setup, while offering some improvement, still managed to stop only about 50% of the attack within the 2-minute window. Although this represents an advancement over the state-of-the-art, the emulation system's reliance on physical resources remains a significant limitation. The framework's performance is heavily dependent on the available hardware, and the limited computational power of the physical machines used in the experiments likely contributed to the observed instability and incomplete mitigation.

Another limitation of the framework lies in its dependence on the version of the network emulator used. The CORE emulator, which serves as the backbone of the emulation framework, is continuously evolving, with the community regularly releasing new versions. However, the version used in this project has been the last one compatible with the specific topology files utilized in the experiments. To maintain compatibility with the latest updates of the emulator, the framework itself would require updates to support new versions of the topology files. This dependency on an evolving emulator presents a challenge for the continued use and development of the framework.

Lastly, although the emulator allows for the connection of physical devices to the emulated topology, the framework currently does not support the integration of physical wireless UEs.

Such integration would likely provide more accurate and insightful data, particularly in scenarios involving mobile devices. Instead, these connections had to be emulated, which may not fully reflect the behavior of real-world wireless UEs.

11.2.2 Cognitive Self-Protection Framework for B5G-IoT Security

In the second development Chapter 7, the primary objective has been to design and implement a cognitive self-protection loop that is aware of the 5G-IoT topology, making it capable of detecting, analyzing, and mitigating DDoS attacks in scenarios involving network topologies with 2 and 4 Edge servers. While the chapter achieved its goals, several specific limitations emerged that need to be addressed for further refinement and application of the system.

Some of the limitations identified in this chapter are inherited from the previous chapter, as the same emulation framework has been utilized to execute the experiments. As a result, issues such as scalability and bandwidth constraints remain present. The limited number of physical machines and the associated constraints on emulation performance directly impact the self-protection loop's ability to operate effectively in larger or more complex network environments.

Another significant limitation is the variability of DDoS attacks used in the experiments. Designing and executing diverse cyberattacks is time-consuming, and for each new attack, a corresponding Snort rule must be studied and created to ensure the NFM component can detect the threat reliably. This requirement for custom rules adds complexity and limits the framework's ability to respond dynamically to a wide range of attack vectors.

The variability in network topology during the experiments has been primarily focused on modifying the number of connected UEs, antennas, and Edge servers. While this provided valuable insights, the topology could be further diversified by altering the number of Core servers, interdomain connections, and DSPs.

A limitation identified in the results is related to the NSH component. The NSH proved to be the most challenging to enhance due to its complexity in creating mitigation plans for DDoS attacks. In many cases, the NSH consumed up to 90% of the total time required to stop an attack when considering the three core components—NFM, NSH, and NSP. This

significant time consumption highlights a clear limitation in the control and management planes of the 5G-IoT network, impacting the system's overall responsiveness to threats. This limitation is addressed in the subsequent chapter, where the distribution of control and management planes is explored as a means to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the self-protection loop.

11.2.3 Distributed Autonomous Loops for DDoS Protection in 5G/6G-IoT Networks

In the third development Chapter 8, the primary objective was to design and implement a distributed cognitive self-protection loop that is aware of the 5G/6G topology, enabling it to detect, analyze, and mitigate DDoS attacks in such network environments. While the chapter successfully demonstrated the benefits of a distributed approach, several specific limitations were identified, many of which are rooted in challenges encountered in the previous chapters.

One of the significant limitations present in this chapter, as with the previous ones, is related to the emulation framework used to execute the experiments. As a result, scalability and bandwidth constraints remain critical issues. The limitations of the software components within the cognitive self-protection loop continue to study the system's overall performance in larger, more complex scenarios.

The results from this chapter highlight the advantages of distributing the control and management planes across the network's stakeholders, resulting in a significant enhancement in the number of connected infected UEs that can be mitigated. Specifically, the system demonstrated an increase in capacity from 64 to 128 UEs with 100% mitigation, an improvement over the results from the previous chapter. However, when scaling up to 256 UEs, a new limitation emerged, revealing the system's struggles to maintain its effectiveness at this higher level of complexity. This indicates that while the distributed approach offers clear benefits, there are still challenges to be addressed in supporting even larger-scale deployments.

Moreover, the distribution of the management plane showed a notable improvement in the execution of the Planner, a crucial component of the NSH identified as a bottleneck in

the previous chapter. This improvement points to a limitation within the DB that stores the relevant information needed for the NSH to function effectively. The performance of the NSH appears to be closely tied to the efficiency and responsiveness of this DB, and the observed limitations suggest that further optimization or restructuring of the data storage and retrieval processes may be necessary to fully realize the potential of the distributed self-protection loop.

11.2.4 Intelligent DDoS Protection Strategies for 5G-IoT and Beyond

In the fourth development Chapter 9, the primary objective was to develop an AI/ML model capable of classifying six distinct classes, including three types of DDoS attacks and three legitimate network traffic patterns, specifically for B5G network topologies. This classification leveraged information from two critical domains: network topology and flow. While the chapter successfully demonstrated the potential of AI/ML in enhancing network security, several specific limitations were identified that could impact the broader applicability and effectiveness of the proposed solution.

One of the core limitations in this chapter, as in the previous ones, is the reliance on the distributed version of the B5G network emulation framework. While this distributed setup provided a necessary foundation for the research, the previously identified limitations in bandwidth and scalability persisted.

Another significant limitation pertains to the variability in both the DDoS attacks and the legitimate traffic patterns used in the experiments. The limited diversity of these inputs restricted the performance of the ML models, as a more varied and comprehensive dataset would likely result in more robust and generalizable models.

Although the results achieved in this chapter are promising—particularly with the HGBC model, which demonstrated over 98% accuracy even when the network topology was altered—there remains a clear opportunity to explore a wider array of ML and deep learning (DL) models.

Finally, a notable limitation is the lack of available 5G network datasets for DDoS attacks within the research community. This scarcity makes it challenging to fully evaluate

the implications and effectiveness of the proposed dataset and model in a broader context. Without sufficient comparative datasets, it is difficult to ascertain how the developed solution stacks up against other potential approaches.

Chapter 12

Conclusions and Future work

Throughout the course of this PhD research, significant advancements have been made in the domains of B5G network emulation, automation, and cybersecurity. The key findings from each of the main chapters can be summarized as follows:

Automated framework to emulate B5G network topologies

Chapter 6 introduces a novel automation framework for deploying B5G network topologies and executing cybersecurity experiments in telecommunications. The framework is distinguished by its robust architecture and orchestration capabilities, which seamlessly interact with the host, emulator, and network emulated nodes. Its main goals include automating the deployment of emulated B5G topologies, facilitating experiment execution, and enabling the switch between predefined use cases. The framework also supports the distribution and orchestration of these topologies across multiple physical host machines.

The experimental evaluation highlights the framework's effectiveness and efficiency. Notably, the execution times for standalone and distributed setups show an increase as the number of UEs grows, with the fastest distributed experiment taking 699 seconds and the slowest 1191 seconds. Despite the longer execution times in distributed setups, the framework offers other benefits, such as higher bandwidth. For instance, while the standalone setup achieves up to 97.14% of the expected bandwidth at lower loads, it drops to 46.62% under higher loads (4096 Mbps). Conversely, the distributed setup maintains performance, achieving 99.93% of expected bandwidth at 128 Mbps and 51% at 4096 Mbps.

In self-protection experiments, the framework effectively automates deployment and execution, consistently detecting, planning, and mitigating cybersecurity threats. The recorded metrics provide valuable insights into the framework's and the emulated infrastructure's behavior. Key benefits include a robust architecture that ensures smooth orchestration of complex topologies, enhanced automation that reduces manual effort and errors, and scalability that supports large-scale B5G network emulations across multiple machines.

Cognitive Self-Protection Framework for 5G-IoT Security

The work in Chapter 7 introduces a novel topology-aware Cognitive Self-protection loop tailored for 5G-IoT multi-tenant networks, capable of autonomously detecting and mitigating cyber-attacks originating from compromised IoT devices and sensors. The loop is designed to handle the complexities of network traffic in these infrastructures, which often involve multiple levels of nested tunneling and encapsulation protocols, such as GTP, VXLAN, and GRE.

The system was empirically validated in an emulated testbed using the the framework presented in Chapter 6 to deploy the 5G-IoT topology. Initial results are promising, showing that the proposed solution can halt a DDoS attack from 16 to 64 infected UEs within 41 seconds in the worst-case scenario, with even better performance in more complex scenarios involving 4 Edge nodes and 16 gNBs, where mitigation takes just 23 seconds. In a second set of experiments, it was observed that TC performs slightly better than OVS for mitigation. However, the system struggles with high numbers of UEs; it is unable to mitigate all malicious network flows within the 2-minute time window when 64 infected UEs are involved.

Future work will focus on exploring the scalability, efficiency, and performance of the cognitive self-protection loop in terms of network size, including the number of UEs, Edge nodes, and CORE nodes. Additionally, the authors plan to investigate the distribution of the Management and Control planes across different stakeholders in the B5G topology to further enhance the self-protection loop's efficiency.

Distributed Autonomous Loops for DDoS Protection in 5G/6G IoT Networks

In Chapter 8, it is investigated the novel concept of a collaborative self-protection system within 5G/6G networks, enabling different stakeholders to autonomously detect,

analyze, and orchestrate the mitigation of massive DDoS attacks. The approach enhances security for stakeholders without requiring direct information exchange, allowing them to work collaboratively while maintaining autonomy. The effectiveness of the self-protection loop—comprising components such as NIDS, SMA, Analyser, Decision Maker, Planner, Orchestrator, and FCA—has been thoroughly tested, demonstrating its capability to manage the detection, analysis, and coordination necessary for protecting network resources.

The system has proven equally effective across various dynamically changing network topologies, exhibiting sufficient intelligence and reactivity to detect and mitigate attacks even as new infected IoT devices are added. The primary contribution of this work—distributing protection efforts among multiple stakeholders—has shown superior performance in both execution time and the number of mitigated attacks compared to traditional approaches, where only the infrastructure provider handled protection. Empirical results indicate that this distributed system can stop and recover from DDoS attacks involving many attackers in under a minute, reducing potential downtime costs from \$3M to approximately \$1,900 per incident, thanks to a response time as short as 20 seconds.

The simultaneous execution of protection loops across different stakeholders creates a multi-layer defense system, leveraging distributed resources for enhanced cybersecurity. This modular and extensible architecture allows for the addition of new functionalities and mitigation strategies tailored to specific threats.

Intelligent DDoS Protection Strategies for 5G-IoT and Beyond

The research introduces a novel dataset designed for 5G-IoT multi-tenant and multi-encapsulated traffic, featuring six distinct network traffic classes intended for classification by ML models. This dataset includes aggregated features and metrics of 5G-IoT network flows across monitored interfaces, providing in-depth insights into flow and network behavior. The study emphasizes the selection of the HGBC for its resilience and ability to classify network flows in various topology scenarios.

The results underscore the critical role of metric aggregation in generating fine-grained data necessary for training AI models to classify 5G network threats. The study evaluated the performance of four ML models—RFC, ETC, SVMC, and HGBC—using the designed

dataset. Among these, HGBC demonstrated superior performance, achieving accuracy and F1-scores exceeding 98.62% in both evaluated scenarios, highlighting its effectiveness in threat classification within complex 5G network environments.

These contributions collectively advance the state of the art in B5G networks, offering practical tools and methodologies that address current challenges in network automation and cybersecurity.

Building on the findings and contributions of this research, several directions for future work are proposed:

- **Extended Use Cases:** Future research should explore additional use cases and scenarios to further validate and expand the capabilities of the developed emulation tool and cognitive self-protection framework. This could include more multi-domain networks, 6G AI-control networks, inclusion of real devices and 5G System emulators such as Open5GS [122].
- **Advanced AI Models:** There is potential to enhance the threat detection and mitigation capabilities by exploring more advanced AI models and techniques. Future studies could investigate the use of DL, RL, and other cutting-edge AI methodologies to improve accuracy and responsiveness in detecting and countering cyber threats. Additionally, create more diverse network traffic patterns from multiple use cases to achieve a more realistic B5G dataset.

In conclusion, this PhD research has significantly advanced the understanding and application of network emulation, automation, and cybersecurity in B5G networks. The developed tools and frameworks provide robust solutions for automated network deployment, experiment execution, and threat mitigation, setting a new standard for future research and practice. By integrating AI-enabled predictive intelligence and creating comprehensive datasets, this work offers valuable resources and methodologies for enhancing network security and resilience. The findings and contributions of this research not only address current challenges but also pave the way for future innovations in the rapidly evolving field of B5G and beyond.

As we look to the future, continued exploration and interdisciplinary collaboration will be key to maintaining and advancing the security and performance of next-generation networks.

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